

Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Ecological and Hydrological Restoration Planning Component: Phase 1 of the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative

This project was funded by the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council (RESTORE) through an Interagency Agreement with the U.S. Forest Service (17-IA-11083150).

Keywords: Apalachicola, conservation, decision support, drones, ecosystems, forestry, Gulf Coast, hydrology, imagery, land cover, lidar, longleaf pine, monitoring, natural communities, remote sensing, restoration, riparian, spatial ecology, vegetation, water quality, water quantity, water yield, wetlands

Key Contributors

<p>Paul Medley, RESTORE Program Specialist Co-Director, Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration @ Florida A&M University USDA, Forest Service, National Forests in Florida 325 John Knox Rd., Tallahassee, FL 32307 paul.b.medley@usda.gov</p>	<p>Jason Drake, RESTORE Program Specialist Co-Director, Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration @ Florida A&M University USDA, Forest Service, National Forests in Florida 325 John Knox Rd., Tallahassee, FL 32307 Jason.drake@usda.gov</p>
<p>Joseph St. Peter, Research Scientist National Center for Landscape Fire Analysis WA Franke College of Forestry and Conservation University of Montana 1401 27th Avenue, CHCB #428, Missoula, MT 59812 joseph.stpeter@umt.edu</p>	<p>Jordan Vernon, GIS Manager Office of Agriculture Technology Services FL Department of Agriculture and Consumer Svcs. The Mayo Building 407 South Calhoun Street, Tallahassee, FL 32399 jordan.vernon@FDACS.gov</p>
<p>John Hogland, Research Forester USDA, Forest Service, Rocky Mtn. Research Station 800 East Beckwith Ave., Missoula, MT 59801 john.s.hogland@usda.gov</p>	<p>Benjamin Battle, Gulf of Mexico Restoration PgM USDA, Forest Service, Southern Region 107 McClellan Ln., Harvest, AL 35749 benjamin.battle@usda.gov</p>
<p>Eben Broadbent, Associate Professor Spatial Ecology and Conservation Lab School of Forest, Fisheries, and Geomatics Sciences Forest Ecology & Geomatics University of Florida PO Box 110410, Gainesville, FL 32611 eben@ufl.edu</p>	<p>Angélica M. Almeyda Zambrano, Research Faculty Spatial Ecology and Conservation Lab Tropical Conservation and Development Program Center for Latin American Studies University of Florida P.O. Box 115530, Gainesville, FL 32611 aalmeyda@ufl.edu</p>
<p>Victor Ibeanusi, Dean School of the Environment Frederick S. Humphries Science Research Center Florida A&M University, Tallahassee, FL 32307 victor.ibeanusi@famou.edu</p>	<p>Gang Chen, P.E., Professor Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering FAMU-FSU College of Engineering 2525 Pottsdamer Street, Tallahassee, FL 32310 gchen@eng.famu.fsu.edu</p>
<p>Gabriel Prata, Postdoctoral Researcher Spatial Ecology and Conservation Lab School of Forest, Fisheries, and Geomatics Sciences Forest Ecology & Geomatics University of Florida PO Box 110410, Gainesville, FL 32611 gprata@ufl.edu</p>	<p>Christy Crandall, Ph.D. School of the Environment Frederick S. Humphries Science Research Center Florida A&M University, Tallahassee, FL 32307 christy.crandall@famou.edu</p>
<p>Yudi Wu, Assistant Professor Department of Mechanical & Environmental Engineering Florida Polytechnic University 4700 Research Way, Lakeland, FL 33805, ARC-2265 ywu@floridapoly.edu</p>	<p>Sinan Abood, Research Scientist USDA, Forest Service Biological and Physical Resources (BPR) 201 14th Street, Yates Bldg., Washington, DC 20227 saabood@mtu.edu</p>
<p>Eni Awowale, Scientific Software Developer Goddard Earth Sciences Data & Info. Service Ctr. NASA Goddard Space Flight Center 8800 Greenbelt Rd., Greenbelt, MD 20771 e.awowale@nasa.gov</p>	<p>Ritika Prasai, Research Associate Institute for a Disaster Resilient Texas Ocean and Coastal Studies Building Texas A & M University at Galveston 200 Seawolf Parkway, Galveston, TX 77553 ritiprasai@tamu.edu</p>

Recommended Citation: Medley, P., Drake, J., St. Peter, J., Vernon, J., Hogland, J., Battle, B., Broadbent, E., Zambrano, A., Ibeanusi, V., Chen, G., Prata, G., Crandall C., Wu, Y., Abood, S., Awowale, E., Prasai, R. (2023). Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Ecological and Hydrological Restoration Planning Component: Phase 1 of the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative. Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER) at Florida A&M University. Final Report to the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council, 181 pp.

Document Organization: Despite the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project's brief 5-year timeline, the contents of this manuscript encapsulate decades of meticulous scrutiny, geospatial analysis, and the creation of pragmatic, geospatially-centric land management methodologies. While each section can be independently read by those interested in specific topics, a comprehensive understanding necessitates traversing certain sections dispersed across the document for crucial contextual insights. Numerous hyperlinks are also provided as supplementary information that bolsters the overarching narrative.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	4
Key Findings	7
1 Background	13
1.1 Longleaf Pine Ecosystems and Hydrology of Florida’s Apalachicola Region	13
1.2 BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill.....	22
1.3 RESTORE and The Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council.....	22
2 Tate’s Hell Strategy 1	23
2.1 Project Overview.....	23
2.2 Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 (Planning Component) Deliverables	26
2.3 Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER)	26
2.4 Partnerships and Strategic Support	27
3 Primary Data Acquisition	29
3.1 Field Vegetation Plot Data Collection and RESTORE Field Data Plot Redesign.....	29
3.2 Hydrologic Infrastructure Assessment.....	34
3.3 Lidar Remote Sensing and USGS 3DEP Data Acquisition for the Apalachicola Region.....	41
4 Primary Data Analysis and Secondary Data Development	45
4.1 Hurricane Michael Damage Assessment	45
4.2 Digital Remote Mensuration and the use of Lidar for Forest Structure Estimation.....	52
4.3 Estimating Ecological Condition of Open Pine Forests	64
4.4 Potential Water Yield from Southeastern Pine Forests	74
4.5 Enhanced Flow Path Mapping	80
4.6 Apalachicola Regional Riparian Base Map	82
5 Restoration Opportunities and Insights.....	86
5.1 Highlights, Context and Considerations.....	86

5.2	Potential Water Yield Gain from Land Management Activities	93
5.3	Apalachicola National Forest Road 128 and Other Hydrologic Infrastructure	95
5.4	Apalachicola NF Dragstrip Gully Erosion Site.....	99
5.5	Bluffs of St. Teresa	105
5.6	Telogia Creek Watershed.....	111
5.7	Geographically Isolated Wetlands	114
5.8	Prescribed Fire	116
5.9	Midstory Treatments/Timber Stand Improvements (TSI)	119
5.10	Wildlife Habitat Improvements	120
5.11	Coastal Blue Carbon Stocks and Mangrove Condition Assessments	122
6	Decision Support Systems (DSS)	125
6.1	Regional Restoration Decision Support System (RRDSS) Prototype.....	126
7	Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI) - Strategies 2 & 3.....	134
7.1	ARRI Overview.....	134
7.2	Monitoring	135
8	Ancillary, Opportunistic and Supportive Research	138
8.1	Mapping Historic Natural Communities of the Apalachicola Region	138
8.2	Apalachicola NF Ecological Condition Model (2016)	140
8.3	The Longleaf Mapping Project	144
8.4	Probabilistic Fine Resolution Landcover	152
8.5	Transferable Rapid Hurricane (Windstorm) Timber Stand Damage Workflow	158
8.6	Storm Cloud	163
8.7	UF Gatoreye Preliminary Drone-based Lidar Projects	168
8.8	Partnership for Remote Inventory Status and Management (PRISM)	172
9	Summary and Conclusions	180
10	Acknowledgements.....	181

Executive Summary

This document, along with related scientific and technical methodologies, peer-reviewed publications, procedural reports, web pages, story maps⁺, geospatial datasets, models, software applications, code, visual representations, and collaborative partnerships, captures the depth and breadth of the comprehensive, interagency hydrologic and ecosystem assessments for the Apalachicola

Region¹ of Florida. This is of vital importance primarily because the Apalachicola Region serves as a major source of clean freshwater for the Gulf of Mexico. Additionally, it holds the status of being an international biodiversity hotspot and represents a significant landscape for longleaf pine restoration efforts[‡]. Through these endeavors, the Tate's Hell Strategy 1 (THS1) Project[‡] provides relevant land management insights and identifies key restoration opportunities[‡] for the planning component of THS1, the first stage of a long-term, cooperative restoration effort of the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI[‡]). This effort began by assessing current hydrologic[‡] and ecological conditions[‡] at multiple scales across the Apalachicola Region, including the assessment of major impacts from Hurricane Michael[‡], which made landfall at Mexico Beach, Florida, on October 10, 2018, as a category 5 hurricane, tearing through the region and causing massive damage and loss of life.

On August 17, 2017, as identified in the initial Funded Priorities List (FPL1[‡]), and approved by the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council (GCERC[‡]), the U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA[‡]), U.S. Forest Service (USFS[‡]), National Forests in Florida (NFF[‡]) and the Florida Forest Service (FFS[‡]) received Resources and Ecosystems Sustainability, Tourist Opportunities, and Revived Economies of the Gulf Coast States Act (aka RESTORE Act[‡]) settlement funds from the BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill[‡] to conduct conservation and hydrologic planning and implementation activities on upland areas of Tate's Hell State Forest (THSF[‡]), and the adjoining Apalachicola National Forest (ANF[‡]) both located near the Gulf of Mexico within the Apalachicola Region in the central panhandle of Florida. The THS1 Project was funded for a total of \$7,000,000 and contained both planning and implementation activities for the U.S. Forest Service and Florida Forest Service. A total of \$2,500,000 was allotted for the THS1 planning component within the Apalachicola Region primarily on the ANF, while \$4,050,000 was provided for project implementation on THSF. Furthermore, as part of this project, an additional \$450,000 was allocated for engineering design and environmental compliance efforts. These funds were specifically designated for the implementation of hydrologic restoration components that had been identified as high-priority within the Tate's Hell State Forest (THSF). Extramural funds were also acquired during this study to construct and/or repair hydrologic infrastructure[‡] on the ANF and assess water quality conditions on the New River within the Apalachicola Ranger District[‡].

THS1 (implementation and planning) efforts were built upon the foundational hydrologic assessment and restoration efforts of the FFS and the Northwest Florida Water Management District (NWFWM) on THSF which were thoroughly outlined in the 2009 two-volume study entitled "Tate's Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan" (Executive Summary[‡], Volume I[‡], and Volume II[‡]). Specifically, the goals of the THS1 Project (planning component) undertaken by the USFS NFF were to identify and prioritize hydrologic and upland restoration targets on the ANF and surrounding areas within the region as well as create applicable and transferrable supporting methodologies, tools, data, and derivatives that employ innovative geospatial technology and solutions to help with this effort. THS1 Project planning components include the following deliverables: 1) Landscape scale hydrologic assessment and comprehensive restoration plan (this document and supporting materials), and 2) Geospatially-enabled regional restoration decision support system (RRDSS) prototype[‡]. For consistency, the final hydrologic assessment and proposed restoration plan documents have been combined and paralleled the

¹Defining the precise boundaries of the Apalachicola Region is not uniformly agreed upon. The term "Apalachicola Region" often refers to the vicinity around Apalachicola River, Bay, or City. Yet, consistency in its usage is limited. In this study, we adopted a generalized outline of the Apalachicola Regional Stewardship Alliance (ARSA[‡]) boundary to define our study area. However, the lidar data coverage largely determined the actual extent, which approximated the ARSA region. It's noteworthy that the ARSA partnership's Cooperative Invasive Species Management Area (CISMA) operates throughout the Apalachicola landscape, addressing invasive species, prevention, early detection, rapid response, monitoring, education, and awareness.

accompanying Web Story Maps for illustrative purposes. Originally, the THS1 Project (planning component) had the goal to produce the landscape scale hydrologic assessment and restoration plan for a limited hydrology study, which was a much smaller footprint. However, in many instances, this has been expanded to the entire Apalachicola Region by leveraging the capabilities of landscape-scale remote sensing technology. Currently, the hydrologic plan for forecasting potential restoration activities has been completed for the ANF and many other areas in the Lower Apalachicola River basin as well as the entire study area. The THS1 planning effort summarized in this document and related materials have indeed helped identify high priority watersheds and management areas, which will be the focus of restoration efforts in the subsequent RESTORE-funded ARRI - Strategies 2 & 3 (FY23-27)[‡]. Additionally, THS1 has assisted in the identification of other regional watersheds where restoration can improve ecological conditions[‡] and help increase water yield[‡]. It is important to note that the spatial assessment and prioritization tools and workflows developed in this collaborative endeavor take advantage of the best available data and have been peer reviewed. They are also readily updated/repeated, and in many cases transferred to other areas with similar habitat. The baseline conditions reported in this document will be updated as ARRI management activities proceed, and conditions are monitored using the tools and workflows developed in this effort along with additional field data, lidar and imagery.

Finally, to help extend the impact and utility of RESTORE THS1 Project funds, the USFS entered a partnership with Florida A&M University (FAMU[‡]) — a nationally-ranked Historically Black College and University (HBCU), to consolidate and share scientific resources by establishing the Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER) on the FAMU campus in Tallahassee. This partnership allows for student (undergraduate, graduate, and post-graduate) participation in RESTORE-funded projects and provides opportunities to partner with FAMU faculty and staff to convey additional expertise that expands our competences. To date, the \$2.5 million investment by the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council in the planning component of the THS1 Project has been matched with a total of over \$6.7 million in partner contributions including direct and in-kind support from USDA, USFS, FAMU, University of Florida (UF), U.S. Geological Survey (USGS), Southeast Aquatics Resource Partnership (SARP), Microsoft, NFWFMD and other partners. Our RESTORE Act partners and their contributions have helped to not only develop deliverables described in this document but also lay a solid foundation for the ARRI, which is scheduled to begin in early FY2024. Furthermore, thanks to the leveraging capabilities offered by RESTORE funds and innovative partnerships, the THS1 Project successfully initiated numerous complementary and opportunistic research endeavors[‡]. These initiatives led to the development of cutting-edge geospatial tools, innovative lidar data processing workflows, actionable baseline datasets for forest mensuration covering the entire region, extensive high-resolution probabilistic land cover datasets encompassing millions of acres, groundbreaking field plot data collection techniques, comprehensive spatial databases for hydrologic infrastructure, spatially-detailed geospatial models and workflows for water yield calculations, enhanced methodologies and datasets for mapping stream flow paths, region-wide riparian base maps, repositories of reusable application code, studies on water quality, wildlife habitat modeling, rapid remote damage assessments, and, notably, the largest-ever recorded effort in drone laser scanning (DLS) data collection[‡] as of the time of writing this document.

Figure 1. Mud Swamp/New River Wilderness on the Apalachicola National Forest near Sumatra, Florida (Image by P. Medley, USFS, 2020).

Key Findings

Overall

- The Apalachicola Region exhibits tremendous potential to enhance the quantity and quality of freshwater resources available to wetlands, waterbodies, and the Floridan and surficial aquifers, including the Apalachicola River and Bay, and the Gulf of Mexico. This potential has been demonstrated, in part, by the results of new spatial water yield workflows developed in the Tate's Hell Strategy 1 Project with our collaborators.
- Collaborative partnerships are crucial at every step of the THS1 Project, especially the establishment of the Center for Spatial Ecology and Restoration (CSER) a strategic collaboration between the U.S. Forest Service and Florida A&M University.
- The partnerships, techniques, data and derivatives, workflows, computer code, and results developed in the THS1 Project have been invaluable for establishing a baseline for the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI). Data assets from THS1 will be leveraged for the upcoming ARRI Strategies 2&3 Project (FY24 to FY29).
- Refined and readily available workflows that derive forest metrics from lidar data can help overcome significant data processing bottlenecks and provide land managers, researchers, and the public with valuable information about landscape characteristics at fine spatial resolutions. This allows for more precise, efficient, and economical habitat and ecosystem monitoring, as well as timely disaster response and mitigation and data-driven prescribed fire management.
- Science-based decision support systems can be easily developed using existing commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) and/or open-source technologies. These systems empower land managers to make

cross-boundary contextual decisions at multiple scales by presenting restoration scenarios through user-friendly and widely distributable applications. However, the effectiveness depends upon continued administrative and financial commitments, along with the establishment of common data standards for long-term sustainability. It is essential to have in-house control over these applications, integrating them into existing enterprise computing systems to support proven land management workflows while aligning outcomes with short and long-term planning objectives. Fortunately, the costs involved are comparatively reasonable, particularly when leveraging existing enterprise technology and software licenses, thus yielding economies of scale.

- A mere 30-minute drone-based data collection flight can generate a substantial amount of high-value, relevant raw "ecospatial" data, sufficient for multiple advanced research and development projects. It is conceivable this may result in an overabundance of information previously unseen, which requires additional tools such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) to efficiently capture meaningful results from volumes of high-valued data generated from modern remote sensing technology.

Water Quality and Quantity

- Hydrologic and ecological conditions were assessed and prioritized using repeatable field and geospatial workflows that have been codified, peer-reviewed, and packaged for reuse and transfer to other locations. These workflows serve as springboards for multiple project spinoffs, and also provide a foundation for future endeavors.
- Approximately 2.7 million acres of riparian wetlands were classified within the THS1 Apalachicola study area. Most riparian ecotones occurred in Palustrine Forested Wetlands and Upland Forest landcover classifications.
- Conducting thorough geospatial hydrologic infrastructure assessments is a crucial initial step in any comprehensive, integrated hydrologic study aimed at enhancing water quality and quantity within a given landscape, regardless of its size.
- Understanding the location and condition of existing hydrologic infrastructure offers valuable contextual information regarding hydrologic flow and aids in identifying and prioritizing restoration opportunities. When considered within the spatial context of the larger landscape, restoration projects can yield significantly higher returns on investment. By creating a multi-scale infrastructure and hydrologic geodatabases that encompass both upstream and downstream conditions can significantly improve predictive capacity and help better prioritize restoration targets.
- Analytical planning workflows and codified tools presented in this study provide a solution to estimate potential water yield impacts resulting from changes in vegetative cover prior to the implementation of forest management practices (e.g., timber thinning, planting, and growth). These spatial workflows employ established, peer-reviewed, and field-verified models that, in turn, permit the user to spatially predict potential water yield changes under various scenarios across the landscape at multiple spatial scales. By incorporating this data into contextual information, it may be possible to determine the eventual flow direction or reservoir of increased or decreased water yields following specific management activities.
- CSER has collaborated closely with Apalachicola National Forest (ANF) staff, utilizing THS1 workflows and products to identify high-priority water quality/quantity restoration opportunities. One potential ARRI water quality improvement location is a 2.4-acre gully erosion site on the ANF, where an estimated 17,000 tons of soil have eroded since 2002.
- A collaborative native plant study of the Apalachicola National Forest by the USDA Forest Service Southern Research Station, CSER, FAMU, and FSU identified the ten-angled pipewort (*Eriocaulon decangulare*) as having great phytoremediation potential for metal contamination with capabilities to uptake many heavy metals from natural soils.

- Several CSER-developed products and methods can be leveraged for future water quality/quantity improvements in the Apalachicola Region. Some of these prospects will be implemented in ARRI Strategies 2&3, while others will be targeted in future restoration projects. One focal area for the ARRI will be the Bluffs of Saint Theresa (BoST), an approximately 17,000-acre property recently acquired by the State of Florida with frontage on Ochlockonee Bay and Alligator Harbor situated between Bald Point State Park, Tate’s Hell State Forest, and the Apalachicola National Forest. CSER-developed workflows have already showcased numerous hydrologic and ecological benefits resulting from planned restoration efforts on BoST, which will be spearheaded by the Florida Park Service, Florida Forest Service, and partners from The Nature Conservancy and others. Another proposed project is a collaboration between the US Fish and Wildlife Service and the USDA aimed at enhancing water quality/quantity in the Telogia Creek watershed. This watershed is extremely important as it provides a significant supply of freshwater to the Gulf of Mexico and serves as critical habitat for multiple species of concern including two federally listed freshwater mussels. It also has 12,439 acres of newly acquired conservation lands that will be strategic for bolstering wildlife habitat and improving water quality and quantity in the Apalachicola Region.

Remote Sensing, Field Plots and Ecological Condition

- Baseline geospatial ecological condition modeling, historical natural community data, and accurate field vegetation plots are essential for creating meaningful representations of current and desired future conditions of forested landscapes and ecosystems. These components form the foundation for constructing comprehensive characterizations that enable effective management and conservation strategies.
- Whether using an area-based remote sensing analysis or using individual tree detection (ITD) segmentation methods to build predictive statistical models for estimating wall-to-wall forest structural metrics, it is imperative to collect accurately designed field data plots. Field plots can be established and maintained in perpetuity for continual reuse, which are not uneconomical especially when considering the highly valuable predictive nature of the resultant data produced over time.
- Field vegetation plot data funded by RESTORE collected at the start of THS1, along with dissertation work conducted by Dr. John Hogland of the U.S. Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station to improve the methodology for collecting field data plots, have been immensely valuable for various aspects of this and other projects. Redesigned plot collection methodology facilitates radiometric correction of remotely sensed data providing enhanced data alignment, improved accuracy, and more robust project outcomes that enable long-term multi-dimensional and multi-temporal spatial analyses.
- In the absence of lidar data and field plots, models and outputs developed for NAIP imagery using FIA data can link remotely sensed imagery to FIA plots with reasonable accuracy to help describe forest characteristics in a spatial manner which is an improvement over simply aggregating plot information to large areas (state, county, and other boundaries). These models and outputs can be used not only to describe forests within specific areas, but also to provide information about the condition and spatial pattern of longleaf (and other) pine at relatively fine spatial resolutions.
- Field plot data gathered during the THS1 project has played a crucial role in assessing the extent of damage caused by Hurricane Michael (October 2018), as well as other storms. It has been instrumental in estimating the conditions resulting from storm-related destruction through the utilization of satellite imagery, lidar-based remote sensing, and spatial analytics.

Lidar Data/Analysis for Conservation and Restoration

- Through this project we have successfully created practical, repeatable, scalable, and efficient area-based lidar processing workflows that can extract dozens of meaningful forest structural metrics with very large (10s to 100s of TBs) Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) and Drone Laser Scanning (DLS) point cloud datasets and derivatives.
- Lidar is an excellent and economical tool for determining forest structure over large landscapes or small project areas, however, at this stage of development, there are relatively few standardized practical workflows to derive meaningful forest structural metrics from huge lidar datasets across large landscapes. While area-based lidar data analysis methods work quite well, individual tree detection (ITD) and crown delineation are two of the most relevant and promising methods for extracting accurate and granular forest structural information from lidar at multiple scales.
- Lidar technology provides a robust foundation for the development of improved water flow path maps and higher-resolution hydrologic datasets. Enhanced hydrologic data are invaluable for prioritizing restoration targets, and particularly stream-road crossings within project areas. By utilizing lidar data, restoration efforts can achieve more accurate results and a greater total impact.
- Lidar data are vital and efficient for analyzing gully erosion and quantifying soil loss over time. It is also essential for planning water quality improvement projects to provide crucial contextual information for developing both short-term and long-term solutions and mitigation strategies.
- Forest damage caused by windstorms or other catastrophic events can be effectively estimated using lidar. By establishing and maintaining field data plots in advance, lidar data can be swiftly and cost-effectively collected after a natural disaster to accurately quantify losses, including timber stand damage and other impacts. Lidar data can not only reveal current losses resulting from damage but also help predict future losses over time. For example, the extent of post-storm tree lean can be accurately captured using high-resolution lidar data, precise ground plots, and location information.
- Lidar data are proving immensely valuable in wildlife habitat modeling within the Apalachicola Region, especially for species such as the Frosted Flatwoods Salamander, Red-cockaded Woodpecker, and Gopher Tortoise.
- ALS, DLS, terrestrial laser scanning (TLS), and vehicular laser scanning (VLS) data as well as different types of (often simultaneously collected) RGB, thermal, and hyperspectral imagery data have wide-ranging conservation and restoration applications. They are increasingly accessible through diverse platforms and systems and can be used independently or together.

Drone-based Data Collection for Assessment and Monitoring

- Aerial/terrestrial drone and sensor technologies have advanced at an astonishing pace within the last decade, enabling faster data collection across more expansive areas all while generating ultra-dense and rich datasets and imagery.
- Ultra-dense DLS point cloud data may likely become a standard land management tool, regardless of the data collection platform. This data revolution has been made possible, in part, by the significant technological advancements in novel materials, optical sensor miniaturization, highly accurate inertial management unit (IMU) sensors and geolocation technology, drones, and battery technology all within a relatively short period of time.
- The difference between standard ALS (4-8 points per meter) and advanced DLS and TLS (100s-1000s of points per meter) data is game-changing in terms of visualization, interpretation, prediction, and application.
- Ultra-resolution lidar derivatives can readily be produced from point clouds with densities surpassing 1000 points per meter. This advancement enables the creation of extremely high-

definition data, facilitating the development of next-generation fusion datasets that combine lidar data with imagery at a remarkable level of positional accuracy.

- Colorized lidar point clouds can be combined with RGB, hyperspectral, and thermal imagery, resulting in the creation of digital hypercubes. These digital hypercubes contain dense spatial and spectral information, enabling advanced multi-dimensional, multi-scalar, and multi-temporal analyses. Fusion datasets (lidar + hyperspectral + thermal) possess the potential to offer unprecedented insights into various aspects of forest health (insect and disease outbreaks), forest structure and composition, timber volume, and even the detection of non-native invasive species.
- A unique spinoff project from THS1, made possible by funding from USFS R08, is the Partnership for Remote Inventory, Status, and Management (PRISM) Project which focuses on collecting, analyzing, and applying cutting-edge drone-borne lidar, hyperspectral, and thermal imagery data and derivatives across approximately 350,000 acres of the Apalachicola Ranger District on the Apalachicola National Forest. This project has achieved remarkable success, generating hundreds of terabytes of the most advanced ecospatial data ever collected. Furthermore, this approach is comparatively cost-effective and time-efficient when compared to traditional methods of acquiring lidar and imagery data.
- Economical and timely production of accurate stem maps for entire forests, along with multiple relevant vegetation metrics, can be achieved through the utilization of drone-borne lidar data. This approach is applicable to both large and small landscapes. Individual tree vegetation metrics for entire landscapes can rival or even surpass the accuracy of traditional manual field data collection methods. Through a RESTORE-funded initiative CSER and the University of Florida's Spatial Ecology and Conservation (SPEC) Laboratory have collaborated to successfully generate and field-verify up to 75 accurate metrics per tree that can be used in various analyses.
- CSER and the UF SPEC Lab partnered to develop hurricane/storm damage workflows in the Google Earth Engine (GEE) environment through a project called "Storm Cloud", which is funded by the USFS Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) Program. The project has yielded promising results in rapidly estimating forest damage using post-event imagery from the Sentinel 1 (radar) and Sentinel 2 (imagery) satellites, particularly when combined with lidar data for baseline assessments of forest structure.
- Rapid, single-pass UAV surveys can achieve denser lidar point clouds up to 175 m from the flightline when compared to aircraft. Accurate ground returns can be achieved up to 170 m from the flightline, where only around 0.5% of the scanned area is not covered by ground returns.
- CSER received two AI for Earth grants and collaborated with teams from Microsoft's Azure and Research groups to test workflows developed in a cloud computing environment (Microsoft Azure). These projects successfully demonstrated that both area-based lidar workflows for estimating forest structure and the hurricane storm damage assessment workflows could be effectively executed on the cloud infrastructure while leveraging collocated data and computing resources. However, it is crucial to manage the costs of cloud computing to maximize efficiency compared to local computing approaches by taking advantage of potential economies of scale.

Education and Training

- [Joseph St. Peter](#), CSER Remote Sensing Analyst and FAMU doctoral graduate has been an important part of the CSER Team and influential to its success. During his tenure with CSER, Dr. St. Peter has applied his skills to relevant restoration work ranging from hurricane timber stand damage across the Apalachicola Region to examining different regression models for estimating basal area across large landscapes. Dr. St. Peter has produced multiple refereed publications with the CSER Team and has helped move the restoration/conservation needle on an array of public and private lands across

the State of Florida. Dr. St. Peter graduated with his Ph.D. in Environmental Science from Florida A&M University in August 2023, and is now employed as a Research Scientist at the National Center for Landscape Fire Analysis, University of Montana, Missoula.

- [Jordan Vernon](#), CSER GIS Analyst, has been a long-time key member of the CSER Team. Mrs. Vernon's contributions to all aspects of CSER's daily operations have been invaluable to the Tate's Hell Strategy 1 Project and ARRI. Her peer-reviewed publication which examines Southern U.S. pine forest water yield as a mechanism to help prioritize regional restoration projects has been pivotal for THS1 and ARRI planning purposes and has provided keen insight into the effects of forest management activities on increasing freshwater quantity along the Gulf Coast. Mrs. Vernon is currently the GIS Manager for the Office of Agriculture Technology Services at the Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Tallahassee, FL.
- [Gabriel Prata](#), a Postdoctoral Researcher funded by RESTORE/CSER at the University of Florida's Spatial Ecology & Conservation (SPEC) Laboratory, has made significant contributions to the THS1 Project. Dr. Prata's work with drone-borne lidar technology has been exceptional, demonstrating the ability to identify damaged and fallen trees in UAS-derived lidar point clouds, even with a rapid, single-pass scanning technique. Additionally, Dr. Prata's collaboration with the U.S. Forest Service-funded Storm Cloud Project has shown the potential for near-real-time remote forest damage assessments. He continues to actively collaborate with CSER on research projects through the UF SPEC Lab.
- [Christy Crandall](#), a FAMU Environmental Science doctoral student helped pioneer CSER's work identifying, prioritizing, and selecting areas for pine basal area reduction to maximize water yields in pine forests in her doctoral dissertation entitled "*A Novel Method to Increase Soil Water Yields in Pine Forests of the Northern Gulf Coast, USA*". Dr. Crandall graduated with her Ph.D. in Environmental Science from FAMU in Summer 2021 and is currently working as an environmental consultant in her home state of Indiana.
- [Yudi Wu](#), a FAMU-FSU College of Engineering doctoral student who worked closely with CSER researchers on a USFS Southern Research Station, Florida Forest Watershed Research Program funded project in collaboration with the FAMU-FSU College of Engineering to examine the impact of failing drainage culverts on water quality within an iron non-attainment watershed in the New River sub-basin. Dr. Wu provided detailed insights into water quality in the New River focusing on areas with drainage culverts. Dr. Wu's diligent work resulted in two peer-reviewed publications including an assessment of the long-term As, Pb, and Cr contamination and uptake by the ten-angled pipewort (*Eriocaulon decangulare*) in the Apalachicola National Forest. After working as a Postdoctoral Researcher with the Department of Environmental & Sustainable Engineering, College of Engineering and Applied Sciences at the University at Albany, State University of New York, she is currently an assistant professor of Environmental Engineering at Florida Polytechnic University in Lakeland, FL.
- [Eni Awowale](#), during her summer internship at CSER, achieved success by developing and implementing water yield workflows using Python. Her work aimed to support CSER staff in modeling and assessing potential water yield improvements resulting from different proposed forest management activities across the entire Apalachicola Region. This workflow, documented in a peer-reviewed publication, played a pivotal role in propelling Ms. Awowale's career in Spatial Ecology. Currently, she holds the position of Scientific Software Developer at NASA's Goddard Space Flight Center in Greenbelt, MD.
- [Ritika Prasai](#), during her summer internship at CSER, took the lead in creating an innovative land use and land cover classification workflow using Google Earth Engine. This workflow, based on Python and making the most of the platform's cloud-computing capabilities and open-source tools, was able

to efficiently process high-resolution (1m) multi-band NAIP imagery over a large landscape in just minutes. The effectiveness of this workflow has been confirmed through a peer-reviewed publication and was instrumental in securing Ms. Prasai a position as a Research Associate at the Institute for a Disaster Resilient Texas, Texas A & M University after completing her M.S. degree at Tarleton State University in Stephenville, TX.

- Edward (Jax) Duncan served as an undergraduate assistant at CSER for several semesters while pursuing his degree in Environmental Science at Florida A&M University. During his time at CSER, Mr. Duncan collaborated with the staff on various projects, and he also acquired his Remote Pilot Certificate under the FAA's Small UAS Rule (Part 107).

Summary and Future

- The techniques developed in THS1 have broad applicability beyond just the Gulf Coast Region, extending to other projects in various states within the U.S. and even to other countries worldwide.
- Monitoring the effectiveness of ARRI Strategies 2&3 management activities to improve hydrologic and ecological conditions will greatly benefit from the comprehensive geospatial analyses conducted in THS1. The insights gained from this work have already been applied to other regional restoration projects, making the monitoring efforts more robust and reliable.
- Lidar is vital for ecosystem and hydrologic restoration, and its significance will continue to grow. The lidar sensor has emerged as one of the most significant contemporary devices for landscape-scale restoration due to its crucial role in simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM). When coupled with miniaturized ultra-resolution image capture devices and various highly mobile data collection platforms, we may very well be on the brink of a land management data revolution.
- Digital forest structural information and imagery may likely be incorporated into the “Metaverse” to be used by future land managers in a hypothetical iteration of the Internet presented as a single, universal, and immersive virtual world facilitated by virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technology to help study and plan land management activities.
- Artificial Intelligence will soon become a dominant force in global society and bring about immense technological shifts in virtually every aspect of public and private society including land management, conservation, and restoration.

1 Background

1.1 Longleaf Pine Ecosystems and Hydrology of Florida’s Apalachicola Region

Southeastern longleaf pine (*Pinus palustris*) forests such as those in the Apalachicola Region of Florida are highly resilient ecosystems capable of withstanding droughts, fires, floods, high winds, wildlife damage, and pests when compared to other native pine forest habitats (The Nature Conservancy, 2023). These ecosystems are generally termed fire-climax plant communities since fire is the dominating control factor of forests in the final stage of ecological succession (climax) which is thought to be at “equilibrium” with existing environmental conditions. In other words, frequent natural fire regimes help achieve and maintain desired forest structure and function within native longleaf pine communities. Longleaf ecosystems support multiple habitat types ranging from wet flatwoods and savannahs to xeric sandhills and rocky mountainous ridges. While mature longleaf forests are varied environments, they typically have open canopies with low basal areas, sparse mid- and understories as well as a diverse, uninterrupted herbaceous layer (Kirkman, Mitchell, Helton, & Drew, 2001; Platt, 1999; Walker & Peet, 1985). An outstanding factor of these cherished ecosystems is ground cover diversity which alone positions it within the most species rich plant communities outside the tropics (Brockway, Outcalt, Tomczak & Johnson, 2005; Peet & Allard, 1993). Up to 900 plant species are found only in longleaf forest habitats rivaling some tropical forest ecosystems (USDA NRCS, 2020), to which an

estimated 2 million acres of undeveloped public and private forest lands in the Apalachicola Region are central to it being designated as a North American biodiversity “hotspot” (Blaustein, 2008; Stein, Kutner & Adams, 2000), and a “significant landscape” for longleaf pine conservation and restoration (America’s Longleaf, 2009).

Longleaf ecosystems, as depicted in Figure 1.1.1, originally spanned approximately 92 million acres across the Southeastern U.S., extending from Virginia to Texas and from the southern Appalachian Region to the Atlantic and Gulf Coasts (Frost, 1993, 2007), but by 1995 had dwindled to less than 3 million acres, existing only as isolated patches within their historic range (Landers, van Lear & Boyer, 1995; Oswalt et al., 2012). Over the course of much of the past century, numerous factors have contributed to the decline of longleaf pine woodlands. These factors include urban development, non-forest land uses, habitat reduction due to fire suppression, and the replacement of longleaf pine forests with pine plantations managed for timber production (Peet & Allard, 1993).

The substitution of native longleaf pine habitat with slash pine (*Pinus elliottii*) plantations for timber production is a complex and contentious matter, carrying significant environmental, economic, and ecological consequences. In the Southeast, where both longleaf and slash pine species are present, including the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project area, slash pine plantations typically comprise densely planted, uniformly aged stands of rapidly growing trees cultivated for timber. While slash pine’s shorter rotation period can lead to more frequent timber harvests and potentially increased profits for landowners and the timber industry, it can have profound implications for ecosystem health, fire ecology, biodiversity, wildlife, soil, and water quality/quantity.

As mentioned earlier, longleaf pine ecosystems are renowned for their ecological richness, serving as vital habitats for a diverse array of plant and animal species, many of which are threatened or endangered. Because longleaf pine forests have evolved with fire as an essential component, they often necessitate controlled burns for their preservation and effective management. In contrast, the management of slash pine forests and pine plantations in general require different management strategies, exerting influence on broader ecosystem dynamics. Consequently, the shift from longleaf to slash pine can and has perturbed native habitats, potentially resulting in declines among imperiled species. Furthermore, slash pine may not offer the same soil and water quality benefits, impacting downstream environments, primarily due to the hydrological alterations commonly associated with pine plantation practices such as ditching and bedding.

Dedicated efforts are underway to restore and conserve longleaf pine ecosystems due to their ecological significance and resilience. Various organizations and government agencies are working towards protecting and rejuvenating these forests through incentives, land management techniques, and conservation initiatives like the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project. Numerous endeavors now aim to strike a balance between timber production and the conservation of native ecosystems. In some instances, land managers employ a combination of longleaf and slash pine where appropriate or implement adaptive management practices to harmonize timber production with ecological conservation objectives. This approach seeks to maintain some of the ecological advantages of longleaf pine while simultaneously meeting economic goals.

However, the challenges are not limited to land management decisions alone. The devastating impacts of Hurricane Michael in 2018 further compounded the difficulties faced by regional longleaf pine ecosystems. This catastrophic event affected at least 28% of the remaining global longleaf pine extent (Zampieri, Pau & Okamoto, 2020), resulting in extensive tree mortality across 18 counties and damaging an estimated \$1.3 billion worth of timber on approximately 2.8 million acres of land (Florida Forest Service, 2018). These factors have had and continue to have profound and enduring effects on regional longleaf ecosystems and their hydrology. Consequently, a holistic and revitalizing approach to landscape restoration is imperative. To this end, the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project encompasses the

examination of upland forest ecology, concurrent hydrological resources, and the utilization of cutting-edge geospatial technology and decision-support resources to better manage this precious resource.

The central panhandle of Florida collectively possesses substantial conservation land holdings, encompassing federal, state, and private ownership. In numerous locations, historical longleaf stands have been logged and then densely replanted with non-native species such as off-site slash or sand pine (*Pinus clausa*). To effectively restore these areas, it is imperative to gain a comprehensive understanding of their current ecological composition and their historical distribution of natural communities, both within the specific site and in relation to neighboring areas across the region. Furthermore, it is crucial to formulate a vision for the desired future conditions, a topic that will be discussed in detail later in this manuscript. Site-specific factors, including structural characteristics, overstory species, groundcover composition, and the surrounding habitat, all play a significant role in shaping potential restoration outcomes. These factors, in turn, inform alternative management approaches, which may involve strategies like thinning and continued prescribed burns, rather than resorting to clear-cutting and the reintroduction of longleaf pine and/or groundcover species.

Figure 1.1.1. Longleaf pine stand located on the Apalachicola National Forest exhibiting excellent ecological condition with high-quality groundcover (Image by J. Drake, USFS, 2016).

At first glance, the Apalachicola Region seems intuitively wet. For local inhabitants this is a known fact, but while this is true, forest cover characteristically belies the extent of hydrological and riparian influences[‡]. Within longleaf pine ecosystems in the Apalachicola Region, abundant rivers, streams, lakes, ponds, seeps, sinkholes, springs, swallets, swamps and ephemeral wetlands provide valuable ecosystem services in the form of microclimate regulation, floodwater storage, natural filtration (McLaughlin & Cohen, 2013), and recharge/discharge functions for one of the most productive aquifer systems in the world—the Floridan aquifer (Miller, 1986, 1990). Consequently, freshwater outflows from forested lands into tributaries, rivers, waterbodies, and aquifers are vital elements that structure physical, biogeochemical, and hydrologic functions in the longleaf pine ecosystems of the region, and thus the biological communities that inhabit them. Timing, quantity, and quality are

essential for freshwater flows from upland forests that move nutrients, change salinity, and total suspended solid levels, which directly impacts riverine and estuarine productivity, distribution of species, and phenology (Brown, Hobbins & Ramirez, 2008; Livingston, 1984; Scavia et al., 2002). Because surface water hydrology is inextricably connected to groundwater and aquifer recharge and/or discharge, Florida's groundwater supplies and therefore aquifers play a central role in surface water body conditions which in turn impacts spring flow, streamflow, and water levels in lakes and wetlands, as well as coastal salinity, saltwater intrusion, and ultimately overall ecosystem and biological community health. Because the Apalachicola Region has a significant proportion of managed, conservation lands as compared to other parts of Florida, managed forests play a vital role in the regional water cycle. In fact, it has been estimated that surface water from forest lands can reliably provide some of the highest quality water that constitutes as much as 50% of the total surface water yield (Liu et al., 2021). Moreover, long-term variations in climate are projected to cause seasonal shifts in runoff and sediment further affecting system phenology, migration, breeding, and distributions (Hovenga, Wang, Medeiros, Hagen & Alizad, 2016). Also worth mentioning are the recent significant reductions in freshwater discharge from the Apalachicola River resulting from greater upstream water use and storage which has coincided with noticeable reductions in the productivity of Apalachicola's commercially and culturally important seafood industries (Florida Sea Grant, 2020). This should further underscore the cruciality of managing quality and quantity of regional freshwater that flows from managed forests into tributaries and rivers to help maintain baseflow and replenish groundwater supplies and aquifers.

The Floridan Aquifer, which underlies all Florida, parts of Alabama, Georgia, Mississippi, and South Carolina, provides drinking water for many major cities including Jacksonville, Orlando, and Tallahassee (Pascale & Wagner, 1982). The Floridan is subdivided vertically into upper and lower aquifers although it primarily functions as one aquifer over most of its extent (Miller, 1990; Williams & Kuniasky, 2016). The surficial (unconfined) aquifer system, which sits on top of a large portion of the Floridan Aquifer (Figure 1.1.2), functions as an important source-sink layer for temporary storage of groundwater that can recharge the underlying Floridan system (SWFWMD, 2020; Williams & Kuniasky, 2016). In the Apalachicola Region, the Floridan Aquifer is recharged by downward leakage of water from the surficial sand aquifer as well as from the water-bearing zone of the upper confining unit. It can also be recharged directly by rainfall in northern Leon County or in southern Georgia where the Floridan is at or near the land surface. Ground water enters the system in the northern part of the region and moves toward the southeast from the potentiometric high in southwestern Gadsden County and south from Leon County toward Wakulla Springs located about 10 miles south of Tallahassee (Pascale & Wagner, 1982). It cannot be overstated how critical the shallow surficial aquifer system is to not only the Apalachicola Region, but to the entire Southeastern U.S.

Figure 1.1.2. Major aquifers located at Florida’s land surface (from FDEP, 2015[†]).

In general, water entering the ground from rainfall is subject to evapotranspiration (ET), stream baseflow, discharge to the coast, or recharge to deeper aquifers (FDEP, 2015; Bush & Johnston, 1988). Depending on the hydrologic conditions and/or location, water bodies can serve as both recharge and discharge areas for aquifers. For instance, when water levels in lakes, ponds or streams are higher than the surrounding groundwater, they can provide recharge to the aquifer. On the other hand, when aquifer water levels are higher than adjacent surface water bodies, then the surface water can receive groundwater discharge. As mentioned previously, many forested areas in the Apalachicola Region have deviated from their desired ecological condition over the years for a variety of reasons which has resulted in numerous overly dense forest stands of off-site pine species planted in very wet areas around the region. These dense stands of thirsty trees can be incredible sources of water loss to the atmosphere through ET (Allen, Breshears & Macdowell, 2015; Cohen, McLaughlin, Kaplan & Acharya, 2020; Hudson, Samuelson & Dixon, 2005; Swank & Corssley, 1988; Tague & Band, 2001). Water not returned to the atmosphere by ET (a significant percentage), direct runoff into water bodies, or removed by pumping for municipal or agriculture supplies percolates downward into the surficial aquifer system which can recharge the Floridan aquifer or move laterally through the surficial system until it discharges to surface waterbodies and flows downstream to estuaries and bays. This process helps maintain the subtle balance of salinity which continues to be an issue of major concern in Apalachicola Bay. Accordingly, increased ET can shift the fraction of precipitation that runs off as surface water or infiltrates as aquifer recharge. Long-term shifts in recharge patterns can change groundwater levels and

subsequently groundwater-surface water interactions and soil moisture (Condon & Maxwell, 2017) which then disrupt the balance, create a negative feedback loop, and further impact forested ecosystems, hydrologic resources, wetlands, and biological communities scattered across the region.

In the coastal plain of the Apalachicola Region, there are countless unpaved roads, failing and degraded drainage culverts, and poorly maintained or designed ditches, which contribute to movement of sedimentation and nutrients. Replacement of substandard culverts, installing wing ditches, ditch plugs, and low-water crossings are specific hydrologic improvement strategies proven to result in better water quality and quantity when designed and installed properly (Clarkin, Keller, Warhol & Nixon, 2006; Gautam & Bhattarai, 2018; Sharpley et al., 2007; Vadas et al., 2007). For example, when stream flows approach culvert design capacity, or when culverts fail, water tends to pond upstream of inlets, causing sedimentation and bank erosion. Proper engineering of road crossing structures can minimize channel blockage during high sediment-transporting flows to help mitigate erosion and sediment deposition.

Simple low-water crossings are comparatively inexpensive structures that are beneficial when used across ephemeral streams where regular flow depth is low (Gautam & Bhattarai, 2018). They are highly useful in naturally unstable channels, or in channels with extreme flow variations (Clarkin, Keller, Warhol & Nixon, 2006). Because they are not as obstructive, they are less likely to cause flow diversions or accelerations which can worsen channel instability. Unlike culverts that can be damaged or plugged by debris, low-water crossings are good for “storm-proofing” roads where large amounts of sediment and debris are expected following big storms or wildfires.

Roadside ditches are a very common feature in the Apalachicola Region, particularly in timber production areas where excessively wet soil conditions limit tree growth and access to harvesting. While ditches have been a boon for slash pine timber production in wet areas, they have a significant downside in that they serve as pathways for sediment, nutrients, and pollutants from adjacent lands (e.g., nitrogen and phosphorus). For example, if soils are phosphorus rich, ditches can serve as a mobilizing mechanism (Sharpley et al., 2007). In this region, ditches can create alternating conditions of drying and wetting. During dry periods, wetland soils are oxidized and aerobic decomposition of soil organic matter increases, which increases the potential for soils to release phosphorus. When the water table rises, released phosphorus can be transported to ditches via subsurface flow (Vadas et al., 2007). Extended periods with saturated conditions can create anoxia or hypoxia, which can result in ferric iron being reduced to ferrous iron. Ferric iron holds phosphorus while ferrous iron releases it. Therefore, strategies to improve water quality should include reducing drainage scope and the effect of ditches that can export mobilized phosphorus, but also capture some mobile phosphorus already in the waterway. This is particularly the case for the 202,436-acre Tate’s Hell State Forest (THSF), which shares much of its boundary and multiple watersheds with the 576,680-acre Apalachicola National Forest (ANF). In the 1950s and 1960s, roadside ditches were excavated in THSF to provide road fill material, and to drain adjacent wetlands where pine stands were often bedded, planted at high densities, and fertilized with nitrogen and phosphorus (NFWFMD, 2009a, 2009b, 2009c). In fact, it is this same silvicultural activity that created most of the hydrologic concerns for THSF and adjacent waters. In general, water quality in and around the largely undeveloped area is good, but the effects of ditching and bedding are the most significant source of water quality degradation (Robert, Crisman, Anderson & Kendell, 2000). As well, natural fire regimes were suppressed in the 50s and 60s resulting in large-scale habitat alterations which have impacted historical ecological communities, and the magnitude, timing, and quality of surface water runoff discharged from Tate’s Hell Swamp to Apalachicola Bay, East Bay, St. George Sound, and surrounding waters (NFWFMD, 2009a, 2009b, 2009c). The State of Florida began purchasing the property from timber companies in 1994 with the specific goal of re-establishing historic surface water drainage patterns, improving water quality of surface runoff into the Apalachicola Bay system, and restoring wetland ecosystems (NFWFMD, 2009a, 2009b, 2009c). Since then, much

restoration work has been accomplished on THSF and adjacent lands within the lower Apalachicola Region (NFWFMD, 2022).

References

- Allen, C. D., Breshears, D. D., & McDowell, N. G. (2015). On underestimation of global vulnerability to tree mortality and forest die-off from hotter drought in the Anthropocene. *Ecosphere*, 6(8), 1-55. <https://doi.org/10.1890/ES15-00203.1>
- Blaustein, R. J. (2008). Biodiversity hotspot: The Florida panhandle. *BioScience* 58(9), 784–790. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.1641/b580904>
- Brockway, D., Outcalt, K., Tomczak, D., & Johnson, E. (2005). *Restoration of longleaf pine ecosystems* (Gen. Tech. Rep. SRS-83) U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Southern Research Station. <https://www.srs.fs.usda.gov/pubs/20672>
- Brown, T., Hobbins, M., & Ramirez, J. (2008). Spatial Distribution of Water Supply in the Conterminous United States. *Journal of the American Water Resources Association*, 44(6), 1474-1487. https://www.fs.usda.gov/rm/value/docs/spatial_distribution_water_supply.pdf
- Bush, P., & Johnston, R. (1988). *Ground-water hydraulics, regional flow, and ground-water development of the Floridan Aquifer System in Florida and in parts of Georgia, South Carolina, and Alabama*. U.S. (Geological Survey Professional Paper 1403-C). United States Geological Survey. <https://doi.org/10.3133/pp1403C>
- Clarkin, K., Keller, G., Warhol, T., & Hixson, S. (2006). *Low-water Crossings: Geomorphic, Biological, and Engineering Design Considerations*. (Report 0625 1808—SDTDC). U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, National Technology and Development Program. <https://www.fs.usda.gov/t-d/pubs/pdf/LowWaterCrossings/index.shtml>
- Cohen, M. J., McLaughlin, D. L., Kaplan, D. A., & Acharya, S. (2020). Evapotranspiration losses from southern pine plantations during the growing season: patterns, causes, and future implications. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 24(6), 3197-3210. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-24-3197-2020>
- Condon, L. E., & Maxwell, R. M. (2017). Systematic shifts in Budyko relationships caused by groundwater storage changes. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*. 21(2), 1117–1135. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-21-1117-2017>
- Florida Department of Environmental Protection (FDEP). *Source Water Assessment and Protection Program (SWAPP): Aquifer descriptions*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://prodapps.dep.state.fl.us/swapp/Welcome/links/aquifers_v
- Florida Forest Service. (2018, October 19). *Hurricane Michael, Florida Forest Service, Initial Value Estimate of Altered, Damaged or Destroyed Timber in Florida*. Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Florida Forest Service. https://www.fdacs.gov/content/download/82204/file/hurricanemichaelinitialtimberdamageestimate_lite.pdf
- Florida Sea Grant. (2020). *Apalachicola Bay Oyster Situation Report* (TP-200). National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from http://www.oyster-restoration.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/05/tp200_apalachicola_oyster_situation_report.pdf
- Frost, C. C. (1993). Four Centuries of Changing Landscape Patterns in the Longleaf Pine Ecosystem. In S. Hermann (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 18th Tall Timbers fire ecology conference: The longleaf pine ecosystem: ecology, restoration, and management*. Tall Timbers Research Station, Tallahassee, FL. (pp. 17–43). http://www.talltimbers.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/03/Frost1993_op.pdf
- Frost, C. (2007). History and Future of the Longleaf Pine Ecosystem. In S. Jose, E. Jokela, D. Miller (Eds.), *The Longleaf Pine Ecosystem. Springer Series on Environmental Management* (pp. 9-49). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-30687-2_2

- Gautam, S., & Bhattarai, R. (2018). Low-Water Crossings: An Overview of Designs Implemented along Rural, Low-Volume Roads. *Environments* 5(2), 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments5020022>
- Hovenga, P. A., Wang, D., Medeiros, S. C., Hagen, S. C., & Alizad, K. (2016). The response of runoff and sediment loading in the Apalachicola River, Florida to climate and land use land cover change. *Earth's Future*, 4(5), 124–142. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015EF000348>
- Hudson, G., Samuelson, L., & Dixon, M. (2005). Evapotranspiration of forests in the southeastern United States. *Journal of Hydrology*, 315(1-4), 219-235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2005.03.006>
- Kirkman, L. K., Mitchell, R. J., Helton, R. C., & Drew, M. B. (2001). Productivity and species richness across an environmental gradient in a fire-dependent ecosystem. *American Journal of Botany*, 88(11), 2119-2128. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3558437>
- Landers, J. L., van Lear, D. H., & Boyer, W. D. (1995). The longleaf pine forests of the southeast: requiem or renaissance? *Journal of Forestry*, 93(11), 39-44. <https://www.srs.fs.usda.gov/pubs/980>
- Liu, N., Caldwell, P. V., Dobbs, G. R., Miniati, C. F., Bolstad, P. V., Nelson, S. A. C., Sun, G. (2021). Forested lands dominate drinking water supply in the conterminous United States. *Environmental Research Letters*, 16(8), 084008. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac09b0>
- Livingston, R. J. (1984). The relationship of physical factors and biological response in coastal seagrass meadows. *Estuaries*, 7(4), 377–390. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1351620>
- McLaughlin, D. L., & Cohen, M. J. (2013). Realizing ecosystem services: wetland hydrologic function along a gradient of ecosystem condition. *Ecological Applications*, 23(7), 1619-1631. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/i23596777>
- Miller, J. A. (1986). *Hydrogeologic framework of the Floridan aquifer system in Florida and in parts of Georgia, South Carolina, and Alabama* (USGS Professional Paper 1403-B). U.S. Geological Survey. <https://pubs.er.usgs.gov/publication/pp1403B>
- Miller, J. A. (1990). *GROUND WATER ATLAS of the UNITED STATES, Alabama, Florida, Georgia, and South Carolina* (HA 730-G). U.S. Department of the Interior, U.S. Geological Survey Publications Warehouse. https://pubs.usgs.gov/ha/ha730/ch_g/G-text6.html
- Natural Resources Conservation Service. (2020). *Longleaf Pine Ecosystem Restoration – FY20-24 Implementation Strategy*. U.S. Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conserv. Service. https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/wps/PA_NRCSCconsumption/download?cid=nrcseprd1562417&ext=pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD). (2009a). *Tate's Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan - Executive Summary*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://www.nfwwater.com/content/download/5001/33687/Exec_070910a.pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD). (2009b). *Tate's Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan – Vol. 1*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://nfwwater.com/content/download/4722/32292/Tates_Hydro_Vol_1_081310a.pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD). (2009c). *Tate's Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan – Vol. 2*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://www.nfwwater.com/content/download/4687/32117/Tates_Hydro_Vol_2_081310a.pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD). (2022). *Apalachicola River and Bay Surface Water Improvement and Management (SWIM) Plan*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://www.nfwwater.com/content/download/18031/121997/Apalachicola%20River%20and%20Bay%20SWIM%20Plan%20November%202017_errata.pdf
- Oswalt, C. M., Cooper, J. A., Brockway, D. G., Brooks, H. W., Walker, J. L., Connor, K. F., Oswalt, S. N., Conner, R. C. (2012). *History and current condition of longleaf pine in the Southern United States*. (Gen. Tech. Rep. SRS–166) U.S. Department of Agriculture Forest Service, Southern Research Station. <https://www.srs.fs.usda.gov/pubs/42259>

- Pascale, C. A., & Wagner, J. R. (1982). *Water Resources of the Ochlockonee River Area, Northwest Florida* (Open-File Report 81-1121). U.S. Geological Survey, Water Resources Investigations. <https://pubs.er.usgs.gov/publication/ofr811121>
- Peet, R. K., & Allard, D. J. (1993). Longleaf pine-dominated vegetation of the southern Atlantic and eastern Gulf Coast region, USA. In S. Hermann (Ed.) *Proceedings of the 18th Tall Timbers fire ecology conference: The longleaf pine ecosystem: ecology, restoration, and management*. Tall Timbers Research Station, Tallahassee, FL. (pp. 45-81). http://talltimbers.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/03/PeetandAllard1993_op.pdf
- Platt, W. J. (1999). Southeastern pine savannas. In R. Anderson, J. Fralish, & J. Baskin (Eds.) *Savannas, Barrens, and Rock Outcrop Plant Communities of North America* (pp. 23-51). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511574627.003>
- Regional Working Group for America's Longleaf. (2009). *Range-Wide Conservation Plan for Longleaf Pine*. America's Longleaf. https://americaslongleaf.org/media/fqipyucuc/conservation_plan.pdf
- Robert, C., Crisman, T., Anderson, L., & Kendell, C. (2000). *Comparative Ecosystem Analysis of Hydrologic Restoration of Tates Hell Swamp* (Publication No. 1603). University of Florida School of Geosciences Faculty and Staff. https://digitalcommons.usf.edu/geo_facpub/1603/
- Scavia, D., Field, J. C., Boesch, D. F., Buddemeier, R. W., Burkett, V., Cayan, D. R., & Titus, J. G. (2002). Climate change impacts on U. S. coastal and marine ecosystems. *Estuaries*, 25(2), 149-164. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02691304>
- Sharpley, A. N., Krogstad, T., Kleinman, P., Haggard, B., Shigaki, F., & Saporito, L. S. (2007). Managing natural processes in drainage ditches for non-point source phosphorus control. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 62(4), 197-206. <https://www.jswconline.org/content/62/4/197>
- Southwest Florida Water Management District (SWFWMD). (2017). *West-Central Florida's aquifers: Florida's great unseen water resources*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://www.swfwmd.state.fl.us/sites/default/files/store_products/flas_aquifers.pdf
- Stein, B. A., Kutner, L. S. & Adams, J. S. (2000). *Precious heritage: the status of biodiversity in the United States*. Oxford University Press.
- Swank, W. T., & Crossley Jr, D. A. (1988). *Forest hydrology and ecology at Coweeta*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Tague, C., & Band, L. E. (2001). RHESSys: Regional Hydro-Ecologic Simulation System—An object-oriented approach to spatially distributed modeling of carbon, water, and nutrient cycling. *Earth Interactions*, 5(10), 1-42. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1087-3562\(2001\)005](https://doi.org/10.1175/1087-3562(2001)005)
- The Nature Conservancy, TNC. (2022) Longleaf Pine: A Tree for Our Time. [Website]. <https://www.nature.org/en-us/what-we-do/our-priorities/protect-water-and-land/land-and-water-stories/longleaf-pine-restoration/>
- Vadas, P. A., Srinivasan, M. S., Kleinman, P. J. A., Schmidt, J. P., & Allen, A. L. (2007). Hydrology and groundwater nutrient concentrations in a ditch-drained agroecosystem. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 62(4), 178-188. <https://www.jswconline.org/content/62/4/178>
- Walker, J., Peet, R. K. (1985). Composition and Species Diversity of Pine-wiregrass Savannas of the Green Swamp, North Carolina. In R. Peet (Eds.) *Plant community ecology: Papers in honor of Robert H. Whittaker*. (pp. 303-319). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-5526-4_20
- Williams, L. J., & Kuniansky, E. L. (2016). *Revised hydrogeologic framework of the Floridan aquifer system in Florida and parts of Georgia, Alabama, and South Carolina* (Professional Paper 1807). U.S. Geological Survey. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3133/pp1807>
- Zampieri, N. E., Pau, S., & Okamoto, D. K. (2020). The impact of Hurricane Michael on longleaf pine habitats in Florida. *Sci Rep* 10, 8483. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-65436-9>

1.2 BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill

On April 20, 2010, an explosion and subsequent fire on the Deepwater Horizon oil drilling rig in the Gulf of Mexico caused the largest offshore oil spill in the United States. This incident ultimately sank the massive rig and resulted in 11 deaths, 17 injuries, and the release of approximately 185 million gallons of crude oil into the Gulf impacting nearly 70,000 square miles of ocean. Despite a massive recovery effort, it took 87 days to cap the leak at the Macondo well blowout. Afterward, as established by Exec. Order No. 13543, 2010[‡], the National Commission on the BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill and Offshore Drilling found that multiple cost-cutting decisions and inadequate safety systems enacted by British Petroleum (BP) and its key contractors, Halliburton and Transocean, were to blame for the disaster. The 2011 report[‡] by the National Commission on the BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill and Offshore Drilling pinpoints the defective cement used on the well as the cause of the explosion. Two key points made by the above-mentioned report conclude that the accident could have been prevented, and the “scientific understanding of environmental conditions in sensitive environments in deep Gulf waters, along the region’s coastal habitats, and in areas proposed for more drilling, such as the Arctic, is inadequate. The same is true of the human and natural impacts of oil spills.” Ultimately, the U.S. and five Gulf States reached a historic settlement with BP to resolve the civil lawsuit over the Deepwater Horizon oil spill. All told, the global resolution of civil claims against BP was worth \$20.8 billion which is the largest settlement with a single entity in U.S. Department of Justice history.

References

Exec. Order No. 13543, 3 CFR 13543 (May 21, 2010).

<https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2010/05/26/2010-12805/national-commission-on-the-bp-deepwater-horizon-oil-spill-and-offshore-drilling>

National Commission on the BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill and Offshore Drilling. (2011). *Deep Water: The Gulf Oil Disaster and the Future of Offshore Drilling*. Presidential Commission.

<https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/GPO-OILCOMMISSION/pdf/GPO-OILCOMMISSION.pdf>

1.3 RESTORE and The Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council

On July 6, 2012, in response to the Deepwater Horizon oil spill, U.S. President Barak Obama signed into law “The Resources and Ecosystems Sustainability, Tourist Opportunities, and Revived Economies of the Gulf Coast States Act”—aka RESTORE Act (RESTORE Act, 2012[‡]) which established the Gulf Coast Restoration Trust Fund in the U.S. Treasury Department. Eighty percent of all administrative and civil penalties paid by responsible parties in connection with the Deepwater Horizon oil spill were deposited into a trust fund and invested. The RESTORE Act paved the way for the establishment of the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council (GCERC[‡]) which includes governors of all Gulf Coast states, the EPA Administrator, and the Secretaries of the U.S. Departments of Agriculture, Army, Commerce, Homeland Security, and Interior. Subsequently, RESTORE funds were made available to fund programs, projects, and activities that restore and protect the diverse marine and terrestrial ecosystems, communities, and economies of the Gulf Coast region of the United States. Additionally, The Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council’s “Comprehensive Plan – Update 2016, Restoring the Gulf Coast’s Ecosystem and Economy” (GCERC, 2016[‡]) outlined the fund use for ecosystem recovery and restoration, economic recovery and tourism promotion, and the geographic scope of Gulf Coast Region under the RESTORE Act, which includes any adjacent land, water, and watersheds within 25 miles of the coastal zones. In August 2015, as part of the initial plan, the Council published a draft RESTORE Act initial Funded Priorities List (FPL), proposing activities that the Council intended to prioritize for funding. After reviewing public comments from the draft FPL, the final version was published on December 9, 2015. The FPL served as the basis for allocating funds under the Council-Selected Restoration Component of

the RESTORE Act, and identified the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 (Planning & Implementation) proposal for funding in the final FPL (GCERC, 2015[†]).

References

- Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council (GCERC). (2015). Resources and Ecosystems Sustainability, Tourist Opportunities, and Revived Economies of the Gulf Coast States Act (RESTORE Act) Initial Funded Priorities List. <https://www.restorethegulf.gov/council-selected-restoration-component/initial-2015-funded-priorities-list>
- Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council (GCERC). (2016). Comprehensive Plan Update 2016. https://www.restorethegulf.gov/sites/default/files/CO-PL_20161208_CompPlanUpdate_English.pdf
- Resources and Ecosystems Sustainability, Tourist Opportunities, and Revived Economies of the Gulf Coast States Act of 2012, Pub. L. No. 112-141, 126 Stat. 588 (2012). <https://home.treasury.gov/system/files/216/Final-Restore-Act.pdf>

2 Tate’s Hell Strategy 1

2.1 Project Overview

Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 (THS1) is the first phase of a long-term, interagency restoration effort called the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative - ARRI[†] (GCERC, 2020) which was approved in the Resources and Ecosystem Sustainability, Tourist Opportunities, and Revived Economies of the Gulf Coast States Act (RESTORE Act[†]) Funded Priorities List 3b[†] and will begin in FY2024. The THS1 implementation element of the project focused on executing hydrologic improvements on Tate’s Hell State Forest (THSF[†]) while the planning component concentrated on prioritizing additional hydrologic and ecological restoration needs on adjacent public and private lands within the Apalachicola Region. The THS1 planning and implementation elements were originally submitted as part of a larger USDA proposal entitled “The Apalachicola Project (TAP) Phase 1: Restoring Apalachicola Bay and Region” (GCERC, 2015[†]). However, only the proposal elements identified on the Council’s final Funding Priority List were selected as “likely to provide near-term, on-the-ground ecosystem benefits, while also conducting planning activities designed to build a foundation for future success as additional funds become available for other parties.” On August 17, 2017, as identified in the first Funded Priorities List, and approved by the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council, the U.S. Forest Service (USFS[†]), National Forests in Florida (NFF[†]) and the Florida Forest Service (FFS[†]) received RESTORE Act settlement funds from the BP Deepwater Horizon Oil Spill to conduct conservation and hydrologic planning and implementation activities on upland areas of THSF, and the adjoining Apalachicola National Forest (ANF[†]) both located near the Gulf of Mexico within the Apalachicola Region in the central panhandle of Florida. The THS1 Project was funded for a total of \$7,000,000 and contained both planning and implementation activities for the USFS and FFS. A total of \$2,500,000 was allotted for the THS1 planning component within the Apalachicola Region primarily on the ANF, while \$4,050,000 was provided for project implementation on THSF. This project also included \$450,000 in funding for engineering design, and environmental compliance work for implementation of elements of hydrologic restoration identified as high priority for THSF. Background information and context for THSF implementation and planning activities can be found in the 2009 two-volume study entitled “Tate’s Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan” (NFWFMD, 2009a[†], 2009b[†], and 2009c[†]).

Spearheaded by the Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD[†]), Tate’s Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan was the strategic result of contributions by many individuals from the NFWFMD, FFS, Florida Fish & Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC[†]), and Florida Natural

Areas Inventory (FNAI[†]). The restoration plan covered 29 state-designated surface water drainage basins (Waterbody IDs[†]) within THSF. To help prioritize restoration targets for hydrologic flow and native habitat restoration, THSF was divided into 19 restoration tracts based on surface water basin boundaries, roads, and forest management units. The following three criteria were used to prioritize tracts for hydrologic and upland restoration: 1) surface water quality benefits, 2) habitats for species of conservation concern, and 3) restoration feasibility. For surface water quality benefits, restoration tracts were prioritized based on potential water quality improvements from wetland treatments, surface water runoff reduction, and proximity of surface water discharges to the Apalachicola Bay, East Bay, and adjacent waters. Habitat priorities for species of conservation concern were focused on wetlands and pine flatwoods but based on species occurrence and habitat presence of state or federally listed plant and animal species. Restoration feasibility was largely based on similarity between historic and current vegetation conditions where current and historical conditions were comparable, and likely to have reduced hydrologic impacts versus areas where differences between historic and current conditions were large and would require extensive restoration activities that could significantly disrupt hydrologic flows.

The results from the THSF plan divided the forest into three prioritized (high, medium, and low) restoration groups (Figure 2.1.1). Of the 19 high-priority restoration tracts, the following, in order of priority from highest to lowest, were identified: 1) Fort Gadsden, 2) Doyle, 3) Sumatra, 4) Whiskey George, 5) Cash Creek, 6) East Bayou, 7) High Creek, and 8) Whiskey George South. All told, the plan outlined deliberate targets for the installation and replacement of built infrastructure that improved hydrologic flows and upland habitat by constructing 54 low-water crossings and 3 bridges, installing 116 ditch blocks, 2 box culverts, and replacing or installing 65 culverts. The plan also recommended stabilizing 65 miles of roads, and planting site-appropriate native tree species on 2,182 acres of cut over former pine plantations. Funded THS1 activities included cultural resource surveys for shovel testing, culvert field assessments, road, and habitat evaluation, 1,100 acres of site preparation and tree planting, 48.7 miles of road stabilization using 97,400 tons of material, installation/replacement of 99 culverts, removal of 11 culverts, and installation of 2 box culverts, 48 new low-water crossings, and 107 ditch blocks. Ultimately, the impact of the fully implemented THSF Hydrologic Restoration Plan will affect greater than 200,000 acres of forest within the THS1 project area. Taken together, THS1 builds upon years of strategic planning, decades of expertise, and employs the best available science and management techniques to help plan, prioritize, and implement current and future restoration opportunities throughout Tate's Hell State Forest, the Lower Apalachicola River Basin and greater Apalachicola Region.

Figure 2.1.1. Map of Tate’s Hell State Forest restoration priority groups from the 2009 Tate’s Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan Volume 1 (from NFWFMD, 2009b).

References

Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council (GCERC). (2020). *The Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative: Strategies 2 & 3* (FPL 3b Activity Description). https://www.restorethegulf.gov/sites/default/files/FPL3b_USDA_Apalachicola_Regional_Restoration_Initiative_Activity_Description.pdf

Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council (GCERC). (2015). *The Apalachicola Project Phase 1: Restoring Apalachicola Bay and Region*. RESTORE Act Project Proposal. <https://www.restorethegulf.gov/sites/default/files/The%20Apalachicola%20Project%20Phase%201%20Restoring%20Apalachicola%20Bay%20and%20Region.pdf>

Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD). (2009a). *Tate’s Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan - Executive Summary*. State of Florida. https://www.nfwwater.com/content/download/5001/33687/Exec_070910a.pdf

Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD). (2009b). *Tate’s Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan – Vol. 1*. State of Florida. https://nfwwater.com/content/download/4722/32292/Tates_Hydro_Vol_1_081310a.pdf

Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD). (2009c). *Tate's Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan – Vol. 2*. State of Florida.

https://www.nfwwater.com/content/download/4687/32117/Tates_Hydro_Vol_2_081310a.pdf

2.2 Tate's Hell Strategy 1 (Planning Component) Deliverables

The goal of the Tate's Hell Strategy 1 Project (Planning Component) is to identify and prioritize hydrologic and upland forest restoration targets on the Apalachicola National Forest and surrounding areas within the region as well as create applicable and transferrable supporting methodologies, tools, data, and derivatives that employ innovative geospatial technology and solutions. In the original 2015 THS1 proposal[†], three separate deliverables were identified as follows: 1) a landscape scale hydrologic assessment, 2) a regional restoration decision support system, and 3) a comprehensive hydrologic assessment and restoration plan. Because of the inherently interconnected nature of the landscape scale hydrologic assessment and comprehensive restoration plan, these elements are presented together in this document rather than as individual deliverables. The Regional Restoration Decision Support System (RRDSS) described[†] in this document, has been published as a Web-delivered application[†] deployed on the USFS ArcGIS Online portal for internal use and testing among agency staff and for demonstration purposes to the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council, partners and stakeholders.

This integrated assessment and restoration plan fulfills the THS1 (Planning Component) goals of assessing, identifying, and prioritizing numerous restoration needs on the Apalachicola National Forest and in the Apalachicola Region, which allows for a more seamless discussion of data acquisition and developmental steps[†] that are integrated throughout the entire project. This plan also describes the open, repeatable geospatial tools and workflows that have been developed for this project which can be transferred to other Gulf of Mexico restoration projects or implemented for forest management applications. Furthermore, we have described many techniques and products that can be applied to more than one of the three original deliverables. The assessment and decision support tools developed and described in this project have been used to prioritize hydrologic and ecosystem restoration opportunities throughout the Apalachicola Region, including initial restoration targets for ARRI which will begin in FY2024.

2.3 Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER)

To help extend the impact and utility of RESTORE THS1 Project funds, the USDA Forest Service, and Florida A&M University (FAMU[†]) entered a partnership to consolidate and share scientific resources by establishing the Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER[†]) on the Florida A&M University campus in Tallahassee, FL. This partnership allows for student (undergraduate, graduate, and post-graduate) involvement in RESTORE-funded projects and provides opportunities to partner with FAMU faculty and staff across many academic units to convey additional expertise and expands our competences. As a result, we have been able to opportunistically launch multiple supporting projects that provide supplementary information and resources germane to RESTORE and other restoration and monitoring activities within the Gulf Coast Region that tie into THS1 and the future RESTORE-funded Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative: Strategies 2 & 3 acknowledged in the RESTORE Council's Funded Priority List 3b (GCERC, 2020), and approved \$5M Council-Selected Restoration Component funding on April 28, 2021.

Since its inception, CSER has made a tremendous contribution to the planning component of the Tate's Hell Strategy 1 Project. CSER scientists, and FAMU faculty, staff and students have collaborated to 1) create groundbreaking region-wide spatial datasets that leverage unique workflows applicable to hydrologic and ecosystem restoration, 2) codify workflows for potential forest water yield gains at

multiple scales across the Apalachicola Region summarized by hydrologic and administrative boundaries, 3) apply workflows to show potential water yield gains and prioritize proposed treatments as part of Tate's Hell Strategy 1 (Planning), and the subsequent ARRI Project, 4) implement redesigned field data plots more amenable to mitigating co-registration errors associated with remotely sensed data, 5) spatially quantify forest loss across the Apalachicola Region following a major storm event, and 6) derive forest structural metrics using a practical open-source lidar processing workflow that allows land managers to determine management strategies that will impact water quality and quantity across the local landscape, 7) develop a workflow to spatially-explicit estimates for open pine forest ecological conditions across the Apalachicola Region, 8) use single-pass UAV-borne lidar sampling as a rapid assessment method for surveying forest structure, 9) demonstrate the accuracy and efficiency of estimating basal area of tree diameter classes using a variety of modeling techniques, 10) identify a native plant on the Apalachicola National Forest that could uptake a large number of heavy metals from the natural soil, and demonstrate great phytoremediation potentials of metal contamination, and much more. All told, CSER and its collaborators have published more than 30 relevant, peer-reviewed manuscripts, codified workflows, code repositories, geospatial tools, and datasets as of summer 2023, detailing the innovative and applied spatially-explicit methods. These results have been incorporated into the landscape scale hydrologic assessment and comprehensive restoration plan and included in the geospatially-enabled regional restoration decision support system prototype. Deliverables are available and presented in this document but will continue to be revised and updated as needed throughout the subsequent ARRI 2&3 Project lifetime. Additionally, CSER/RESTORE has mentored three successful Ph.D. graduates at Florida A&M University in the School of the Environment, and College of Engineering. CSER scientists have also taught and mentored multiple primary, middle, and high school students, and provided learning opportunities for undergraduate and graduate students, interns, and post-graduates. In conjunction with our partners, in addition to Florida A&M University, CSER/RESTORE has funded doctoral and post-doctoral opportunities at the University of Montana, and the University of Florida, each of which has provided invaluable research for THS1 and the forthcoming ARRI Project.

Through this partnership, we have also developed multiple industry connections that have helped us to better understand and address substantial technological challenges related to solving complex ecological problems with a significant spatial component. These interactions have translated into relevant information that has been applied to multiple projects including local and cloud-based processing workflows for large geospatial datasets, IoT soil moisture sensor testing in remote forest locations, fusion of UAV-borne imagery and lidar, and post-windstorm timber stand damage assessments. Moreover, this partnership provided the opportunity to help train the next generation of environmental professionals in a cross-functional, translational scientific environment. As a result, we have been able to introduce young people to the concepts of long-term land stewardship while leveraging the power and utility of the latest technological advances in natural resources management.

References

Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council (GCERC). (2020). *Restore Council Activity Description: The Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative: Strategies 2 & 3*. https://www.restorethegulf.gov/sites/default/files/FPL3b_USDA_Apalachicola_Regional_Restoration_Initiative_Activity_Description.pdf

2.4 Partnerships and Strategic Support

Strategic partnerships and stakeholder input are critical elements to successfully assess current ecohydrologic conditions in the Apalachicola Region and prioritize future restoration opportunities. Hence, the partnership with Florida A&M University as well as many other partnerships contributed to

the THS1 and subsequent ARRI Projects. Our efforts have relied heavily on the following alphabetically listed organizations to help deliver results throughout this initiative:

- Center for Aquatic Technology Transfer (CATT, USFS Southern Research Station) — Hydrologic infrastructure assessment and geospatial data collection.
- Chesapeake Conservancy — Regional Restoration Decision Support System (RRDSS) planning and design assistance.
- Davis Instruments — IoT data sensor and acquisition support.
- Dewberry Corporation — 2018 FL Panhandle lidar data draft product support.
- Florida Agricultural & Mechanical University
 - College of Agriculture & Food Sciences - Water quality on forested lands
 - College of Science & Technology - High performance computing, data science, education
 - Division of Research - Collaborative extramural research initiatives
 - FAMU/FSU College of Engineering – Watershed modeling, Spatial Ecohydrology
 - NOAA/FAMU Center for Coastal and Marine Ecosystems – Minority education
 - School of the Environment – Energy Food Water Nexus, Geospatial Education
 - FAMU Sustainability Institute – Microsoft AI for Earth planning/meeting support
- Florida Fish & Wildlife Conservation Commission — hydrologic data sharing for the Apalachicola River Wildlife and Environmental Area.
- Florida Forest Service — THS1 implementation, accomplishment reporting, field evaluations, strategic planning.
- Florida Natural Areas Inventory — Field plot data collection and historic natural community mapping.
- Microsoft Corporation — two A.I. for Earth grants funding and in-kind support for CSER in Azure Cloud computing and post-disaster image processing.
- The Nature Conservancy — Strategic planning in-kind support for THS1 and ARRI, frosted flatwoods salamander pond restoration support.
- Northwest Florida Water Management District - Funding and logistics support for 2018 USGS 3DEP Apalachicola Regional QL1 lidar data acquisition under Interagency Agreement 17-IA-11080500024, and 2020 data acquisition logistical support.
- RESTORE - Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Team (GCERT) — Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 and Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative funding as well as logistical, planning and accounting/reporting systems support.
- University of Florida Spatial Ecology & Conservation Lab — Ultra-resolution drone-based lidar data, hyperspectral and thermal imagery acquisition. Remote Sensing coordination, logistics, mission planning, preprocessing, and distribution, collaboration on data collection and processing workflows related to applications of drone-borne lidar and imagery for forestry and natural disaster damage assessment. Storm Cloud and PRISM project partners.
- Southeast Aquatics Resource Partnership — Hydrologic infrastructure restoration and aquatic organism passage support based on high priority sites identified in this project and funding for ANF NFR 128.
- USDA Forest Service Region 8 — 2018 FL Panhandle lidar data acquisition funding under Interagency Agreement 17-IA-11080500024.
- USDA Forest Service Rocky Mountain Research Station — Foundational research in plot design and data processing methodology as well as geospatial software tools.

- USDA Forest Service Southern Research Station — Funding for graduate student studies through SRS Florida Forest Watershed Research Program (Dr. Johnny Grace), and hydrologic infrastructure evaluations through the CATT Team.
- USDA Natural Resource Conservation Service — Support and coordination of USDA RESTORE projects.
- U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service – FR128 low-water crossing construction design and logistics coordination.
- U.S. Geological Survey — 3DEP National Geospatial Programs and Federal Emergency Management Agency — Funding support for 2018 Apalachicola Regional QL1 lidar data acquisition under Interagency Agreement 17-IA-11080500024.
- Woolpert Corporation — 2018 panhandle lidar data acquisition planning.

3 Primary Data Acquisition

3.1 Field Vegetation Plot Data Collection and RESTORE Field Data Plot Redesign

Obtaining high-quality field plot data that accurately characterize forested landscapes is crucial for developing precise spatial derivative datasets from remotely sensed information. The vast size of the Apalachicola Region and previous experience with the accuracy of spatial outputs in relation to plot data led CSER staff to recognize that traditional field vegetation survey methods for individual stands were sometimes impractical and often resulted in sub-standard accuracy when remotely characterizing forested landscapes. Additionally, collecting field plot data can be both time-consuming and expensive while data collection standards and schema often vary widely.

Prior to initiating Tate's Hell Strategy 1, pioneering research conducted by staff at the USFS, Rocky Mountain Research Station (RMRS) and National Forests in Florida, focused on the effectiveness of image-based analyses to derive key forest metrics from area-wide datasets to characterize longleaf pine habitats in the Southeastern United States (Hogland & Anderson, 2015, 2017; Hogland et al., 2017a, 2017b, 2018a, 2018b, 2018c). This research culminated in what is primarily known as the Longleaf Mapping Project (LMP), which utilized readily available forest plot data from the USFS Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) Program with a long observation record. By integrating FIA plots with remotely sensed aerial and satellite imagery (including Landsat, NAIP, and Sentinel), the modeling of forest metrics across extensive areas in Alabama, Florida, and Georgia was accomplished. The Longleaf Mapping Project is discussed in much greater detail later in this this document.⁺

Overall, the Longleaf Mapping Project was novel and proved to be successful and effective in determining the presence or absence of pine and hardwood stands as well as estimating tree density and basal area in southern pine landscapes that spanned millions of acres across the Southeastern U.S. Most importantly, it served as a precursor to plot design modifications that facilitated the development of methodologies and improved upon forest structural estimates at landscape and project scales using image- and lidar-based analyses. However, limitations in FIA data combined with the image-based assessment methodology and variable quality of the image product inputs posed multiple challenges to addressing spatial data alignment, thus reducing general accuracy and predictability of image-based assessments, particularly at project scales that required a higher degree of precision. Image-based assessments revealed that errors associated with the co-registration of multi-temporal images and plot data acquired from different sources with variable resolutions would continue to be problematic for accurately representing ground conditions with a high degree of fidelity. As a result, careful reexamination of plot design methodology and image source variability became necessary before proceeding with the THS1 Project.

In addition to the Longleaf Mapping Project, there was a related research initiative focused on mapping and modeling ecological conditions within longleaf pine habitat on the National Forests in Florida. This project, known as the Ecological Condition Modeling (ECM) Project and detailed in the manuscript by Trager et al. (2018), integrated essential plot design elements and methodologies drawn from the Longleaf Mapping Project. The ECM Project served as a critical component of THS1, significantly expanding our understanding of remote modeling and mapping techniques applicable to southeastern pine forests. Rather than using an image-based assessment, the Florida ECM Project used lidar and relied heavily upon custom designed field plots and historic natural community data painstakingly collected with our partners at Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI[‡]), Florida's Natural Heritage Program and a state member of the NatureServe network. Based on the results of the LMP and early iterations of the ECM Project, it became evident that image-based analyses to derive forest metrics were appropriate and useful in certain situations at broader scales, but the need for a new forest plot design was apparent, and lidar provided a more accurate solution overall although it was harder to acquire and generally more expensive. Consequently, a complete reevaluation of the field data collection methodology was necessary to ensure effective area-wide data coverage and to enhance the overall accuracy of the spatial analyses and resultant data in THS1.

To facilitate the pivot to a more accurate mapping solution to characterize forested landscapes that were functional at both large and small scales, CSER and their partners created "RESTORE field plots", which were funded by RESTORE Act funds in THS1 and designed specifically for image- and lidar-based remote sensing analyses. A total of 246 RESTORE field plots were established between December 2017 and March 2018, covering 27 unique natural communities in the Apalachicola region. These plots were strategically placed on public lands within 804 meters (0.5 mile) of a road to help capture spectral values from remote sensing datasets, including Landsat, Sentinel-2, and NAIP imagery. Agricultural and urban landcovers were excluded to focus on sampling the range of forest conditions in the Apalachicola Region. Fortuitously, these plots proved critical in evaluating post-Hurricane Michael timber stand damage discussed later in this document[‡].

The RESTORE-funded plots, designed by Dr. John Hogland at the USFS Rocky Mountain Research Station (Hogland, 2019[‡]), aimed to increase the observable area within a forest plot while maintaining efficiency for ground crews to conduct measurements, and provided an improved mechanism for mitigating the impact of field and image registration errors through spatial aggregation and image normalization while employing spatial, statistical, and machine learning algorithms (Hogland and Affleck, 2019; Hogland et al., 2019, 2020). The plot design consisted of four 9-meter radius subplots arranged closely together within a 36-meter square plot (Figure 3.1.1). This design ensured that 78.5% of the plot area was observed, in contrast to FIA plots that observed 12.3% of the area due to their larger rectangular shape and "Turkey Foot" design scheme. As mentioned, the RESTORE field plot design helped reduce the negative impact of co-registration errors between field and remotely sensed data which improved the accuracy of the outputs. Subplot measurements within the RESTORE field plots included species, condition, and diameter at breast height (DBH) for each tree over 5 cm, as well as vegetative cover and tree count. Although these measurements were fewer than those required for FIA plots, they increased measurement efficiency while still providing sufficient data for training area-based forest models. Table 3.1.1 below presents the summary statistics from the RESTORE field plots.

Figure 3.1.1. Depiction of RESTORE field plot design (a) and FIA vegetation plot design (b). The area within the yellow box is the plot while the circles represent the subplots where forest observations are taken. RESTORE field plot area is 1,296 m², and the area within the subplots is 1,017.9 m². FIA Plot area is 5,460 m², and the area within the subplots is ~672.5 m².

Table 3.1.1. Summary statistics from forest plots (n = 246).

	BA (m ² /ha)	TPH	QMD (cm)	Elevation (m)
Min	0	0	0	0.34
Mean	20.07	1032.95	16.72	15.11
Median	17.66	756.49	16.78	9.35
Max	76.87	5943.74	63.97	75.35
SD	16.11	179.55	8.61	15.17

The following are a few key observations that helped CSER Team members refine the approach to create and manage plot data that are more amenable to remote sensing analyses. Fixed-area plots are typically more expensive than traditional variable-radius plots. However, they are better suited for use as ground truth with lidar and other remotely sensed data sets. Lidar derivatives, such as 95% canopy height, canopy cover, and relative density of lidar returns from 2ft to 10 ft, can be summarized and extracted for each fixed-area plot. These derivatives can then be directly related to field metrics of interest, such as basal area and timber volume, from the corresponding plot. Variable-radius plots have an unknown shape and area because trees are selected based on the probability proportional to basal area. As a result, it is difficult to precisely relate lidar derivatives to data from variable-radius plots since we don't know exactly which trees were selected for the plots (Figure 3.1.2). Although the spatial resolution of lidar derivatives can be adjusted to match the average area sampled by variable-radius plots across a study area, statistical models will likely be less precise compared to those developed using fixed area plots.

Figure 3.1.2. An example layout of a fixed-radius and variable-radius plot with the same center. The black-square outline is a lidar bin or image pixel, the gray circle is a fixed-radius plot, and the solid gray dots represent trees. All trees within the gray circle are counted in fixed-radius plot sampling but only the trees marked with (x) are counted in variable-radius sampling at a given BAF (From: Deo et al. 2016. *Canadian J. of Remote Sensing*, 42:5, 428-442).

It is important to collect field data across all ecological communities of interest and their range of conditions. Existing GIS layers (e.g., ecological communities, stand data including dominant forest type and stand age, fire history, etc.) can be very helpful in this process to create a sustainable database with robust multi-temporal data that can be repeatedly referenced. Previously, we have also used spectral and textural metrics from imagery along with roads and public lands to collect field data across a wide range of conditions with public accessibility. This sampling approach along with the fixed area plot design discussed above allowed us to collect only 246 plots over a highly biodiverse 5-million-acre area of the Florida Panhandle and yet still derive accurate lidar-based estimates of forest basal area, trees per acre, and quadratic mean stem diameter (St. Peter et al., 2021).

Using submeter GPS units is crucial for geolocating field plots, which ensures accuracy at each plot reference point, such as subplot centers or plot corners. It is highly recommended to collect multiple positions to enhance precision. While there are various dataloggers, Bluetooth GPS, and software options available, it is advisable to consult the technical accuracy specifications for the chosen unit software or subscription service that handles data correction. Accurate GPS data also plays a critical role in minimizing geo-registration errors between field plot data and lidar data, as well as other remotely sensed datasets. The accuracy is essential not only during the initial assessment stage but also

for revisiting field plots after management activities or natural disasters. For instance, following Hurricane Michael, we had to revisit 70 field plots that were estimated to have experienced various degrees of damage. The use of submeter GPS units instilled confidence in capturing updated field data from the same locations. Furthermore, for specific significant reference plots on the Apalachicola National Forest, we have taken the strategic approach of burying a metal conduit pipe a few inches below the soil surface. This method enables us to relocate the plot corners using a metal detector in conjunction with a submeter GPS unit, similar to boundary location techniques used by land surveyors.

Finally, collecting tree-level data in fixed area plots has provided unexpected benefits, such as generating value-added products like tree basal area categorized by diameter size class for timber and wildlife applications. However, prior to collecting field data, it is crucial to consider the datasets you may want to estimate in the future using airborne lidar. For instance, if there are metrics vital for forest fire behavior models, such as canopy base height, it is advisable to collect the additional data either across all plots or a subset of plots. This simple addition enables the development of statistical models to estimate these conditions across the entire landscape, thus maximizing plot value over time (St. Peter et al., In preparation).

References

- Deo, R. K., Foese, R., Falkowski, M. J., & Hudak, A. (2016). Optimizing variable radius plot size and LiDAR resolution to model standing volume in conifer forests. *Canadian Journal of Remote Sensing*, 42(5), 428-442.
- Florida Natural Areas Inventory. (2021, June 24). *Natural Communities Guide*. <https://www.fnai.org/naturalcommguide.cfm>
- Hogland, J. S., & Anderson, N. M. (2015). Estimating FIA plot characteristics using NAIP imagery, function modeling, and the RMRS Raster Utility coding library. In S. M. Stanton & G. A. Christensen (Eds.), *Pushing boundaries: new directions in inventory techniques and applications: Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) symposium 2015* (pp. 340-344). Gen. Tech. Rep. PNW-GTR-931. Portland, OR: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Pacific Northwest Research Station. <https://www.fs.usda.gov/research/treesearch/50440>
- Hogland, J., & Anderson, N. (2017). Function Modeling Improves the Efficiency of Spatial Modeling Using Big Data from Remote Sensing. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 1(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc1010003>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., Gilbert, J., Abernathy, R., Knight, G., Knight, A. (2017a). Cost-Effective Mapping of Longleaf Extent and Condition using NAIP Imagery and FIA Data: A Pilot Project in the Heart of the Longleaf Range. Longleaf Pine Mapping and Monitoring Final Report to delivered to the National Fish & Wildlife Foundation and Longleaf Alliance, 33pp.
- Hogland, J. S., St. Peter, J. R., & Anderson, N. M. (2017b). Raster surfaces created from the cost-effective mapping of longleaf extent and condition using NAIP imagery and FIA data project. <https://doi.org/10.2737/RDS-2017-0014>
- Hogland, J.S., Anderson, N., Affleck, D., St. Peter, J. (2018a). Using FIA Plot and Remotely Sensed Data to Map Longleaf Extent and Condition: Emphasizing High Resolution Outputs for Cross-ownership Planning, Monitoring, and Restoration. Ft. Stewart Longleaf Mapping Project Final Report delivered to the National Fish & Wildlife Foundation and Longleaf Alliance, 32pp.
- Hogland, J. S., St. Peter, J. R., & Anderson, N. M. (2018b). Raster surfaces created from the mapping of longleaf extent and condition using Landsat and FIA data project. Fort Collins, CO: Forest Service Research Data Archive. <https://doi.org/10.2737/RDS-2018-0039>

- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., St. Peter, J., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2018c). Mapping Forest Characteristics at Fine Resolution across Large Landscapes of the Southeastern United States Using NAIP Imagery and FIA Field Plot Data. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 7(4), 140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi7040140>
- Hogland, J. S. (2019). Estimates of forest characteristics derived from remotely sensed imagery and field samples: Applicable scales, appropriate study design, and relevance to forest management (Graduate Student Theses, Dissertations, & Professional Papers No. 11505). Retrieved from University of Montana ScholarWorks: <https://scholarworks.umt.edu/etd/11505>
- Hogland, J., & Affleck, D. L. R. (2019). Mitigating the Impact of Field and Image Registration Errors through Spatial Aggregation. *Remote Sensing*, 11(3), 222. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs11030222>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., Affleck, D. L. R., & St. Peter, J. (2019). Using Forest Inventory Data with Landsat 8 Imagery to Map Longleaf Pine Forest Characteristics in Georgia, USA. *Remote Sensing*, 11(15), 1803. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11151803>
- Hogland, J., Affleck, D. L. R., Anderson, N., Seielstad, C., Dobrowski, S., Graham, J., & Smith, R. (2020). Estimating Forest Characteristics for Longleaf Pine Restoration Using Normalized Remotely Sensed Imagery in Florida USA. *Forests*, 11(4), 426. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/f11040426>
- St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., Ibeanusi, V., & Broadbent, E. (In preparation). A comparison of single and ensemble regression model workflows for estimating basal area by tree size class across large landscapes. Manuscript in preparation for *GIScience & Remote Sensing*.
- St. Peter, J., Anderson, C., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2020). Spatially quantifying forest loss at landscape scale following a major storm event. *Remote Sensing*, 12(7), 1138. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12071138>
- St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., & Ibeanusi, V. (2021). Forest structural estimates derived using a practical, open-source lidar-processing workflow. *Remote Sensing*, 13, 4763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13234763>
- Trager, M. D., Drake, J. B., Jenkins, A. M., & Petrick, C.J. (2018). Mapping and Modeling Ecological Conditions of Longleaf Pine Habitats in the Apalachicola National Forest. *Journal of Forestry*, 116, 304–311. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jofore/fvx017>

3.2 Hydrologic Infrastructure Assessment

Beginning in the winter of 2017, a team from the U.S. Forest Service, and Center for Aquatic Technology Transfer (CATT[†]) was deployed to Bristol, Florida to begin an intensive assessment of drainage structures on the western district of the Apalachicola National Forest. These surveys are a critical component for evaluating and improving existing drainage networks across extremely flat topography such as the Southeastern Coastal Plain where streams and wetlands are intricately woven across the landscape. Moreover, as evidenced by prior restoration work on THSF, the connection and movement of water between ditches, which are prevalent in this region, is invaluable when trying to accurately assess current and historic hydrologic flow across the landscape. Between two visits that spanned six months, multiple surveys were conducted on the Apalachicola Ranger District (ARD) consisting of near-real time data collection on all district roads opened and maintained for public use. The team of four was able to cover approximately 1,000 miles of roadway, capture basic infrastructure and condition data, identify maintenance problems, evaluate surrounding habitat evaluations, and determine flow direction for 1,459 structures. Basic infrastructure data for single pipe ditch connectors and locations of extreme erosion events, culvert failures, and deteriorating road conditions were also included. All told, over 4,400 surveys were conducted across the 302,000+ acre ARD.

Most of all points surveyed during the CATT Team assessment included waterbody culverts, basic cross drains, and multiple points of significant hydrologic interest (Figure 3.2.1). A breakdown of

hydrologic infrastructure surveys conducted by the CATT team during the winter 2017/18 field season is illustrated in Table 3.2.1. Waterbody culverts were the highest priority in this road infrastructure inventory primarily because they were crossings of interest to forest hydrologists and engineers for potential restoration, road improvement, and as candidates for development of enhanced hydrologic flow path maps[‡]. Wetland connectors made up the largest group of surveyed waterbody culverts (66%). Most of the culverts in this category were functional (81%) and in good to fair condition (65%). Correspondingly, basic cross drains, which were culverts that primarily connected ditches on either side of the roadway, were collected using a simplified survey. However, function and condition trends for cross drains showed a larger proportion, as compared to waterbody culverts, to be in unknown condition or nonextant. Further investigation showed that many of these structures were completely buried, or significantly compacted single pipe culverts which were identified with the aid of a metal detector. Consequently, in-depth surveys that could not be conducted may be addressed in future surveys. Finally, points collected in the miscellaneous category served multiple purposes. These features showed significant failures and erosion concerns that typically accompanied other waterbody or basic infrastructure locations. The surveys signaled that the structural integrity of coincident hydrologic features had been compromised, and repair/replacement was imminent. Informal road assessments were also taken by the CATT team, which made up the remaining miscellaneous data category. Tracking which roads had been completely surveyed, or at what point a road could no longer be surveyed, was identified with an end of road point feature. Large mudholes and overrun roads were also collected to provide USFS engineers with road condition information, which was useful in timber sale contracts and road maintenance packages. A final “other” category was included in the miscellaneous points layer, encapsulating anything of interest that did not fit a previous designation. These included the presence of user-created trails/roads into forested stands, downed trees on the roadway, or even debris piled on the roadside. A pictorial representation of the above-mentioned features is illustrated in Figure 3.2.2.

Figure 3.2.1. Distribution of 4,000 hydrologic survey points on Apalachicola Ranger District of the Apalachicola National Forest.

Table 3.2.1. Hydrologic infrastructure surveys for infrastructure types conducted by the CATT team during the winter 2017/18 field season. Includes summary of subtypes for each feature collected, and qualitative function and condition assessment for all infrastructure points collected.

		Count		Count		Count				
		Type		Functioning		Condition				
Waterbody	Culverts	1459								
		Stream Crossings	257	18%	Yes	1187	81%	Good	376	26%
		Wetland Connectors	956	66%	Yes, but	76	5%	Fair	575	39%
		Wetland Drains	240	16%	No	158	11%	Poor	344	24%
		Uncertain	6	<1%	N/A	38	3%	Unknown	103	7%
							N/A	61	4%	
Basic	Crossdrains	699								
		Parallel Drains	38	5%	Yes	356	51%	Good	125	18%
		Combination Drains	200	29%	Yes, but	74	11%	Fair	239	34%
		Cross Drains	459	66%	No	187	27%	Poor	140	20%
		Uncertain	2	<1%	N/A	82	12%	Unknown	59	8%
							N/A	136	19%	
Miscellaneous	Points	2267								
		Significant Failures	34	1%						
		Erosion Issues	93	4%						
		Overrun Roads	216	10%						
		Mudholes	1146	51%						
		End of Road/Other	778	34%						
Total		4,425 pts								

Figure 3.2.2. Hydrologic infrastructure surveys (2017-18) across the Apalachicola Ranger District showing various hydrologic infrastructure types and conditions.

Following the CATT Team visit, stream crossings, as well as select wetland connector sites, underwent additional surveys to evaluate their accessibility and condition for aquatic organism passage. Aquatic connectivity of streams and wetlands in the Southeast has collectively become an important issue for land managers. Roadways often act as dams or barriers that can disconnect aquatic habitats resulting in habitat fragmentation and loss of biodiversity. To address these ecological impacts of road infrastructure and prioritize dam removal or identify culvert improvement projects, The Nature

Conservancy, and the Southeast Aquatic Resource Partnership (SARP) began collecting data on these structures that feed into the comprehensive GIS database to help evaluate improvement opportunities based on various metrics such as the material of the structure, dimensions of inlet and outlet, and water depth. The aquatic connectivity survey was originally developed by the North Atlantic Connectivity Collaborative and later adapted by SARP for better application in the Southeastern U.S. SARP coordinates with multiple state and federal agencies to acquire funding for these surveys and collectively have developed an extensive, national spatial database of aquatic barriers[†].

When the CATT team returned in 2021 to complete infrastructure surveys on the remaining forest roads, they also began collecting additional AOP surveys on several stream crossings and wetland connectors. Priority collection areas for AOP surveys on the National Forest started near the Apalachicola River and moved eastward as sites were completed. A total of 205 sites were captured using the AOP protocol[†], however, only 191 received final scores which are shown below in Figure 3.2.3. Fourteen sites were not scored because no or only partial surveys could be conducted, culvert locations could not be found due to GPS errors, or culverts had been removed between the initial CATT and AOP assessments. Issues found consistently across severe, significant, and moderate barriers, including perched outlets, and undermining that presented physical accessibility barriers to aquatic organisms and culvert failure, and stream constriction at crossings that could lead to increased water velocities within pipes to potentially disrupt migration and alter the natural stream channel (Figure 3.2.4).

Figure 3.2.3. Map depicting Aquatic Organism Passage (AOP) survey locations, and the final impairment classification for 191 sites, conducted by the SRS CATT team in Nov/Dec 2021 using the SARP AOP protocol.

Figure 3.2.4. Examples of culverts that received a severe or significant barrier score during SARP prioritization at selected AOP survey locations on the Apalachicola National Forest.

References

Southeast Aquatic Connectivity Program. (2019, April). *SARP Stream Crossing Survey Field Form, version SE2.1*. Southeast Aquatic Resource Partnership. Retrieved November 22, 2022 from <https://southeastaquatics.net/sarps-programs/southeast-aquatic-connectivity-assessment-program-seacap/culvert-assessments/sarp-culvert-assessment-datasheet/view>

3.3 Lidar Remote Sensing and USGS 3DEP Data Acquisition for the Apalachicola Region

Typically, LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) systems for active, optical remote sensing of objects use pulsed laser light emitted from a transmitting laser source directed towards a target of interest which can be practically anything. Once a laser pulse is discharged and strikes the target of interest, a portion of its energy is reflected to an optical receiver (sensor) located near the laser emission source. By measuring the round-trip travel time between the source, the surface of an object it strikes, and the optical receiver (sensor), it is possible to determine the distance between the sensor system and the target (ranging). The data produced from these sensor systems, which can be mounted to multiple data collection platforms (airplane, drone, automobile, etc.), result in a set of points called a “point cloud”. When these point clouds are combined with data from a Global Positioning System (GPS) for locational information, and an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) for movement statistics (speed, direction, acceleration, etc.), the data can be transformed into a three-dimensional (3D), geo-referenced set of data points in space and be used to virtually represent almost any object such as bare ground (terrain), buildings, trees, cars, people, etc. Primarily, lidar point cloud data used in land management applications are first interpolated into digitally rasterized representations of surface elevation (Digital Elevation Models or DEMs) to represent bare earth topography, and subsequently Digital Surface Models (DSMs) that include other features such as vegetation and manufactured structures. In some countries, DEM and DTM (Digital Terrain Model) are synonymous and represent bare earth elevations

referenced to a common earth model, but in the U.S., a DTM typically refers to a vector point dataset used to augment a DEM by including linear features such as contours, ridges, and breaklines. From here, the information can be further analyzed and transformed into many useful datasets such as terrain derivatives (slope, ruggedness, prominence, etc.), and forest metrics like canopy height models (CHMs, which are DSMs minus DEMs). Several of the above-mentioned models are exemplified in Figure 3.3.1.

In the early days of lidar data, acquisition over large landscapes was extremely challenging for a variety of reasons including high costs, underdeveloped technology, long and complicated acquisition procedures, excessive processing and delivery times, lack of consistent data standards and data QA/QC protocols, spurious and confounding data errors, and expensive processing equipment used for very large datasets, all of which resulted in slow initial growth of this technology for digital forest mensuration and practical land management applications. In response to the growing need for a wide range of three-dimensional representations of the Nation's natural and constructed features as well as high-quality digital topographic data, the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) 3D Elevation Program (3DEP)[‡] was created. USGS 3DEP is managed by the USGS National Geospatial Program with the specific goal to “complete acquisition of nationwide lidar to provide a national baseline of consistent high-resolution topographic elevation data – both bare earth and 3D point clouds” (USGS n.d.). The first full year of 3DEP production began in 2016 and by the end of fiscal year 2021, 84% of the U.S. had readily available lidar data, or ongoing elevation data collections that met 3DEP specifications for accuracy and resolution. In 2017, the US Forest Service, National Forests in Florida, and Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD) partnered with USGS 3DEP to help fund and acquire badly needed airborne lidar data to complete data coverage over the Florida Panhandle to the eastern extent of the NFWFMD boundary, which included newly collected data for the Apalachicola Region. This timely partnership proved to be a strategic collaboration that provided the opportunity to acquire the latest high-quality remote sensing data, which would later inform our study area assessments and restoration plans for THS1 and beyond. Additionally, this data proved to be a strategic pre-Hurricane Michael timestamp for later comparisons against post-Hurricane Michael data.

In 2019, a combination of QL1 and QL2 lidar¹ data was delivered to the USFS and our partners in four separate collections of classified version 1.4 LAS files which were later loaded into local and cloud storage for additional processing[‡]. We refer to the collections used for the THS1 study area as Leon, Block 2, Block 3, and Choctawhatchee (Figure 3.3.2). The Leon lidar collection consisted of 876 (5000 ft × 5000 ft) tiles covering all of Leon County. Leon data had a nominal pulse spacing (NPS) of 0.35 m (QL1) and was acquired between 5 February 2018 and 25 April 2018 (OCM Partners 2018a). Blocks 2 and 3 consisted of 6845 and 6598 (1 km × 1 km) tiles, respectively, and covered the western and southern counties surrounding Leon County (Figure 3.3.2). Block 2 and Block 3 lidar data were collected in early 2018 and had an NPS of 0.7 m (OCM Partners 2018b). The Choctawhatchee data were acquired in early 2017 and had an NPS of 0.7 m (QL2). The Choctawhatchee lidar collection consisted of 3893 (1 km × 1 km) tiles (OCM Partners 2017). The four raw lidar datasets totaled approximately 11 terabytes (TB), with derivatives were more than 12TB.

References

- OCM Partners. (2018a). *TLCGIS Lidar: Leon County, FL*. NOAA Fisheries. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/inport/item/60045>
- OCM Partners. (2018b). *TLCGIS Lidar: Florida Panhandle*. NOAA Fisheries. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/inport/item/58298>

¹ Topographic data quality levels (QL1 and QL2) acquired from the USGS 3DEP lidar program and initially used in the THS1 Project had a nominal pulse spacing (NPS) of less than or equal to 0.35 m and 8 or more points per square meter for QL1, while QL2 lidar had a NPS of less than 0.71 m and 2 or more points per square meter.

OCM Partners. (2017). *NFWMD Lidar: Lower Choctawhatchee*. NOAA Fisheries. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/inport/item/55725>

St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., & Ibeanusi, V. (2021). Forest Structural Estimates Derived Using a Practical, Open-Source Lidar-Processing Workflow. *Remote Sensing* 13(23), 4763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13234763>

United States Geological Survey (USGS). (n.d.). *3D Elevation Program*. United States Department of the Interior. <https://www.usgs.gov/3d-elevation-program>

Figure 3.3.1. Lidar point cloud data in land management applications (left) are typically classified (ground, vegetation) and then interpolated to create raster surfaces such as Digital Surface Models (top right), Digital Elevation Models (middle right) and relative derivatives such as Canopy Height Models (lower right). The raster surfaces depicted in this figure are from a small subset of points on the western Apalachicola National Forest derived from lidar point clouds.

Figure 3.3.2. Study area in the Florida panhandle (~22,900 km²). Areas of each lidar dataset are shown in different colors and labelled accordingly. Block2 and Block3 are shown using the same color, as these datasets were collected at the same time and separated during postprocessing. The Apalachicola National Forest and Tate’s Hell State Forest are shown in gray. (St. Peter, et al., 2021).

4 Primary Data Analysis and Secondary Data Development

4.1 Hurricane Michael Damage Assessment

During the initial phases of the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 (THS1) Project, the Apalachicola Region faced the devastating impact of Hurricane Michael, a catastrophic category 5 hurricane that struck the Florida panhandle on October 10th, 2018⁺. Hurricane Michael stands as the second most powerful hurricane to make landfall on the continental United States, boasting estimated maximum sustained winds of 259 km/h (161 mph). The impact was immediately felt across the Apalachicola Region, the National Forests in Florida, as well as CSER staff, goals, and timelines. All told, Hurricane Michael was directly responsible for 16 deaths and approximately \$25 billion in damages across the United States (Beven et al., 2019). Recovery is still ongoing.

The aftermath of the hurricane resulted in widespread damage to local forests (Figure 4.1.1), marked by initial studies revealing an alarming tree mortality (up to 89%) in specific longleaf pine sites (Zampieri et al., 2020). In the wake of the hurricane, numerous drainage structures in the Apalachicola Region were also damaged or filled with sediment and woody debris (Figure 4.1.2) thus affecting local hydrologic flows. Recognizing the pressing need to comprehensively assess the hurricane's impact across the study area, both for swift disaster response and its repercussions on the THS1 Project, CSER staff turned to remote sensing data for some quick answers. This data proved crucial for quantifying the

hurricane's effects on timber, infrastructure, and other critical resources within the Region. Since then, these data and techniques have been repeatedly referenced and incorporated into ancillary workflows. By harnessing the capabilities of remote sensing, CSER achieved timely and precise assessments of the forest damage inflicted by Hurricane Michael. This comprehensive evaluation not only steered decisions regarding disaster recovery and strategic forest management but also played a pivotal role in shaping the THS1 Project's planning outcomes.

Figure 4.1.1. Aerial view of post-Hurricane Michael timber stand damage (Image by M. Keys, USFS, 2018).

Existing methods for gauging forest damage from natural disasters, such as changes in the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), often prove inadequate. They struggle either in capturing changes over time or accurately reflecting authentic forest damage caused by the storm. To overcome these limitations, CSER staff embraced an inventive approach inspired by certain workflows and products derived from the Longleaf Mapping Project (Section 7.3). This approach facilitated the utilization of top-notch publicly-available satellite imagery, recently established RESTORE field plots (Figure 4.1.3, Section 3.1), and innovative image processing techniques. The result was an extensive, high-resolution raster and map dataset that gauged forest damage in terms of tree basal area (BA) loss — a key parameter used by forest managers. Fortuitously, the steps to accomplish this overall strategy relied on methods that CSER and our colleagues had mostly developed in a prior project to estimate forest metrics at landscape spatial extents using fine spatial resolution remotely sensed datasets (Hogland et al., 2018; Hogland et al., 2019).

Figure 4.1.2. Example of a culvert on the Apalachicola National Forest no longer functioning properly due to blockage from downed trees and limbs from Hurricane Michael (Image by J. Drake, USFS, 2018).

Specifically, this analysis utilized Sentinel-2⁺ satellite imagery as the primary remotely sensed data source. The Sentinel satellite constellation offers numerous advantages over some other imagery data sources such as relatively high temporal and spatial resolution which make it valuable for tasks like land monitoring, emergency management, security, climate change analysis, and marine applications. The high temporal resolution is possible because the Sentinel-2 mission has a twin-satellite constellation with a high revisit frequency. Under optimal conditions, a single Sentinel-2 satellite provides a 10-day revisit rate at the equator. This frequency improves to 5 days when two satellites operate in tandem, assuming cloud-free conditions. This equates to approximately 2-3 days of revisit time at mid-latitudes which makes it very useful for acquiring before and after images of storm-damaged areas especially when many are obscured by clouds. It also boasts 10m horizontal resolution for its red, green, blue and near infrared bands, which allows for high resolution outputs to be used at multiple scales across the landscape.

Figure 4.1.3. RESTORE field plots and revisited plot locations within the Apalachicola study area. Hurricane Michael storm track and wind swath with categorized wind speeds are shown for reference. (St. Peter et al., 2020).

The particular methodology used in this analysis allowed us to create a detailed basal area (BA) model using pre-hurricane field plot data and Sentinel-2 imagery which was then applied to pre- and post-hurricane images over the same location. Fundamentally, tree basal area refers to the collective cross-sectional area occupied by tree stems in a specific location. This metric is commonly used in forestry and has been applied previously to quantify hurricane-induced forest damage (Flynn et al., 2010). For this project, utilizing BA provided a clear measure and unambiguous workflow to help estimate storm damage. Ultimately, the difference between the modeled BA in the pre- and post-Hurricane estimates would become the complete forest damage estimate following Hurricane Michael. The explicit workflow to create the forest damage estimates is shown in Figure 4.1.3. In addition to providing a high-quality representative proxy dataset to forest damage, this workflow (Figure 4.1.4) addressed major processing barriers of imagery analysis at this extent, including: 1) specifically addressing co-registration errors among multi-temporal images, 2) aligning overlapping imagery to a common radiometric scale, 3) accounting for phenological differences of vegetation within mosaicked multi-temporal images, and 4) the ability to create models exclusively for forested lands while providing the flexibility to mask, exclude, or include other elements of the landscape that may or may not be pertinent to the analysis across a particular landscape.

Figure 4.1.4. Flowchart of the imagery preprocessing and modeling steps including the principal component analysis (PCA) to reduce predictive variable dimensionality, Softmax neural network of tree presence model and the general linear model estimating basal area. (St. Peter et al., 2020).

Seventy of the RESTORE field plots were revisited after Hurricane Michael (Figure 4.1.3) to assess forest damage across a range of different natural communities and estimated wind speeds. The measurements taken at each revisited plot consisted of the tree species, condition, diameter at breast height (DBH), and a qualitative assessment of hurricane damage across the entire plot and an estimate of canopy cover for functional plant types. Field results showed over 30% of the revisited RESTORE field plots had moderate to heavy damage, with a loss of 10% of all trees that were surveyed across all plots. Storm debris (downed trees, limbs, and foliage) was heavy (15-45%) across most natural communities

and the percent of coarse woody debris increased significantly (7.9% to 15.6%) when comparing pre- and post-storm data across all plots. Results showed that damage was heaviest in wetland communities, specifically bottomland forests and bay galls (Figure 4.1.5).

Figure 4.1.5. Heavy post-Hurricane Michael damage to bottomland forest (Image by C. Anderson, FNAI, 2018).

The model estimated a total BA loss of 19.18% in the project area, 7.67% in the Apalachicola National Forest, and 28% within the hurricane force wind area of Florida (Table 4.1.1). The resulting map of forest damage in Florida at 10-m spatial resolution is shown in Figure 4.1.6. Estimates of heavy forest damage can clearly be seen within the main swath of estimated hurricane force winds.

Table 4.1.1. Modeled basal area loss for the overall project area, the Apalachicola National Forest (ANF) as well as the areas that experienced hurricane force and tropical storm force winds. (St. Peter et al., 2020).

	Area Size (Hectares)	Avg. BA Loss (m ² /hectare)	95% CI (m ² /hectare)	Total BA Loss (m ²)	95% CI (m ²)	Percent BA Loss
Project Area	1,900,773	73.2	63.7-82.6	7,328,640	6,383,549 - 8,273,731	19.18%
ANF	254,199	29.3	25.5-33.1	392,204	341,626 - 442,782	7.67%
Hurricane	1,146,405	90.0	78.4-101.6	5,435,244	4,734,323 - 6,136,165	28.01%
Tropical Storm	674,434	46.6	40.6-52.7	1,657,659	1,443,890 - 1,871,428	13.16%

Figure 4.1.6. Spatial estimates of relative basal area loss after Hurricane Michael (2018) in the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project area. Blue pixels represent no estimated basal area loss. Pixels in non-forested areas were masked out using a tree presence model (From St. Peter et al. 2020, Dataset- St. Peter et al. 2019).

To assess the accuracy of the modeled forest damage estimates, field and modeled BA loss were summarized into three categories- Heavy (>3.72 m² BA loss), Medium (1.4 to 3.72 m² BA loss) or Light (<1.4 m² BA loss). Overall, the BA loss model performed well at categorizing forest hurricane damage in revisited areas. However, there was less agreement for the Medium Category (Table 4.1.2). The model overestimated damage in some areas, primarily due to very heavy crown damage while trees still lived.

Table 4.1.2. Error matrix of forest BA loss categories as evaluated at revisited RESTORE field plot locations. Field observations are the reference (top row), while basal area model estimates are predicted (first column). (From St. Peter et al., 2020).

Predicted \ Reference	Heavy	Medium	Light	
Heavy	3	5	2	
Medium	1	2	7	
Light	0	4	45	
Overall Accuracy				0.72

In essence, this assessment of post-windstorm forest damage and its derivative data introduced an efficient remote sensing technique for quantifying and pinpointing high-resolution (10m) forest damage across vast landscapes while maintaining usability at project scales. The raster outputs that depicted forest damage subsequent to Hurricane Michael (St. Peter et al. 2019) spanned the hurricane-affected regions, proving instrumental in the THS1 Project's planning and other land management endeavors.

To make this assessment swiftly accessible for timely disaster responses, the analysis should ideally occur within days of a natural disaster. However, the acquisition of cloud-free satellite images immediately after a hurricane, although essential, can be challenging. Many of these limitations were surmounted in subsequent projects through collaborations with partners such as Microsoft⁺, and later with the University of Florida, details of which are elaborated in the Storm Cloud Project outlined in Section 7.6 of this report.

Ultimately, this unexpected initiative yielded a comprehensive, high-resolution raster and map dataset, alongside reusable workflows. These tools aid in assessing and quantifying forest damage, measured in terms of forest basal area (BA) loss. Due to the pivotal role this parameter plays for land managers, coupled with its clear and straightforward nature in estimating hurricane-induced timber damage, further refinement holds the potential to generate results that can translate into official damage estimates considerably earlier than comparable estimates from on-site sources.

References

- Beven II, J. L., Berg, R., & Hagen, A. (2019, May 17). *National Hurricane Center Tropical Cyclone Report: Hurricane Michael*. (AL 142018). National Weather Service. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. https://www.nhc.noaa.gov/data/tcr/AL142018_Michael.pdf
- Flynn, D. F., Uriarte, M., Crk, T., Pascarella, J. B., Zimmerman, J. K., Aide, T. M., & Caraballo Ortiz, M. A. (2010). Hurricane Disturbance Alters Secondary Forest Recovery in Puerto Rico. *Biotropica*, 42, 149–157. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-7429.2009.00581.x>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., Affleck, D. L., & St. Peter, J. (2019). Using Forest Inventory Data with Landsat 8 Imagery to Map Longleaf Pine Forest Characteristics in Georgia, USA. *Remote Sensing* 11, 1803. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11151803>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., St. Peter, J. R., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2018). Mapping Forest Characteristics at Fine Resolution across Large Landscapes of the Southeastern United States Using NAIP Imagery and FIA Field Plot Data. *Int. J. Geo-Inf.* 7, 140. <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/11/15/1803>
- St. Peter, Joseph, Anderson, Chad, Drake, Jason, & Medley, Paul. (2019). Spatially Quantifying Forest Damage from Hurricane Michael using Sentinel-2 Imagery [Data set]. (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8237469>
- St. Peter, J., Anderson, C., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2020). Spatially Quantifying Forest Loss at Landscape-scale Following a Major Storm Event. *Remote Sensing*, 12(7), 1138. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs12071138>
- Zampieri, N. E., Pau, S. & Okamoto, D. K. (2020). The impact of Hurricane Michael on longleaf pine habitats in Florida. *Scientific Reports* 10, 8483. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-65436-9>

4.2 Digital Remote Mensuration and the use of Lidar for Forest Structure Estimation

Discrete return lidar systems are an increasingly vital source of digital spatial information on forest characteristics that are frequently acquired over large spatial extents. The increase in high-quality lidar data provides land managers with remarkable opportunities to leverage finely detailed, large extent vegetation information to inform and monitor management activities. Lidar data also presents

distinct advantages over passive spectral sensors, as they possess the capacity to unveil underlying structures within densely canopied forests. Particularly in ecologically diverse forests like those in the Southeastern U.S., lidar's capability to observe multiple layers of forest canopy holds the potential to significantly enhance forest metric estimations. Mid- and understory forest structural assessments are essential in the Southeastern U.S. for estimating the condition of longleaf and open pine ecosystems (Nordman et al., 2016; Trager et al., 2018), assessing habitat of endangered species (Garabedian et al., 2017), calculating evapotranspiration (Cohen et al., 2017), and planning and managing prescribed fires (Darracq et al., 2016; Young et al., 2017).

While the availability of free, publicly accessible airborne lidar data is continually expanding, substantial obstacles still impede the complete utilization of these information-rich datasets for natural resource applications across expansive regions. In our project, the airborne lidar data, detailed in section 3.3, contain invaluable intricate data regarding the three-dimensional arrangement of vegetation and bare earth surfaces. However, the extraction of meaningful products from lidar point clouds (as exemplified in Figure 4.2.1) is a preliminary requirement. The process of generating standard bare earth products, such as digital elevation models (DEMs), from lidar data is well-established and carried out by commercial vendors for the USGS 3D Elevation Program. Yet, a necessity exists for further refining standards and establishing replicable workflows to create primary lidar derivatives for terrestrial vegetation structure, including canopy cover.

Figure 4.2.1. Small subsection (100x100 meters) extracted from a lidar point cloud dataset. The blue dots correspond to ground and lower vegetation returns, while the yellow to red dots depict returns from the canopies of taller trees. Notably, the average pulse density in this specific region amounts to 16 pulses per square meter, a significant increase compared to the typical pulse density of 4 to 8 pulses per square meter found in most contemporary airborne lidar datasets.

In response to this challenge, the CSER team devised a new and repeatable open source lidar processing workflow aimed at producing canopy height, canopy cover, and relative density metrics from lidar datasets (St. Peter & Drake, 2021). This new workflow was constructed by utilizing foundational elements of the highly efficient R software package called "lidR" (Roussel et al., 2020; Roussel & Auty, 2022). The core of this approach is a custom R function called "RDCC" (Relative Density and Canopy Cover), which transforms three-dimensional lidar point cloud data into an array of 28 distinct metrics for canopy height, canopy cover, and relative density (Table 4.2.1).

Table 4.2.1. List of the relative density canopy cover (RDCC) function output bands, variable name, and description of output variables. Variables are forest metrics derived from LAS point cloud input files.

Band	Variable	Description
1	Num_Returns	Total number of returns in cell
2	Num_GrndRet	Number of ground returns in cell
3	Num_1stRet	Number of first returns in cell
4	Grnd_Elev	Ground Elevations
5	Mn_RH	Mean of all Relative Heights
6	SD_RH	Std. Dev of all Relative heights
7	RHt_95th	Relative Height 95%
8	RHt_90th	Relative Height 90%
9	RHt_75th	Relative Height 75%
10	RHt_50th	Relative Height 50%
11	RHt_25th	Relative Height 25%
12	RHt_10th	Relative Height 10%
13	RHt_05th	Relative Height 5%
14	RD_2to10ft	Relative Density .6096-m to 3.048-m (Shrubs)
15	RD_10to20ft	Relative Density 3.048-m to 6.096-m (Low midstory)
16	RD_20to49ft	Relative Density 6.096-m to 14.935-m (High midstory)
17	RD_gt2ft	Relative Density all returns $\geq$.6096-m
18	RD_gt10ft	Relative Density all returns $\geq$ 3.048-m
19	RD_gt20ft	Relative Density all returns $\geq$ 6.096-m
20	RD_gt49ft	Relative Density all returns $\geq$ 14.935-m
21	CC_gt2ft	Canopy Cover $\geq$.6096-m (based only on first returns)
22	CC_gt10ft	Canopy Cover $\geq$ 3.048-m (based only on first returns)
23	CC_gt20ft	Canopy Cover $\geq$ 6.096-m (based only on first returns)
24	CC_gt49ft	Canopy Cover $\geq$ 14.935-m (based only on first returns)
25	MnRHgt2ft	Mean of all relative heights $\geq$.6096-m
26	MnRHgt10ft	Mean of all relative heights $\geq$ 3.048-m
27	MnRHgt20ft	Mean of all relative heights $\geq$ 6.096-m
28	MnRHgt49ft	Mean of all relative heights $\geq$ 14.935-m

The RDCC function is user-friendly and leverages freely accessible, open-source, and scalable software, effectively diminishing barriers to deploying lidar data across regional scales. Importantly, this process is transferable and adaptable, compatible with diverse lidar datasets that encompass various units, lack classified ground points, and originate from different lidar platforms (such as airborne and UAS). Such transferability empowers users to rapidly generate products tailored for land managers without necessitating point cloud classification, which proves to be invaluable in time-critical scenarios, like assessments of post-disaster forest damage.

We used the RDCC lidar workflow to translate 11TB of lidar point cloud data (approximately 22,000 files with over 375 billion lidar points) into layers of meaningful information related to forest structure. The products were multi-band raster datasets (GeoTIFFs), where each band is described in Table 4.2.1. These raster datasets were created at a 5-m resolution over the entire and 22,900 km²

Apalachicola Region. The entire process took just over 27 hours on a Windows laptop with 4 CPU cores and 16 GB of RAM. We also tested our workflow in a distributed cloud computing environment consisting of Linux virtual machines and an Azure storage blob for the 11 TB of lidar data. This Azure environment was funded through a grant to CSER from Microsoft’s AI for Earth program. Running on a virtual machine which utilized 30 logical cores, this processing step took 28.5 hours to complete. This makes our workflow approximately twice as fast as a Python package used to process a large lidar point cloud dataset distributed across a cluster of 6 virtual machines each with 6 cores and 32 GB RAM to produce 10-m resolution GeoTiffs with 21 bands (Meijer et al., 2020).

The canopy height, cover and density outputs created from RDCC selected in previous research found them to be useful forest metrics, which could provide information for a variety of forest management applications, such as wildlife habitat assessment and forest structure and inventory assessments as well as prescribed fire planning. Additionally, when combined with field plot data these primary lidar derivatives can be used to provide accurate estimates of stand density, basal area, vegetation biomass (Bouvier et al., 2015; Drake et al., 2003; Pearse et al., 2018; Yao et al., 2012), and understory canopy structure (Jarron et al., 2020, Zald et al., 2015). In this project, we used RDCC metrics to create spatial predictive models for several forest metrics, including basal area, trees per acre, quadratic mean diameter, and the basal area of trees within different size categories.

The general workflow illustrated in Figure 4.2.2 was adhered to each forest metric during the entirety of the modeling process. Utilizing the RDCC function, 5-meter resolution multi-band raster datasets were generated from the lidar point cloud data. Subsequently, focal statistics were computed on the RDCC outputs, yielding predictive raster datasets that featured 5-meter mean and standard deviation values across all 28 RDCC bands. The RMRS Raster Utility toolbar (Hogland & Anderson 2017) facilitated this operation. To align with the dimensions of the RESTORE field plots (Section 3.1), a neighborhood size of 40 meters by 40 meters was selected. This choice aimed to approximate the plot size accurately. These predictive layers were then integrated with summary information extracted from the RESTORE field plots, forming the basis for the creation of statistical models.

Figure 4.2.2. Workflow diagram with the RDCC open-source R function workflow shaded in blue on the left-hand side. The subsequent raster processing utilized the raster data generated by the RDCC function. This phase involved creating predictive raster datasets used to develop statistical models to derive forest metric raster datasets. The right-hand portion of the overall workflow can be conducted using various geographic or spatial software tools. Furthermore, it offers the flexibility to complimentary independent data, such as the spectral variables (St. Peter et al., 2021).

By sampling these predictive raster datasets at the precise locations of the RESTORE field plots, a consolidated dataset was constructed. This dataset provided the foundation for generating forest metric models. From the pool of 48 predictive raster surfaces (encompassing RDCC bands 5-28, represented as mean and standard deviations), predictor variables relevant to the target forest metric were meticulously chosen. The variable selection procedure followed a backward stepwise approach,

aligning with the methodologies outlined in Hogland et al., 2019. The subset of selected variables underwent further refinement by eliminating predictor variables that did not display statistical significance, resulting in the retention of a concise linear model. The final step in the overall workflow was to create raster surfaces for BAA, TPA and QMD from the linear models and the RDCC predictive raster datasets using the RMRS Raster Utility Arc toolbar (Hogland & Anderson, 2017). A summary of the outcomes of this modeling process is presented in Table 4.2.2.

Table 4.2.2. Model results for basal area per acre (BAA) in ft²/acre, trees per acre (TPA), and quadratic mean stem diameter (QMD) in inches; v is the number of variables used in the model, RMSE is the root mean squared error.

Response	adj. r ²	v	RMSE	Deviance Explained
All BAA	0.774	4	33.06	77.7%
Pine BAA	0.676	8	24.05	68.7%
All TPA	0.779	7	24.80	78.6%
All QMD	0.583	5	2.14	58.8%

In Figure 4.2.3, the QMD raster, derived from this workflow, is displayed. This raster encompasses the entire Apalachicola Region, which spans approximately 22,900-km². The forest metrics produced from this process were shared with forestry experts within the region. This step aimed to evaluate the practicality and qualitative significance of the outputs, and the assessment yielded very positive feedback. These products have been used in planning efforts, including risk mapping for Southern Pine Beetle (SPB) in dense plantations on the Apalachicola NF and surrounding lands.

In addition to generating raster outputs for total basal area (BAA) that encompassed all trees as well as pine trees, we extended our methodology to formulate models for BAA across distinct size classes, delineated by tree diameter at breast height (DBH). Unlike certain other studies, our approach refrained from attempting to model the distribution of individual tree diameters. Instead, we opted for a direct estimation of basal area, focusing on three tree size categories that held direct relevance to forest management objectives.

This decision was driven by the desire to streamline the process, fostering ease of reproducibility and method critique. Additionally, our approach aimed to circumvent the challenges tied to fitting a model curve, such as the Weibull distribution, to a distribution of tree diameters – an approach adopted in some studies (Packlen & Maltamo, 2007). These assumptions introduce complexities and potential errors that prove unwarranted in the context of our project goals. A simple linear model, in many cases, achieves comparable, if not superior, accuracy while directly modeling the target forest metric.

To estimate basal area based on DBH class, we incorporated methods elucidated by Hogland et al., 2020, a PhD graduate supported by CSER. These methods allowed for the spatial quantification of the standard error associated with our basal area estimates based on DBH. These standard error estimates serve a twofold purpose: they facilitate the identification of areas with heightened uncertainty, and they guide future sampling endeavors by pinpointing under-sampled regions.

The tree DBH size categories were selected based on their significance in forest operations and wildlife management. A 10" DBH threshold is pivotal in determining whether a tree can be utilized for pulp wood or saw timber, while pine trees greater than 14" DBH play a crucial role in the habitat of endangered species, the red-cockaded woodpecker (*Dryobates borealis*) (Nordman et al., 2016). The resulting size categories were structured as follows: 2"-10" DBH, 10"-14" DBH, and greater than 14" DBH.

Figure 4.2.3. Quadratic Mean Diameter (QMD) raster estimated from the workflow in Figure 4.2.2. The upper half of the figure shows the entire extent of the raster with the bottom insert area bordered in red. The spatial resolution of the raster is 5m.

This analysis entailed a comparison of three distinct modeling processes. The first approach was linear regression modeling, akin to previous modeling efforts showcased in Table 4.2.2. The other two methods involved ensemble models. These ensemble models employed a randomly selected subset of the data (75% of the data, selected with replacement), repeated multiple times (50 times in our case), to inform a multitude of models. The outcomes of these multiple models were subsequently averaged to yield a single modeled estimate. Additionally, the ensemble modeling approach generates data about the standard error of model estimates, which can be used to map the spatial variability inherent in modeled estimates.

The first of the ensemble methods used generalized additive models (ensemble GAM), adopting the methods and software outlined in Hogland 2021. The second approach, unique to our study, substituted GAM modeling with linear modeling, aptly named ensemble LM (ensemble linear modeling). The summarized outcomes of these models are presented in Table 4.2.3. The resultant raster outputs, covering all tree species within our study area, are depicted in Figures 4.2.4 and 4.2.5.

Table 4.2.3. Summary results for models of basal area per acre (BAA) in ft²/acre by tree diameter (DBH in inches). Best values for each tree diameter class are bolded. The “all” tree species DBH < 10 was an exponential model while all other models used a linear model. The pine models included a regional effect for the Leon block, except for the ensemble GAM models.

All Tree Species	Deviance Explained	RMSE	Non-Pine Tree Species	Deviance Explained	RMSE
DBH < 10 Single Model	0.657	28.42	DBH < 10 Single Model	0.657	22.89
DBH < 10 Ensemble LM	0.516	36.04	DBH < 10 Ensemble LM	0.667	22.29
DBH < 10 Ensemble GAM	0.675	28.36	DBH < 10 Ensemble GAM	0.731	20.09
DBH 10-14 Single Model	0.447	17.48	DBH 10-14 Single Model	0.445	14.31
DBH 10-14 Ensemble LM	0.456	17.14	DBH 10-14 Ensemble LM	0.459	13.93
DBH 10-14 Ensemble GAM	0.514	16.21	DBH 10-14 Ensemble GAM	0.511	13.25
DBH > 14 Single Model	0.709	19.04	DBH > 14 Single Model	0.593	19.03
DBH > 14 Ensemble LM	0.712	18.93	DBH > 14 Ensemble LM	0.606	18.54
DBH > 14 Ensemble GAM	0.805	15.63	DBH > 14 Ensemble GAM	0.623	18.11
Pine Tree Species	Deviance Explained	RMSE			
DBH < 10 Single Model	0.520	23.86			
DBH < 10 Ensemble LM	0.517	23.94			
DBH < 10 Ensemble GAM	0.695	19.12			
DBH 10-14 Single Model	0.476	13.12			
DBH 10-14 Ensemble LM	0.253	20.61			
DBH 10-14 Ensemble GAM	0.530	12.43			
DBH > 14 Single Model	0.537	12.04			
DBH > 14 Ensemble LM	0.543	11.97			
DBH > 14 Ensemble GAM	0.682	10.05			

Figure 4.2.4. Basal area (ft²/acre) of all tree species with diameter at breast height (DBH) greater than 14" across the whole ARRI region. The light blue box defines the area shown in close-up views in Figures 4.2.5. and 4.2.6.

In the subsequent stage, we conducted a comparative assessment of these three modeling methods based on their interpretability, practicality, and accuracy. The ensemble GAM approach emerged as the most accurate among the methods. However, it entailed a processing time 30 times longer than that required by the ensemble LM method. This prolonged processing time reduced its practicality, and its interpretability was hampered by the complex, opaque nature of GAM models.

In contrast, the ensemble LM method exhibited superior accuracy in most cases compared to the single model approach. It also boasted better interpretability and quicker processing times than the ensemble GAM models. Both ensemble techniques offered the added advantage of generating standard error raster datasets, an illustrative instance of which is displayed in Figure 4.2.6. On the other hand, the single linear regression method proved notably more interpretable and practical to generate. However, it was less accurate than the ensemble models (excluding ensemble LM models for pine trees), and it did not produce a standard error raster. Our objective in comparing these modeling approaches was to underscore the merits and limitations intrinsic to each of these methods. This insight is intended to inform decision-making for future analysis projects, whether within or beyond the scope of the ARRI study area.

Figure 4.2.5. Comparison of three DBH classes for estimating basal area (BA). Top left is 2021 true color NAIP imagery for a subset of the ARRI study area focused on Telogia Creek (see light blue box in Figure 4.2.4). Top right is BA (ft²/acre) of all tree species with DBH < 10", bottom left is BA of all tree species with DBH 10"-14" and bottom right is BA of all tree species with DBH >14". The resolution of all BA raster layers is 5m.

The raster outputs generated from the lidar processing and modeling workflows described in this section serve as a foundational cornerstone for various ensuing endeavors within this project. These include the estimation of forest ecological conditions (Section 4.3) and potential water yield gains from forest thinning (Section 4.4), as well as provision of essential information for decision support tools, as detailed in section 5.5 of this report. Moreover, the workflows devised within this section offer versatility beyond their initial scope. Notably, they are applicable not only to airborne lidar data, typically characterized by 4 to 8 pulses per square meter, but also to ultra-dense drone-borne lidar point clouds, featuring hundreds of pulses per square meter. This transformation yields valuable metrics such as canopy cover and shrub density, illustrated in Figure 4.2.7. The resultant drone-derived forest structure datasets can subsequently be combined with forest plot data to derive secondary forest metrics, such as basal area, employing the workflow delineated in Figure 4.2.2. The adaptable nature of these lidar workflows ensures their potential utilization in monitoring the efficacy of forest management activities during subsequent phases of ARRI (Section 6.2).

Figure 4.2.6. Standard error estimate (in ft²/acre) of the BA model for all tree species with DBH >14" (shown in bottom right of Figure 4.2.5). Stand error raster was produced using the ensemble GAM methods developed by Hogland et al., 2020.

Figure 4.2.7. Top: Drone-borne 3D lidar point cloud (100s of points per square meter) from the University of Florida’s GatorEye platform. Bottom: 2D raster surfaces derived using RDCC workflow (St. Peter and Drake 2021) such as 95% canopy height (left), canopy cover (middle) and shrub density (right).

References

- Bouvier, M., Durrieu, S., Fournier, R. A., & Renaud, J. P. (2015). Generalizing predictive models of forest inventory attributes using an area-based approach with airborne Lidar data. *Remote Sensing of the Environment* 156, 322–334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2014.10.004>
- Cohen, M., McLaughlin, D., Kaplan, D., & Acharya, S. (2017). *Managing Forest for Increase Regional Water Availability: Report on Task 7: Year 3 Annual Report*. (FDACS Contract No. 20834). Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services. State of Florida. https://www.fdacs.gov/content/download/76293/file/20834_Del_7.pdf
- Darracq, A. K., Boone, W. W., & McCleery, R. A. (2016). Burn regime matters: A review of the effects of prescribed fire on vertebrates in the longleaf pine ecosystem. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 378, 214–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2016.07.039>
- Drake, J. B., Knox, R. G., Dubayah, R. O., Clark, D. B., Condit, R., Blair, J. B., & Hofton, M. (2003). Above-ground biomass estimation in closed canopy Neotropical forests using lidar remote sensing: Factors affecting the generality of relationships. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 12, 147–159. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1466-822X.2003.00010.x>
- Garabedian, J., Moorman, C., Peterson, M. N., & Kilgo, J. (2017). Use of Lidar to define habitat thresholds for forest bird conservation. *Forest Ecology Management*, 399, 24–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2017.05.024>
- Hogland, J., & Anderson, N. (2017). Function Modeling Improves the Efficiency of Spatial Modeling Using Big Data from Remote Sensing. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 1(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc1010003>

- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., Affleck, D. L., & St. Peter, J. (2019). Using Forest Inventory Data with Landsat 8 Imagery to Map Longleaf Pine Forest Characteristics in Georgia, USA. *Remote Sensing*, 11(15), 1803. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11151803>
- Hogland, J., Affleck, D. L., Anderson, N., Seielstad, C., Dobrowski, S., Graham, J., & Smith, R. (2020). Estimating Forest Characteristics for Longleaf Pine Restoration Using Normalized Remotely Sensed Imagery in Florida USA. *Forests*, 11(4), 426. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f11040426>
- Jarron, L. R., Coops, N. C., MacKenzie, W. H., Tompalski, P., & Dykstra, P. (2020). Detection of sub-canopy forest structure using airborne Lidar. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 244, 111770. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.111770>
- Hogland, J. (2021). *Ensemble Generalized Additive Models (EGAM)*. Jupyter Notebook: <https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1GnRagruTUCoPJQZSkZ2vMKS9aAKgnhEw>
- Meijer, C., Grootes, M., Koma, Z., Dzigan, Y., Gonçalves, R., Andela, B., van den Oord, G., Rangelova, E., Renaud, N., & Kissling, W. (2020). Laserchicken-A tool for distributed feature calculation from massive Lidar point cloud datasets. *SoftwareX*, 12, 100626. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2020.100626>
- Nordman, C., White, R., Wilson, R., Ware, C., Rideout, C., Pyne, M., & Hunter, C. (2016, May 12) *Rapid Assessment Metrics to Enhance Wildlife Habitat and Biodiversity within Southern Open Pine Ecosystems*. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and NatureServe, for the Gulf Coastal Plains and Ozarks Landscape Conservation Cooperative. https://www.natureserve.org/sites/default/files/projects/files/openpinemetrics-finalreport_12may16.pdf
- Packalen, P., & Maltamo, M. (2008). Estimation of species-specific diameter distributions using airborne laser scanning and aerial photographs. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*, 38, 1750-1760.
- Pearse, G. D., Dash, J. P., Persson, H. J., & Watt, M. S. (2018). Comparison of high-density Lidar and satellite photogrammetry for forest inventory. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 142, 257–267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2018.06.006>
- Roussel J., Auty D., Coops N.C., Tompalski P., Goodbody T.R., Meador A.S., Bourdon J., de Boissieu F., & Achim A. (2020). lidR: An R package for analysis of Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) data. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 251, 112061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.112061>
- Roussel J. & Auty D. (2022, December 15). *Airborne LiDAR Data Manipulation and Visualization for Forestry Applications* (R package version 4.0.2). <https://cran.r-project.org/package=lidR>
- St. Peter, J., & Drake, J. (2021). RDCC- R Workflow to Derive Forest Relative Density and Canopy Cover metrics from Lidar Point Cloud Data (8.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8253263>
- St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., & Ibeanusi, V. (2021). Forest Structural Estimates Derived Using a Practical, Open-Source Lidar-Processing Workflow. *Remote Sensing* 13(23), 4763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13234763>
- Trager, M. D., Drake, J. B., Jenkins, A. M., & Petrick, C.J. (2018). Mapping and Modeling Ecological Conditions of Longleaf Pine Habitats in the Apalachicola National Forest. *Journal of Forestry*, 116, 304–311. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jofore/fvx017>
- Yao, W., Krzystek, P., & Heurich, M. (2012). Tree Species classification and estimation of stem volume and DBH based on single tree extraction by exploiting airborne full-waveform Lidar data. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 123, 368–380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2012.03.027>
- Young, J. A., Mahan, C. G., & Forder, M. (2017). Integration of Vegetation Community Spatial Data into a Prescribed Fire Planning Process at Shenandoah National Park Virginia (USA). *Natural Areas Journal*, 37, 394–405. <https://doi.org/10.3375/043.037.0312>
- Zald, H. S., Wulder, M. A., White, J. C., Hilker, T., Hermosilla, T., Hobart, G. W., & Coops, N. C. (2015). Integrating Landsat pixel composites and change metrics with lidar plots to predictively map

forest structure and aboveground biomass in Saskatchewan, Canada. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 176, 188–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2016.01.015>

4.3 Estimating Ecological Condition of Open Pine Forests

Assessing and monitoring the ecological condition of forests helps understand the health of these ecosystems and their ability to support diverse species and provide numerous ecosystem services including carbon sequestration, water purification, soil erosion control, and climate regulation. Ecological condition assessment allows forest managers to track changes over time and practice adaptive management techniques to promote sustainable forests that balance ecological, social, and economic needs. Understanding the ecological condition of forests also helps assess their resilience to various natural and human-induced disturbances, such as wildfires, pests, and pathogens. Perhaps most importantly, ecological condition assessments are an effective way to combine disparate datasets about forests into simple condition scores to help guide management and conservation efforts.

In the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project, we built upon past efforts to estimate current conditions of Southern open pine forests in comparison with desired conditions. For example, the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and NatureServe developed rapid field assessment techniques (hereafter referred to as “Rapid Field Approach”) to assess open pine forest conditions based on reports, studies, and feedback from conservation stakeholders and experts at in-person workshops (Nordman et al. 2016). The US Forest Service, National Forests in Florida also worked closely with Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI) to develop an Ecological Condition Model (ECM) for the Apalachicola National Forest (Trager et al. 2018). This approach, which will hereafter be referred to as the “2016 ANF ECM” was developed from USFS corporate datasets (e.g., forest stand data), historic natural community data, forest fire history, and forest structural data from airborne lidar data collected from 2007 to 2011. The 2016 ANF ECM was validated with over 300 field plots where ecological condition was assessed by experienced FNAI and USFS scientists. This method was determined to be remarkably accurate and closely aligned with habitat types selected by the federally threatened red-cockaded woodpecker (see Trager et al. 2018 and Section 7.2 for more details on the 2016 ANF ECM).

Our overarching goal in the THS1 Project was to develop a new ECM that could seamlessly span all lands in the Apalachicola Region using repeatable methods that could later be used to characterize other regions. As such, we used only datasets that were available throughout the area and did not rely on any data layers from specific landowners to inform the model. Furthermore, we sought to assess ecological condition at a high enough spatial resolution to guide management effectiveness at the scale of individual forest stands or across the whole landscape. By taking this approach, we created ecological condition scores that could be readily updated through time to measure progress and gauge the effectiveness of management activities at multiple scales.

Methods

The first step of the ECM process was to identify datasets that could be used to mask/exclude areas that should not be included in the model, such as hardwood dominated floodplain forests and urban areas. Unfortunately, a detailed, field-validated historic natural community dataset, such as the one developed for the 2016 ANF ECM (Section 7.1), does not currently exist for the entire project area. Instead, we utilized the Florida Cooperative Land Cover (CLC) dataset produced through a partnership between the Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC) and Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI). The CLC is a continuously revised, ecologically-based statewide land cover developed from existing sources with different land managers, and expert reviews of aerial photography (FWC, 2022). We identified all land cover classes related to open pine ecosystems (e.g., flatwoods, sandhill, upland pine) and created a simple binary (1= open pine, 0= all other land cover) raster product. We also

used the CLC data to refine the input layer weightings (i.e., relative importance) for wet prairies and pine plantations as detailed in the tables below.

The next step in the ecological condition modeling process was to separately assess canopy conditions as well as midstory and understory layers using suitable and readily available geospatial datasets that cover the whole project area. To accomplish this, we carefully evaluated input datasets and condition class thresholds defined in the Rapid Field Approach and the 2016 ANF ECM. It is critical to note that the Rapid Field Approach defined four ecological condition classes (1- excellent, 2- good, 3- fair, 4- poor), whereas the 2016 ANF ECM defined five classes (1- excellent, 2- good, 3- fair, 4- poor, 5- very poor). The “1- excellent” condition class used in the 2016 ANF ECM represented less than 1% of the Apalachicola NF and was used primarily to distinguish older stands. Because of this, and since areas defined as “1- excellent” or “2- good” in the 2016 ANF NF ECM are managed the same (i.e., maintained with regular prescribed fire), we decided to use the four condition class system developed for the Rapid Field Approach by collapsing classes 1 and 2 from the 2016 ANF ECM into the “1- excellent” condition class (see Table 4.3.1. for crosswalk).

Table 4.3.1. Ecological condition score crosswalk used in the 2016 Apalachicola NF ECM (Trager et al. 2018) and the current, ARRI-wide ECM developed for the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project based on the “Rapid Field Approach” from Nordman et al., 2016.

2016 Apalachicola NF Ecological Condition Model (“2016 ANF ECM”)	ARRI-wide ECM and “Rapid Field Approach”
Excellent (1) and Good (2)	Excellent (1)
Fair (3)	Good (2)
Poor (4)	Fair (3)
Very Poor (5)	Poor (4)

The third step examined all input data used in both the Rapid Field Approach and the 2016 ANF ECM. As part of this effort, CSER produced many directly equivalent input datasets such as canopy pine and hardwood basal area, stand density index (SDI) and canopy cover (see Section 4.2). Related CSER datasets were used in place of some input data, such as midstory and shrub relative density from lidar for field-estimated overall midstory and shrub cover. It was not always possible to use a replacement dataset for some input datasets, for example the USFS stand age data used in the 2016 ANF ECM. Nevertheless, the input datasets used in this ECM were directly and indirectly related to nearly all input datasets for both the Rapid Field Approach and the 2016 ANF ECM.

To complete this process, all input data layers were first reclassified into 4 different ecological conditions based on threshold values used in the Rapid Field Approach and the 2016 ANF ECM. This was an iterative procedure that required testing threshold values from both approaches across several areas of the project area that were well known to CSER staff, for example areas on the ANF, Tate’s Hell State Forest, Tall Timbers Research Station, Apalachicola Bluffs and Ravines, and private pine plantations in the “Red Hills” near Tall Timbers. In most cases, “compromise” thresholds between the thresholds defined for the 2016 ANF ECM and those defined for the Rapid Field Approach were used. For lidar-derived metrics without a direct field equivalent (e.g., the relative density of shrubs) threshold values from the 2016 ANF ECM were used.

The fourth step of the revised ECM methodology used the weighted sum tool in ArcGIS Pro (Esri Inc., 2023) to assign a higher weight or relative importance to some of the input layers and combine all input scores into an overall score for canopy, midstory, or understory. Each of these workflows (canopy, midstory, and understory) was created using Model Builder in ArcGIS Pro so it could be derived rapidly for smaller areas well known to CSER staff in an iterative manner to adjust input weights as needed (see Figure 4.3.1 for canopy Model Builder workflow). All ECM workflows and tools have been posted to an online repository for use in future projects (Drake et al., 2023a).

Figure 4.3.1. ArcGIS Pro Model Builder (ESRI Inc. 2023) example used to calculate component ecological condition model scores (Drake et al., 2023a).

The input raster data layers (Drake et al., 2023b), their overall weight/importance, and threshold ranges used to derive ecological condition scores are listed below for canopy (Table 4.3.2), midstory (Table 4.3.3) and understory (Table 4.3.4). As previously mentioned, nearly all input data were derived from CSER using airborne lidar data (Section 4.2). However for the understory layer we incorporated fire history data from the Florida Fire Occurrence Dataset (1994-2019)[‡], which was derived from Landsat Imagery using the USGS Landsat Burned Area Essential Climate Variable (BAECV²) (FWC, 2020; Teske et al., 2021). Because wet prairies are very different structurally from all other open pine ecosystems, we developed separate thresholds for many canopy and understory layers in these areas. Multiple iterative QA/QC evaluations followed this particular step to help validate the data prior to the final step primarily because there were many “moving parts” encountered while transitioning from the 2016 Apalachicola NF Ecological Condition Model (“2016 ANF ECM”) to the ARRI-wide ECM and “Rapid Field Approach”.

² The Landsat Burned Area Essential Climate Variable (BAECV[‡]) data, developed by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS), uses multi-temporal Landsat imagery to identify burned areas across the conterminous U.S. using a semi-automated algorithm. This approach has been adopted by Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission and partners from Tall Timbers Research Station to produce the Florida Fire Occurrence Dataset as well as SE FireMap tool[‡] which is anticipated for broad release in 2025.

Table 4.3.2. Raster input layers for ECM canopy condition assessment and ranges for determining condition scores. The right-hand column represents threshold differences applied to areas identified as wet prairies (note- gray cells represent no difference from range in middle column). Weighted sum percentages represent relative weight (out of 100%) for each input used to determine overall canopy condition scores.

Canopy Input Layer (Weighted Sum %)	Condition Score	Ranges	Wet Prairie Ranges
Pine Basal Area (35%)	Excellent	30-60 ft ² / acre	0-20
	Good	20-30 or 60-80	20-60
	Fair	0-20 or 80-90	60-90
	Poor	>90	
Hardwoods Basal Area (15%)	Excellent	0-12 ft ² / acre	
	Good	12-22	
	Fair	22-37	
	Poor	>37	
Pine Basal Area, DBH>14" (10%)	Excellent	>20 ft ² / acre	0-10
	Good	10-20	10-20
	Fair	>0-10	>0-10
	Poor	0	0
Canopy Cover (15%)	Excellent	20-55%	0-20%
	Good	0-20% or 55-65%	20-65%
	Fair	65-85%	
	Poor	>85%	
Stand Density Index (25%)	Excellent	60-125	0-40
	Good	40-60 or 125-160	40-125
	Fair	20-40 or 160-200	125-160
	Poor	0 to 20 or >200	>160

Table 4.3.3. Raster input layers for ECM midstory condition assessment and ranges used to determine condition scores. Weighted sum percentages represent the relative weight (out of 100%) for each input used to determine overall canopy condition scores.

Midstory Input Layer (Weighted Sum %)	Condition Score	Ranges
Lidar Relative Density 20-49 feet (50%)	Excellent	0-5%
	Good	5-10%
	Fair	10-20%
	Poor	>20%
Lidar Relative Density 20-49 feet (40%)	Excellent	0-5%
	Good	5-10%
	Fair	10-20%
	Poor	>20%
Hardwoods Basal Area (10%)	Excellent	0-12 ft ² / acre
	Good	12-22
	Fair	22-37
	Poor	>37

Table 4.3.4. Raster input layers for ECM understory condition assessment and ranges for determining condition scores. The right-hand column represents threshold differences applied to areas identified as wet prairies (note- gray cells represent no difference from range in middle column). Weighted sum percentages represent relative weight (out of 100%) for each input used for canopy condition scores.

Understory Input Layer (Weighted Sum %)	Condition Score	Ranges	Wet Prairie Ranges
Lidar Relative Density 2-10 feet 20%	Excellent	0-5%	0-1%
	Good	5-7.5%	1-7.5%
	Fair	7.5-20%	
	Poor	>20%	
Canopy Cover (3x3 focal mean) 60%	Excellent	0-50%	0-20%
	Good	50-60%	20-50%
	Fair	60-80%	50-60%
	Poor	>80%	>60%
Total Number of Fires 20%	Excellent	>3	
	Good	2	
	Fair	1	
	Poor	0	

The final step in this ECM process was to combine the ecological condition scores from the canopy, midstory, and understory workflows into an overall ecological condition score. This was done using the weighted sum tool with the values shown in Table 4.3.5. Initially, all areas were weighted the same, however, they were later adjusted for wet prairies to emphasize the importance of understory metrics. CSER staff also noticed that recently clear-cut pine plantations had undesirably higher ecological condition scores. This occurred primarily because clearer areas typically have no midstory or shrub concerns. By weighting canopy scores slightly higher, most cleared plantation scores were adjusted to more suitable levels (e.g., “Fair” vs. “Good”). Given that most pine plantations are mechanically and/or chemically site prepped, and assuming this activity results in “long-lasting” impacts to the ground cover, this adjustment is justified. Later, CSER staff plan to explore the utility of high resolution (1m) probabilistic land cover data derived from the Longleaf Mapping Project (Section 7.3) to further refine and improve understory condition estimates. For example, the probabilistic estimates for shrub and grass cover may complement existing lidar derived shrub cover estimates (Table 4.3.4).

Table 4.3.5. ECM weights used to produce overall condition scores. Weights were adjusted for wet prairies and pine plantations in the Cooperative Land Cover dataset (FWC, 2022).

ECM Component	Weighted Sum %	Weighted Sum % Adjusted for Wet Prairies	Weighted Sum % Adjusted for Plantations
Canopy	60%	10%	70%
Midstory	15%	30%	10%
Understory	25%	60%	20%

Results

Final outputs from ECM workflows utilized in this study are high resolution (5 m) raster datasets for canopy, midstory, understory, and overall ecological condition spanning nearly 2.5 million acres of open pine ecosystems throughout the Apalachicola Region including private lands (Drake et al., 2023c, see Figure 4.3.2). This outcome provides consistent, detailed, and granular data which can be used by

individual landowners as well as by groups working across land ownerships and type to strive towards common restoration goals such as the Apalachicola Regional Stewardship Alliance (ARSA).

When all regional open pine lands are considered, the vast majority (71%) are estimated to be in fair or poor condition. However, if only public or private conservation lands are considered (FNAI, 2023, transparent gray overlay areas shown in Figure 4.3.2) then the relative proportion in excellent or good condition (~45%) is much higher. In fact, of all open pine lands in excellent or good condition throughout the region, over half (54%) are found in conservation lands despite representing only 35% of the total open pine area. The summary of ecological condition scores for all open pine lands in the Apalachicola Region, Florida Conservation Lands, and the Apalachicola National Forest are listed in Table 4.3.6.

Figure 4.3.2. Overall ecological condition scores for open pine communities across the Apalachicola Region. ECM estimates from lidar derived data products are discussed in Section 4.2, the Cooperative Land Cover (FWC, 2022), and Florida Fire Occurrence Datasets from the Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission. A total of 2,224,459 acres of open pine habitat was evaluated based on information from Nordman et al., 2016 and Trager et al., 2018. Florida Conservation Lands (FNAI, 2023) are shown as a transparent light gray overlay.

Table 4.3.6. Summary of ecological condition scores for all open pine communities within the Apalachicola Region, Conservation Lands (FNAI, 2023) and the Apalachicola NF.

ECM Score	ARRI-Wide		FL Conservation Lands		Apalachicola NF	
	Open Pine (Acres)	Total Area (%)	Open Pine (Acres)	Total Area (%)	Open Pine (Acres)	Total Area (%)
1- Excellent	232,401	10.4%	163,525	21.1%	98,989	25.4%
2- Good	407,392	18.3%	182,662	23.6%	80,789	20.8%
3- Fair	857,793	38.6%	214,508	27.7%	100,271	25.8%
4- Poor	726,873	32.7%	214,493	27.7%	109,107	28.0%
Total	2,224,459		775,188		389,156	

We compared the ECM results with prior results from the 2016 ANF ECM (Trager et al. 2018, Section 7.2.2). To accomplish this, the region-wide ECM was clipped using the Apalachicola NF (ANF) boundary (Figure 4.3.3) and then the distribution of ecological condition scores was compared to the distribution from 2016 ANF ECM (Table 4.3.7). The relative distribution of ecological condition scores in either excellent or poor condition shows remarkable similarity, whereas there is slightly higher disagreement in the relative distribution of areas in either good or fair condition which aligns with expert opinion resulting from decades of experience traversing and studying the ANF.

Table 4.3.7. Comparison of overall ECM scores from 2016 ANF ECM and ARRI-wide ECM clipped to ANF boundary. See crosswalk of old vs. new class scores in Table 4.3.1.

Condition Score	2016 ANF ECM	ARRI-wide ECM Clipped to ANF
1- Excellent	24% (79,137 ac)	25% (98,989 ac)
2- Good	28% (97,140 ac)	21% (80,789 ac)
3- Fair	22% (73,571 ac)	26% (100,271 ac)
4- Poor	27% (91,232 ac)	28% (109,107 ac)

Figure 4.3.3. Overall ecological condition scores for all open pine communities on the Apalachicola NF.

It is important to note that areas from the updated ECM differed slightly from the 2016 ANF ECM because the latest method used CLC data (FWC, 2022) to define open pine habitat whereas the 2016 version used historic natural community data developed specifically for the ANF (Section 7.2.1). There were also some small private inholdings recently added to the ANF which were not included in the 2016 ANF ECM. One such inholding can be seen in the large square area of the center of Figure 4.3.4. The western portion of this inholding had no stand data, so although it was included in the 2016 ANF ECM, it was uniformly scored in poor condition. In contrast, the eastern portion was not yet part of the ANF and was not included. Both areas were evaluated and showed much greater variability in ecological conditions in the western portion of the former inholding. Outside of this former inholding, there is generally close agreement in the spatial distribution of ecological conditions between the two approaches (Figure 4.3.4). All told, the updated ECM included 48,076 additional acres that were not evaluated in the 2016 ANF ECM. It is plausible these additional acres could account for some differences in the relative distribution of ecological condition scores as well as the acreages in each class (Table 4.3.7). Additionally, the 2016 ANF ECM utilized several corporate datasets such as stand age and canopy dominant species to estimate ecological conditions, whereas the current estimate utilized only datasets that were available across all lands within the region. Given these differences in methodology, and total area evaluated, the agreement in overall distribution of ecological scores (Table 4.3.7) and the spatial patterns of ecological conditions from both models (Figure 4.3.4) validates the utility and transferability of this regionwide approach when compared to the peer-reviewed 2016 ANF ECM (Trager et al. 2018).

Figure 4.3.4. Close-up of ecological conditions estimated in 2016 ANF ECM (Trager et al. 2018) at 0.5 acre resolution using data from 2007-2014 (Top), and ecological conditions estimated for the THS1 Project at 5-m resolution using geospatial data from 2018- 2022 (Bottom).

As a final validation step, CSER staff compared ECM estimates with field estimates collected by FNAI scientists from 2011-2017 captured in 354 field plots widely distributed across the ANF. As was the case with the 2016 ANF ECM, nearly half (46%) of the ECM estimates were in the same condition score as those assigned in the field and nearly 90% were either in the same class or were one class removed from the field-assessed score (e.g., ECM predicts “3- fair”, field assessment of “4- poor”). A preliminary analysis of the areas where the ECM score did not agree with the field assessments did reveal two interesting trends. First, 96 out of the 354 field plots were identified in the field by FNAI scientists as wet prairies. This high percentage (27%) of field plots from a natural community that represents only 7% of the total open pine area on the ANF may seem odd, however these communities have very high biodiversity and many of these field plots correspond to monitoring locations for federally listed plants. Interestingly, 74 out of these 96 plots were not classified as wet prairies in the statewide CLC data meaning that these areas were evaluated using the thresholds for general open pine (Tables 4.3.2 and 4.3.4) which resulted in nearly 70% of these areas being at least one ECM class off. Secondly, some differences resulted from restoration activities that had occurred since the original field assessments were made (96% in 2011-2014). Airborne lidar data used to create most of input data layers for the ECM were collected in 2018. We have not conducted a detailed analysis of this discrepancy, however, areas that received mechanical treatments between 2014 and 2018 to reduce midstory and shrubs were all scored higher in the ECM than originally assigned in the field. A more detailed analysis of differences in timber sale areas may reveal the same trend. However, the dates when timber was cut are not available, but rather when the timber was sold.

Despite these differences and given that our approach did not rely on corporate stand data (species composition, age) or past management activity data (e.g., mechanical site preparation, TSI, commercial thinning), the overall agreement between the revised region-wide ECM, the 2016 ANF ECM, and 2011-2017 field plots, illustrates the accuracy and reliability of this approach. Further refinements are always possible as other data layers become available and additional field validation efforts outside of the ANF are pursued. That said, partners may want to adjust weightings of input layers or add additional layers to improve the accuracy for their specific restoration needs. Nonetheless, this regional ECM, and the 2016 ANF ECM that preceded it, provide a baseline dataset for future studies as well as an adaptable and repeatable workflow to be used in other efforts including the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI)- Strategies 2 & 3 to help monitor the effectiveness of management activities over time.

References

- Drake, Jason, St. Peter, Joseph, Medley, Paul, & Vernon, Jordan. (2023a). Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative Open Pine Ecological Condition Model (2023)- ArcPro Toolbox (2023 (v1)). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8236853>
- Drake, Jason, St. Peter, Joseph, Medley, Paul, & Vernon, Jordan. (2023b). Input raster datasets for Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative Open Pine Ecological Condition Model (2023) (2023 (v1)) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8234220>
- Drake, Jason, St. Peter, Joseph, Medley, Paul, & Vernon, Jordan. (2023c). Output raster datasets from Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative Open Pine Ecological Condition Model (2023) (2023 (v1)) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8237290>
- Esri Inc. (2023). ArcGIS Pro (Version 3.1) [Computer software]. Environmental Systems Research Institute.

- Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC). (2022). *Florida Cooperative Land Cover Map*, (Version 3.5) [Data set]. State of Florida. <https://myfwc.com/research/gis/regional-projects/cooperative-land-cover>
- Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC). (2020). *Florida Fire Occurrence Data*. [Data set]. State of Florida. <https://myfwc.com/research/gis/wildlife/florida-fire/>
- Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI). (2023). Florida Conservation Lands, (May, 2023 update) [Data set]. <https://www.fnai.org/publications/gis-data>
- Nordman, C., White, R., Wilson, R., Ware, C., Rideout, C., Pyne, M., & Hunter, C. (2016). *Rapid assessment metrics to enhance wildlife habitat and biodiversity within Southern open pine ecosystems*. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and NatureServe. https://www.natureserve.org/sites/default/files/openpinemetrics-finalreport_12may16.pdf
- Teske, C., Vanderhoof, M. K., Hawbaker, T. J., Noble, J., & Hiers, J. K. (2021). Using the Landsat Burned Area Products to Derive Fire History Relevant for Fire Management and Conservation in the State of Florida, Southeastern USA. *Fire*, 4(2), 26. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/fire4020026>
- Trager, M. D., Drake, J. B., Jenkins, A. M., & Petrick, C.J. (2018). Mapping and Modeling Ecological Conditions of Longleaf Pine Habitats in the Apalachicola National Forest. *Journal of Forestry*, 116, 304–311. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jofore/fvx017>

4.4 Potential Water Yield from Southeastern Pine Forests

Ecosystem services encompass the numerous benefits that our natural environment provides to humans and other living organisms. Healthy forested ecosystems offer an extensive array of crucial services alongside indispensable timber resources. Besides valuable products such as wood, resin, fruits, nuts, mushrooms, and other non-timber goods that are used for food, medicine, and textiles, here are some vital services provided (in no particular order) by forested ecosystems:

- **Recreation and Tourism**
 - Forests provide spaces for various recreational activities like hiking, camping, birdwatching, and ecotourism, which have economic and health benefits.
- **Cultural and Aesthetic Values**
 - Forests hold cultural significance for many communities and indigenous groups. They also provide aesthetic beauty and a sense of connection to nature.
- **Medicinal Resources**
 - Many medicinal plants and traditional remedies are found in forests, contributing to human health and well-being.
- **Biodiversity Support**
 - Forests offer a home to countless plant and animal species, supporting biodiversity.
 - Many valuable genetic resources, such as rare medicinal plants and threatened animal species can be only found in healthy forests.
- **Pollination Services**
 - Forests support pollinator populations (e.g., bats, bees, butterflies), which are essential for the reproduction of many plant species, including agricultural crops.
- **Nutrient Cycling**
 - Decomposition and nutrient recycling: Forest ecosystems contribute to the breakdown of organic matter and recycling of nutrients, enriching the soil.
- **Climate Regulation**
 - Forests absorb and store carbon dioxide (carbon sequestration), helping mitigate climate change by reducing greenhouse gas concentrations.
 - Trees improve air quality by filtering pollutants and enhancing human health.

- **Climate Adaptation**
 - Forests can help buffer against extreme weather events like storms and provide shade, cooling urban areas and reducing the heat island effect.
- **Erosion Control**
 - Forests stabilize soils and prevent erosion by holding the soil in place with their root systems which can minimize the erosive impact of rainfall and flowing water on the soil surface.
- **Water Regulation**
 - Forests protect watersheds and maintain steady water flows by absorbing and releasing water gradually, reducing the risk of floods and droughts. By acting like a natural sponge, forests slow down water flows during heavy rainfall which can reduce the risk of downstream flooding, and conversely forests hold water in reservoirs and wetlands during drier periods.
 - Trees and other vegetation can impact water evaporation by the process of transpiration which is basically the exhalation of water vapor through tiny openings on the surface of leaves called stomata. This can regulate the quantity of freshwater that is either lost to the atmosphere or returned to the landscape.
- **Water Purification**
 - Trees and vegetation filter pollutants from rainwater and trap sediments that impair water quality.

To summarize, these ecosystem services underscore the critical significance of conserving and sustainably managing forested ecosystems to ensure the continual welfare of both human societies and the natural world. Poorly managed forests can have detrimental effects on ecosystem services, impacting both the environment and neighboring communities reliant on them. By comprehending a forest's health, composition, and structure, managers can make informed choices about management activities that either enhance or harm these services. Long-term sustainable land management practices are developed by quantifying the impacts of various activities, gauging their adverse effects on the environment, communities, and ecosystems.

Accurate and easily accessible forest structural and condition data are indispensable for effective forest management, as they not only aid in timber resource management but also in assessing broader impacts on critical resources and services. Reliable data empowers forest managers to formulate strategies that optimize their goals, ensuring the forests' health and productivity for years to come. Modern technologies like remote sensing expedite strategy development and can transcend traditional administrative boundaries.

In the Apalachicola Region and across the Southeastern U.S., overly dense off-site pine stands, which replace native longleaf pine forests, present challenges. These fast-growing plantation pine species can stifle longleaf pine regeneration, disrupting the ecosystem's equilibrium, reducing biodiversity, and hampering resilience. Densely packed stands reduce the cover of native, pyrogenic herbaceous species which in turn obstructs frequent fires crucial for longleaf pine forests, leading to fuel buildup and heightened wildfire risk, with potential catastrophic consequences.

This disruption also reverberates through water resources. Dense pine stands tend to have higher water demands due to increased evapotranspiration rates, reducing available groundwater and surface water resources. This impacts stream flow and water availability for wetlands, which are crucial for microclimate regulation. Proper forest management practices, such as thinning dense stands, prescribed burning, and nurturing native longleaf pine growth, are vital to address these issues.

Given the emphasis on water by RESTORE and the THS1 Project, evaluating potential impacts on water resources becomes crucial for responsible and sustainable forest management that balances human needs with environmental preservation. As such, this section presents newly developed

predictive water yield models and workflows, providing accurate data products that offer operational management tools. These tools allow land managers to prioritize terrestrial and hydrologic restoration projects concurrently. Spearheaded by CSER staff and former Ph.D. student Christy Crandall, this endeavor establishes an integrated and forward-looking water yield methodology, aiming to uncover water sources that could be returned to ecosystems as a beneficial service. This methodology blends established forest management practices with peer-reviewed water models to derive predictive, spatially-explicit water yield estimates from high-resolution forest and climate datasets under various timber management scenarios and climate conditions. Additionally, these workflows address the link between upland pine management and enhancing available water resources in the Apalachicola River, and Bay. This is vital not only for forest health but also for supporting fisheries like the Eastern oyster (*Crassostrea virginica*), an iconic staple of the Gulf Coast.

In 2018, University of Florida researchers concluded a multi-year project[‡] funded by Florida’s Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services (FDACS[‡]) to collect in-situ data on southern pine forests in Florida with the primary goal of developing a simple, robust method to estimate forest water yield at a stand level (Cohen, Kaplan, & Acharya, 2018). In-situ data were collected at sites across North and Central Florida under various types of ownership with different dominant pine species, stocking densities, and management practices to capture the complete range of Florida’s pine forests. Sites were monitored for four years with collected data including soil characteristics, standard forest metrics, and meteorological data. The presented empirical model, available in the 2022 peer-reviewed publication from Acharya et al., 2022, shows that leaf area index, depth to groundwater, and aridity index (a ratio of potential evapotranspiration to precipitation) are the strongest predictors of stand water yield.

To spatially apply this water yield model to the ARRI project area, four remotely sensed raster datasets, shown in Table 4.4.1, were compiled, including a pine species basal area product developed using data and methodologies from Section 4.2 of this document. These inputs (Vernon & St. Peter, 2022a) were then processed with custom geospatial tools for ArcGIS Pro and custom Python scripts to output water yield estimates (Vernon & St. Peter, 2022b) for current conditions as well as three different timber thinning scenarios and three likely climate scenarios. The production of both an ArcGIS Pro toolbox (Vernon, 2022) and Python script (Awowale, 2021) for water yield processing allows land managers with different GIS backgrounds or accessibility limitations to utilize this workflow and incorporate results into their own analyses.

Table 4.4.1. Summary of geospatial datasets used in the spatial water yield (WY) workflow and their corresponding in-situ model variable. Spatial resolutions, pixel units, and data sources are also included. (Adapted from Vernon et al., 2023). Input datasets available from Vernon & St. Peter (2022a).

In-Situ WY Model Variable	Geospatial Dataset	Spatial Resolution	Pixel Units	Source
LAI	Pine Basal Area	5m	ft ² /acre	St. Peter et al., 2021
DTW	Depth to Water Table	30m	feet, msl	Arthur et al., 2017
Aridity Index	Potential Evapotranspiration	500m	mm/yr	Running et al., 2021
	Mean Annual Precipitation	4km	mm/yr	PRISM Climate, 2014

Water yield outputs developed during this study included ten raster datasets, each a total of 1.34GB at a 10m spatial resolution across the entire THS1/ARRI project area with water yield units in centimeters per year (Vernon & St. Peter, 2022b). Processing times for the ArcGIS Pro tools and Python scripts were also tracked, completing a full scenario in 10 and 3 minutes, respectively. Baseline water yield was calculated using a pine-specific basal area product, a short-term average regional aridity index and binary depth to groundwater raster. Raster data used in timber thinning scenarios had basal areas

capped to three different values, while those in the climate scenarios utilized two extreme aridity indexes. The timber thinning scenarios estimated water yield with basal area reductions to a maximum of 7, 11, and 18 m² per hectare (30, 50, and 80 ft² per acre), and these thresholds were selected because they represented the low, middle, and high ends of excellent condition southern pine ecosystems in the Southeastern Coastal Plain as defined by US Fish and Wildlife and NatureServe[‡]. The observed minimum and maximum aridity index values measured during the 7 years of meteorological data included in this study served as the inputs for extreme climate scenarios, with minimum aridity representing high precipitation scenarios and maximum aridity for dry scenarios. Climate scenarios were included in this analysis as they offered land managers the potential to include climate change mitigation opportunities into their decision making process. The difference between each scenario output and the baseline water yield created the potential water yield gain (PWYG) datasets that can then be summarized at project-level boundaries to prioritize potential restoration opportunities. For example, Figure 4.4.1 shows how PWYG summarized at multiple levels can direct timber thinning projects to maximize water yield under an intense thinning plan.

This water yield estimate product and workflow, graphically summarized in Figure 4.4.2, directly address the need to direct our restoration efforts in the upland ecosystems of the Gulf of Mexico in ways that also benefit the coastal ecosystems. To accomplish this goal, we needed to quantify the effect of our restoration efforts on the hydrological system and do so in a repeatable manner. The repeatability would be essential to run multiple potential management scenarios and compare outcomes against each other as well as against current conditions and for future restoration monitoring. The high resolution nature of these spatial water yield products also allows for integration into decision support systems for land managers to incorporate relevant datasets and priorities to develop wholistic forest management plans. The results from this effort are further expanded in Section 5.2[‡] of this document and illustrate how this study was translated into opportunities for hydrologic restoration that could help improve water quantity conditions in targeted areas within the Apalachicola Region.

Figure 4.4.1. PWYG in cubic meters per year summarized using the HUC12 (a) and Forest Service management compartment (b) boundaries. PWYG scenario from baseline water yield to intense timber thinning plan with a maximum basal area of 7 m²/ha (30 ft²/acre) shown for both (a) and (b).

Figure 4.4.2. Generalized graphical depiction of water yield workflow with inputs and example outputs. Additional/expanded examples of this study are presented in the Restoration Opportunities and Insights Section 5 of this document.

References

- Acharya, S., Kaplan, D. A., McLaughlin, D. L., & Cohen, M. J. (2022). In-Situ Quantification and Prediction of Water Yield From Southern US Pine Forests. *Water Resources Research*, 58, s2021WR031020.
- Arthur, J.D., Baker, A.E., Cichon, J.R., Wood, A.R., & Rudin, A. (2017). Florida Aquifer Vulnerability Assessment: Contamination Potential Models of Florida's Principal Aquifer Systems: Florida Geological Survey Bulletin No. 67. Retrieved from http://publicfiles.dep.state.fl.us/FGS/FGS_Publications/B/B67.pdf (Accessed on March 10, 2022).
- Awowale, O. (2021). Water Yield Estimation Python Workflow (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8270691>
- Cohen, M. J., McLaughlin, D. L., Kaplan, D. A., & Acharya, S. (2018). Managing Forests for Increased Regional Water Availability. FDACS Contract No. 20834 Final Report. Available online: https://www.fdacs.gov/content/download/76293/file/20834_Del_7.pdf
- Nordman, C., White, R., Wilson, R., Ware, C., Rideout, C., Pyne, M., & Hunter, C. (2016). *Rapid assessment metrics to enhance wildlife habitat and biodiversity within Southern open pine ecosystems*. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and NatureServe. https://www.natureserve.org/sites/default/files/openpinemetrics-finalreport_12may16.pdf
- PRISM Climate Group, Oregon State University. (2014). Data Created February 4, 2014. Available online: <https://prism.oregonstate.edu> (Accessed on March 24, 2022).
- Running, S., Mu, Q., Zhao, M., & Moreno, A. (2021). MODIS/Terra Net Evapotranspiration Gap-Filled Yearly L4 Global 500 m SIN Grid V061 PET_500m, NASA EOSDIS Land Processes DAAC. Available online: <https://doi.org/10.5067/MODIS/MOD16A3GF.061> (Accessed on March 22, 2022).
- St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., & Ibeanusi, V. (2021). Forest Structural Estimates Derived Using a Practical, Open-source Lidar-Processing Workflow. *Remote Sensing*, 13(23), 4763.
- Vernon, J., St. Peter, J., Crandall, C., Awowale, O. E., Medley, P., Drake, J., & Ibeanusi, V. (2023). Spatial Application of Southern U.S. Pine Water Yield for Prioritizing Forest Management Activities. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 12(2), 34. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi12020034>
- Vernon, J. (2022). Water Yield Estimation ArcPro Toolbox (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6949797>
- Vernon, J., & St. Peter, J. (2022a). *Input raster datasets for an application of a fine resolution spatially explicit forest water yield model in Florida's panhandle*. [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8237429>
- Vernon, J., & St. Peter, J. (2022b). *Output raster datasets from an application of a fine resolution spatially explicit forest water yield model in Florida's panhandle*. [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8237445>

4.5 Enhanced Flow Path Mapping

The enhanced flow path mapping initiative was a supplementary project explored by CSER staff and the Chesapeake Conservancy's Conservation Innovation Center (CIC) to examine methods to increase the fidelity and accuracy of hydrologic flow lines within the Apalachicola Region. Enhanced flow path mapping is a technique that has been used by CIC in areas throughout the Northeast to improve hydrologic flow lines and land cover datasets for several restoration projects. However, application to the ARRI project area has not yet been entirely explored, although the need clearly exists. As a test, CSER staff employed the DEM processing workflow established by CIC combined with culvert locations from the hydrologic infrastructure assessment to improve hydrologic flow lines on the Apalachicola Ranger District using ArcMap version 10.7 and the ArcHydro toolset. By adjusting the catchment size required to initiate stream creation during analysis, we were able to increase stream density and

connectivity in the Little Owl Creek HUC12 subwatershed, showing a high resolution view of the movement of water across the landscape. Cross-validation between results of this methodology and the USGS NHDPlus HR (beta) dataset created a more refined stream product. Figure 4.5.1 shows the enhanced flow lines from our analysis and the NHDPlus flow lines for the Little Owl Creek watershed.

The ARRI project area provides a unique landscape for testing EFPM techniques. Elevation gains in the coastal plain, including on the Apalachicola National Forest and Tate’s Hell State Forest, are minimal, only about 100ft above sea level, and roughly 19% of its area is forested wetlands. The presence of these wetlands can increase noise (TIN artifacts) and sinks in digital elevation models, which can be addressed during the creation of a hydro-conditioned DEM, but significant care must be taken to ensure useful information is not lost. This is a very tedious process within a geographic area in which minimal elevation changes create sensitive pit-filling thresholds. Multiple iterations of EFPM may need to be run to determine the most accurate output if this technique is to be used in other project areas around the Gulf Coast.

Figure 4.5.1. Enhanced flow path mapping example for Little Owl Creek subwatershed (HUC12) on the Apalachicola National Forest.

The lack of infrastructure data can also limit the effectiveness or accuracy of EFPM in other areas. For example, the infrastructure assessment conducted on the ARD only surveyed Forest Service maintained roads. Any county or state road through the forest required heads-up digitizing of infrastructure locations using the 1m DEM and World imagery for identification. Because EFPM was limited to subwatersheds that wholly or largely intersected the ARD, heads-up digitizing was a feasible

undertaking on the unsurveyed roads within these selected subwatersheds. However, it is difficult to apply this technique across the entire ARRI project area because reliable culvert information is not available everywhere (i.e., private lands) and heads-up digitizing where data gaps exist requires additional resources.

There are three different types of hydrologically processed DEMs generated during EFPM: hydro-flattened, hydro-conditioned, and hydro-enhanced. Hydro-flattening is already complete with USGS delivered products, mostly in lakes, large rivers, and other bodies of water, where these features are flattened (TIN artifacts removed) to a single elevation using established breaklines as bounding areas (USGS, 2022). Hydro-conditioning includes additional processing of a DEM to ensure water flow is continuous across the entire surface area by filling pits and sinks, while hydro-enforcing takes pre-processing even further by removing barriers that impede flow direction and accumulation in a DEM (Muane, 2007). Typically, these barriers are in the form of roads due to the road surface elevation being displayed on the DEM. This cuts off the continuation of flow during stream and watershed geoprocessing because the tools do not “know” that flow is happening underneath the road surface. Simulating flow under roadways using the locations of culverts on the Apalachicola Ranger District can be done by artificially breaching roadways in the DEM at these sites and altering the elevations so that flow direction and accumulation are not cut off during analysis.

Once a hydro-enforced DEM is produced, the tools available in the ArcHydro toolbar are used to develop multiple raster datasets used in drainage line and watershed processing, like flow direction and flow accumulation. Streamline definition initiates the creation of streamlines by entering a minimum catchment area from the flow accumulation raster. Following the CIC workflow (Saavedra, 2018), a minimum catchment area of 60 acres was used to initiate the flow network within the 30,000 acre Little Owl Creek subwatershed shown in Figure 4.5.1. This process of adjusting the catchment area to derive flow networks can also be used to detect ditch networks across the landscape.

References

- Metcalfe, C. K., Wilkerson, S. D., & Harman, W. A. (2009). Bankfull Regional Curves for North and Northwest Florida Streams. *Journal of the American Water Resources Association*, 45(5), 1260-1272. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-1688.2009.00364.x>
- Saavedra, D. (2018, July). *Enhanced Flow Path Methods Overview*. Conservation Innovation Center. https://www.chesapeakeconservancy.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/CIC_Enhanced_Flowpath_Methods_20180703.pdf
- United States Geological Survey. (2022). *Appendix 2: Hydro-Flattening Reference. Lidar base specification 2022 rev. A*. U.S. Department of the Interior. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from <https://www.usgs.gov/ngp-standards-and-specifications/lidar-base-specification-table-contents>

4.6 Apalachicola Regional Riparian Base Map

In general, riparian areas are vital natural resources that support multiple ecosystem types and functions but can also be very sensitive to environmental changes. That said, riparian area definitions are variable, and have changed over time with the user or author’s perspective. Definitions for riparian areas typically focus on the components and characteristics of the landscape, geographic scale, and legislative mandates for applicable water quality best management practices (Ilhardt, Verry & Palik, 2000). According to Swanson et al. (1982), riparian zones are described as locations where biological, physical, and chemical interactions between aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems occur (Swanson et al., 1982). Gregory et al. (1991) further characterized riparian areas as the interface between terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, which offer distinctive habitats with high species diversity and can be used as dispersal corridors for plants and refugia for wildlife (Gregory et al., 1991). In 2003, The National

Environmental Compliance Handbook provided detailed guidance to Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) officials on compliance with Federal environmental requirements when delivering technical and financial assistance. This manuscript included a more detailed definition of riparian areas as follows: “Riparian areas are ecotones that occur along streams, rivers, lakes, ponds, and wetlands. They are distinctively different from the surrounding lands because of unique soil and vegetative characteristics that are strongly influenced by free or unbound water in the soil. Riparian ecosystems occupy the transitional area between the terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. Typical examples include floodplains, stream banks, and lakeshores. Riparian areas may exist within all land uses, such as cropland, hay land, pastureland, rangeland, and forestland.” (USDA, NRCS, 2003). As is typical with transitional areas between aquatic and terrestrial environments, riparian zones provide a dynamic habitat for significantly different species collections as compared to adjacent non-riparian areas which contributes to, and typically increases the overall regional biodiversity (Sabo et al., 2005). Riparian zones also buffer landscapes against erosion, filter stormwater contaminants from urban and agricultural land use types and improve water availability for human and animal use. In the Apalachicola Region of Florida, there are thousands of miles of streams, rivers, waterbodies, shorelines, and ecotones distributed throughout predominantly intermingled pine forests that create complex hydrologic and terrestrial networks which have profound impacts on all ecosystems within the region, particularly downstream in the Gulf of Mexico. In effect, riparian zones can be considered the life blood of the Apalachicola landscape and should largely be considered as important conservation areas.

Upon initial observation, the Apalachicola Region may appear to be consistently humid and wet, a perception held by local residents familiar with the area. However, despite this seemingly moist environment, the presence and influence of riparian areas are not always immediately apparent. This is particularly significant when considering the impact of the region's geomorphology and karst topography, which play pivotal roles in the Gulf Coastal Lowlands, constituting the majority of the area. Notably, this lowland zone represents the largest geomorphic region in Florida, introducing a layer of complexity to the region's hydrology and ecosystem dynamics. A prime example of this habitat can be found in Tate's Hell State Forest. For an in-depth exploration of the Apalachicola Region's geomorphology, you can refer to the resources provided by the Florida Natural Area Inventory[‡].

To comprehensively understand the extent of this phenomenon, CSER scientists collaborated with USFS researchers to develop an Apalachicola Regional Riparian Area Base Map. This map serves to provide a clearer representation of the riparian zones within the Apalachicola Region. However, it's essential to recognize that this effort, while valuable, does not offer a complete picture of the regional riparian landscape. Several data gaps are known to exist, including the absence of USGS streamgages in the southern portion of the region and the limited resolution of certain landscape-scale geospatial datasets. Furthermore, the Apalachicola landscape features unique elements that may not be adequately captured by readily available hydrologic datasets. These elements include isolated vernal wetlands, sinks, seeps, springs, swallets, and other intricate stream and tributary hydrography.

This study, funded by RESTORE as part of Tate's Hell Strategy 1, delineates riparian ecotones and provides a general land cover composition of the demarcated ecotones using freely available data and a geospatial model built on Python 3 that can be used with ArcGIS Pro. Specifically, this method employs Riparian Buffer Delineation Model (RBDM) v6.1[‡] which is an ArcGIS Desktop\Pro toolbox designed to map variable-width riparian areas utilizing open source geospatial data. This technique is not influenced by variations in landform, but accounts for river/stream watercourse and associated floodplains. Optional data and attributes such as riparian wetlands, riparian soil type, and riparian land cover classes can be used to facilitate detailed riparian area mapping. The model consists of three toolboxes: RBDM, RBDM Utilities, and RBDM Hydro to facilitate data download, preparation, and processing tasks. For more information, please visit <https://www.riparian.solutions>.

The following datasets were used as inputs to develop the regional riparian ecotone base map, and gray highlighted layer names used as inputs in the riparian delineation process.

- *Streams (model Input)*: prepared NHDPlus HR flow lines.
- *Lakes (model Input)*: prepared NHDPlus HR waterbodies.
- *Watersheds (model Input)*: prepared NHDPlus HR HUC-12 watersheds.
- *Wetlands (model Input)*: prepared FWS wetlands dataset for the State of Florida queried on the following: estuarine and marine wetland, freshwater emergent wetland, freshwater forested/shrub wetland, and freshwater pond.
 - <https://apps.nationalmap.gov/downloader/#/>
 - <https://www.fws.gov/wetlands/Data/State-Downloads.html>
- *soil*: prepared gSSURGO raster dataset with all soil attributes.
 - <https://datagateway.nrcs.usda.gov/>
- *Soil_riparian_hydric_floodfreq*: prepared riparian soil dataset using a two parameter query as follows: hydric rating > 90% and flood frequency (very frequent, frequent, or occasional).
- *soil_riparian (model Input)*: prepared riparian soil dataset using state-wide Florida gSSURGO and a four parameter query as follows: hydric rating > 90%, flood frequency (very frequent, frequent, or occasional), drainage class (very poorly drained, poorly drained, or somewhat poorly drained), and hydrologic soil group (C, D, A/D, B/D, or C/D).
- *fl_2016_ccap_10m (model Input)*: prepared C-CAP land cover at 10-meter spatial resolution.
 - <https://coast.noaa.gov/data/digitalcoast/pdf/ccap-class-scheme-derived.pdf>
 - <https://coast.noaa.gov/digitalcoast/data/ccapderived.html>

Prior to running the model, a determination of an appropriate 50-year flood height was required, which was a critical input into to the model. Fifty-year flood height values were calculated from USGS National Water Information System (NWIS) gauges using Annual statistics and Field Measurements data at each gauge up to 2017. Methodology from Mason (2007) was used to calculate 50-year flood height. All the processed gauges are compiled in this dashboard for easy access and faster 50-year flood estimation per HUC-2, HUC-8, and HUC-10 watersheds. Additional research on this methodology is available in Abood (2016), Abood, Maclean, and Mason (2012). Using this method, approximately 2.64 million acres of riparian wetlands were classified with most riparian ecotones occurring in Palustrine Forested Wetlands and Upland Forest landcover classifications (Table 4.6.1). Figure 4.6.1 below is the spatial distribution of riparian zones captured within the Apalachicola Region using this method and the best freely available data. In addition to the spatial distribution of riparian buffers shown in Figure 4.6.1, analyses were also conducted to examine the landcover classes of riparian ecotones using Coastal Change Analysis Program (C-CAP) Derived Land Cover – BETA Product and Classification Scheme.

For all intents and purposes, the Apalachicola Region of Florida is largely covered by what can be classified as riparian zones. This fact presents unique challenges for land managers, particularly as we seek to incorporate more ecological concepts into holistic management methods. While the techniques presented herein are clearly an option for delineating riparian ecotones, there are many other methods in the scientific literature, e.g., Fernández, Álvarez-Cabria, and Peñas, (2012) and Homes and Goebel, (2011). That said, most have a common theme – geospatial analysis. When planning riparian management across the landscape, reliance on digital geospatial data is vital to help delineate functional riparian areas, but this alone is not a substitute for on-site delineation, but rather another tool in the kit.

Table 4.6.1. Apalachicola Regional riparian area landcover classifications with acreages.

Value	Landcover Class	Count	Riparian Acres
0	Background	96,268	2,378.83
2	Impervious Developed	1,578,235	38,998.98
8	Grassland	5,491,346	135,693.91
11	Upland Forest	25,972,179	641,785.53
12	Scrub/Shrub	4,968,292	122,768.98
13	Palustrine Forested Wetland	53,736,293	1,327,850.67
14	Palustrine Scrub/Shrub Wetland	7,029,342	173,698.56
15	Palustrine Emergent Wetland	3,079,796	76,103.30
17	Estuarine Scrub/Shrub Wetland	104,994	2,594.45
18	Estuarine Emergent Wetland	1,569,300	38,778.19
19	Unconsolidated Shore	336,206	8,307.82
20	Bare Land	1,424,973	35,211.80
21	Water	1,273,198	31,461.36
22	Palustrine Aquatic Bed	85,767	2,119.35
23	Estuarine Aquatic Bed	28,313	699.63
Total	15 Classes	106,774,502	2,638,451.36

Figure 4.6.1. Apalachicola Regional riparian base map derived with the Riparian Buffer Delineation Model (RBDM) v6.1[†].

References

- Abood, S. A. (2016). The science of mapping riparian areas utilizing GIS & open source data. In O. S. Pokrovsky (Ed.), *Riparian Zones: Characteristics, Management Practices and Ecological Impacts* (pp. 37-56). Nova Science Publishers, Inc.
- Abood, S. A., Maclean, A. L., & Mason, L. A. (2012). Modeling riparian zones utilizing DEMs and flood height data. *Photogrammetric Engineering & Remote Sensing*, 78, 259-269. <https://doi.org/10.14358/PERS.78.3.259>
- Fernández, D., Barquin, J., Álvarez-Cabria, M., & Peñas, F. J. (2012). Quantifying the performance of automated GIS-based geomorphological approaches for riparian zone delineation using digital elevation models. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.*, 16, 3851–3862. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-16-3851-2012>
- Gregory, S. V., Swanson, F. J., McKee, W. A., & Cummins, K. W. (1991). An Ecosystem Perspective of Riparian Zones. *BioScience*, 41(8), 540–551. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1311607>
- Holmes, K. L., & Goebel, P. C. (2011). A Functional Approach to Riparian Area Delineation Using Geospatial Methods. *Journal of Forestry*, 109, 233-241. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jof/109.4.233>
- Ilhardt, B. L., Verry, E. S., & Palik, B. J. (2000). Defining riparian areas. In E. S. Verry, J. W. Hornbeck, & C. A. Dolloff (Eds.), *Riparian management in forests of the continental eastern United States* (pp. 23–42). Lewis Publishers.
- Mason, L. A. (2007). GIS modeling of riparian zones utilizing digital elevation models and flood height data. [Master of Science thesis, Michigan Technological University]. https://www.riparian.solutions/files/ugd/d5da6c_8edb498f7b244803b3f132d98ee7d32a.pdf
- Natural Resources Conservation Service (NRCS). (2003). National Environmental Compliance Handbook. (All U.S. Government Documents Utah Regional Depository Paper 163). United States Department of Agriculture. <https://digitalcommons.usu.edu/govdocs/163>
- Sabo, J., Sponseller, R., Dixon, M., Gade, K., Harms, T., Heffernan, J., Jani, A., Katz, G., Soykan, C., Watts, J., & Welter, J. (2005). Riparian zones increase regional species richness by harboring different, not more, species. *Ecology*, 86, 56-62. <https://doi.org/10.1890/04-0668>
- Swanson, F. J., Gregory, S. V., Sedell, J. R., & Campbell, A. G. (1982). Land-water interactions: the riparian zone. In R. Edmonds (Ed.), *Analysis of coniferous forest ecosystems in the western United States* (pp. 267-291). Hutchinson Ross Publishing Co. <https://andrewsforest.oregonstate.edu/publications/1343>

5 Restoration Opportunities and Insights

5.1 Highlights, Context and Considerations

In 2017, the U.S. Forest Service (USFS), National Forests in Florida (NFF), and the Florida Forest Service (FFS) secured RESTORE Act funding for the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 (THS1) Project, a five-year endeavor. The project aimed to advance conservation, ecosystem restoration, and hydrologic improvement planning, and implementation across Tate’s Hell State Forest (THSF), the Apalachicola National Forest (ANF), and the Apalachicola Region in Florida. The THS1 Project has since achieved several overarching goals, including restoring surface water drainage patterns, improving water quality and quantity, enhancing wetland function, identifying restoration targets, and devising plans for future ecosystem and hydrologic restoration activities. Throughout, this approach emphasized the creation and use of spatial tools and analytics. It also involved numerous agencies, partners, contributors, and stakeholders across various projects sometimes supported by multiple funding sources. Moreover, the project was temporarily disrupted by the impacts of Hurricane Michael in 2018 just as the project was getting underway. Interestingly, this setback led to the discovery of synergies with prior workflows from different projects that have now been codified and reused multiple times in other elements of this study.

Despite the THS1 Project's well-defined early goals, the implementation process proved intricate, non-linear, and even chaotic at times. Amid these objectives, the THS1 Project Team aimed to leverage both the tangible and intangible advantages of spatial analytics within the dynamic interplay of natural and human-created systems. Notably, such analyses frequently revealed unexpected connections and trends, sporadically leading to serendipitous revelations, as was the case here. By integrating spatial data with advanced technology and applying this to the complex relationship among numerous factors in the Apalachicola Region, we unveiled hidden correlations, repetitions, and self-similarities within the longleaf pine habitat's distribution and behaviors. Although not revolutionary, our exploration has unearthed intersections and synergies previously unseen to us, yielding remarkable preliminary outcomes that will be further developed in ARRI and beyond. This underscores that amidst apparent chaos, intricate systems hold hidden order and self-organization. When armed with the appropriate tools and an open-minded approach, it's possible to divulge these concealed yet valuable elements. Some of these surprise elements are already being developed into useful tools to help characterize the regional landscape and will likely be deployed in ARRI Strategies 2&3.

Another crucial aspect is the holistic nature of our evaluation of potential restoration sites. If data were available for a location, they were often included or modeled. This approach highlighted the importance of considering various factors in tandem. These restoration target areas typically showed numerous potential outcomes, some nested or tiered at different scales. The outcomes encompassed water, vegetation, infrastructure, wildlife, recreation, and interrelated socioeconomics. Essentially, no facet within the THS1 study area operated in isolation; instead, each interconnected with other pivotal features that could influence the outcomes or be addressed concurrently, thus increasing potential returns. The bottom line is a multifactorial analysis that can reveal diverse and significant results. This process shouldn't be disregarded in favor of potentially simpler non-spatial solutions.

For the remainder of this section, we highlight specific restoration opportunities in each subsection resulting from years of planning, spatial analysis, and collaborative efforts. While not an exhaustive list of identified prospects, this section presents key elements that guided our focus towards precise locations offering:

- Salient prospects for hydrologic and ecosystem restoration in multiple habitat types.
- Strategies for both direct and indirect enhancement of water quality and quantity.
- Opportunities to optimize land management practices (e.g., fire, timber stand improvements, timber thinning, groundcover restoration, etc.) to yield enhanced terrestrial and hydrologic ecosystems.
- Fresh insights into partner-managed lands across the region and the downstream interconnectedness of potential sites.
- Action plans for implementing multi-factorial restoration projects within ARRI 2&3.
- Novel restoration prospects and insights pertaining to coastal zones in the Big Bend and Apalachicola Regions, e.g., coastal mangrove habitat characterizations and blue carbon stock assessments, or enhancing forest resilience through climate-responsive management strategies that impact vital and often unnoticed ephemeral wetland hydrology.

Fully depicting these extensive opportunities would demand more space and time than presently available. This is primarily due to the region's ever-changing landscape and the resources needed for this endeavor. The reality is that the scope is vast and evolving, instant changes (e.g., hurricanes, wildfires, floods) necessitate coordinated short-, medium-, and long-term planning and budgeting efforts to bring these plans to fruition. These options also emerge from the interconnected rationales expounded upon across this document, each necessitating distinct planning and execution strategies. Indeed, the interdependence of these elements not only creates opportunities for synergy

and collaboration but also introduces challenges when land managers fail to consider these areas and their actions within the broader context of the surrounding landscape. An abbreviated highlight of priority restoration examples with short descriptions of activities (in no specific order) follows below. These, and other restoration prospects uncovered across the Apalachicola Region during the THS1 planning initiative are further detailed in this section and others.

- **Bluff of St. Teresa** - Water quality and quantity impacts following habitat restoration activities (dense sand pine removal) on a recently acquired 17,185-acre land tract in Franklin, County, FL between Ochlockonee Bay, and Alligator Harbor, FL are a high priority concern. This property holds a strategic advantage due to its location, offering numerous opportunities for valuable returns on restoration projects and fostering collaborative initiatives across different organizations – federal, state, and private. The downstream effect could be substantial.
- **Telogia Creek Watershed** - In the Telogia Creek Watershed (spanning Gadsden and Liberty Counties), comprehensive activities are badly needed, including detailed forest structural assessments, precise watershed hydrologic modeling, and thorough water quality evaluations, particularly in zones where water quality standards are not being met. The potential for collaboration across various state and federal agencies offers a wealth of opportunities to execute impactful projects. These projects involve characterizing habitat conditions in key watershed areas, notably riparian zones, assessing pertinent water quality parameters, and devising strategies to enhance the health and resilience of the entire Telogia Creek Watershed. This watershed's strategic location further emphasizes its significance, hosting numerous threatened and endangered species and ecosystem services.
- **Geographically Isolated Wetlands** - Ephemeral ponds are a key element to enhance forest resilience through climate-responsive management strategies. Ephemeral wetland hydrology ultimately promotes long-term forest vitality for numerous reasons. By characterizing and restoring resiliency and function of GIWs as means to improve freshwater availability to coastal ecosystems will have manifold and cascading effects on not only water, but wildlife habitat and other ecosystem services. It also helps fill knowledge gaps about forested wetlands' role in managing hydrology amid fluctuating water availability and climate shifts.
- **Mangroves in the Big Bend Region of the Florida Gulf Coast** - Coastal mangrove habitat vegetation structural assessments and blue carbon characterizations using ultra-resolution drone-borne lidar and imagery will yield high-valued returns for future decades. By describing northwardly expanding coastal mangrove habitat conditions (Cedar Key to Apalachicola, FL) and conducting vegetation structural assessments will help quantify valuable blue carbon stocks and better understand, quantify, and protect blue carbon resources as well as harness the potential of these ecosystems for climate change mitigation, coastal protection, and resiliency.

To further expound upon additional restoration opportunities, Figure 5.1.1 highlights some, but not all near-term restoration targets and their probable boundaries within the THS1 Project area, including recently acquired conservation lands of strategic importance. Comprehensive details about these projects, along with sub-projects, are accessible throughout various subsections of this section and other areas of this document, peer-reviewed publications, downloadable datasets, and application code. It is important to note that many of these opportunities do not stop at traditional administrative or operational boundaries and should always be considered within the context of the broader landscape or “hydroscape”. Furthermore, Table 5.1.1 offers a partial roster of potential restoration targets, outlining pertinent Hydrologic Unit Codes (HUCs) and Apalachicola National Forest management compartment boundaries. This table also speaks to the highly interconnected nature, and potential advantages or pitfalls related to managing large landscapes from the perspective of traditionally established boundaries that do not consider the comprehensive terrestrial and hydrologic environment.

For example, if required activities are conducted in a few management compartments on a ranger district abutting a strategic water resource, the probability of all land managers knowing their potential impacts to a connected water body is unlikely, but these data simply cannot be ignored. This is one of the redeeming elements of raster-based cross-boundary spatial analyses which are generally limited only by data availability and does not need to stop at traditional demarcations.

With all of the competing objectives in mind, conducting large-scale land management activities can have significant positive and/or negative downstream repercussions on water resources. These consequences can stem from alterations to the natural landscape, changes in hydrological patterns, and modifications in the way water moves through the environment. That said, here are some potential downstream impacts which can be regulated when we operate with the best available information:

- **Water Quality Degradation** - Land management activities such as deforestation, and urban development can lead to increased runoff of pollutants like sediment, fertilizers, pesticides, and other chemicals into water bodies. This can degrade water quality, making it less suitable for human consumption, aquatic life, and recreational use.
- **Increased Flooding** - Poor land management practices, such as removing natural vegetation or altering natural drainage systems, can disrupt the natural flow of water and increase the likelihood of flooding downstream. Without natural buffers, rainfall and stormwater runoff can quickly accumulate and overwhelm waterways.
- **Altered Streamflow** - Large-scale land surface alteration can change the way water moves through landscapes. Removal of vegetation can reduce water absorption, leading to faster runoff and increased erosion. This can result in irregular streamflow patterns, with more intense, rapid flows during rainfall events and reduced flows during drier periods.
- **Habitat Destruction** - Alterations to the landscape can destroy or disrupt aquatic and riparian habitats that many species rely on for shelter, breeding, and feeding. This can lead to declines in biodiversity and negatively impact fisheries and other aquatic ecosystems downstream.
- **Sedimentation** - Erosion caused by land surface alterations can increase sediment loads in rivers and streams. Excess sediment can clog waterways, reducing their capacity to carry water and increasing the need for costly maintenance efforts to keep channels clear.
- **Changes in Groundwater Levels** - Some land management practices can alter the balance between surface water and groundwater. Excessive groundwater pumping for irrigation or construction purposes can lower groundwater levels, potentially reducing base flow to streams and affecting ecosystems downstream.
- **Temperature Changes** - Alterations to land cover, such as deforestation or urbanization, can influence microclimates and lead to temperature changes in water bodies. Increased temperatures can stress aquatic organisms and lead to unfavorable conditions for cold-water species.
- **Nutrient Imbalances** - Agricultural activities which involve the use of fertilizers, can lead to nutrient runoff into water bodies, especially if riparian buffers and streamside management zones (SMZs) are not in place. Excessive nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus can cause eutrophication, leading to algal blooms, oxygen depletion, and overall ecological imbalances downstream. Additionally, construction projects or landscape alterations of any kind have the potential to liberate soil-bound nutrients that can be translocated to intermittent and perennial waterbodies creating downstream problems from the overabundance of nutrients.
- **Drought and Water Scarcity** - Poor land management practices can exacerbate the impacts of drought. Removal of vegetation can reduce soil moisture retention, exacerbating water scarcity issues during dry periods.

- **Social and Economic Impact** - Downstream communities that rely on water resources for drinking, agriculture, industry, fisheries, and recreation can face economic and social challenges due to degraded water quality, increased flooding, and reduced availability of water. This is absolutely the case in the Apalachicola Region of Florida that has seen dramatic declines in oyster fisheries directly and indirectly related to freshwater availability (Florida Sea Grant, 2020).

To mitigate these downstream effects, integrated and sustainable land management approaches are crucial. These approaches should consider the complex interactions between land and water systems, involve stakeholders from various sectors, and prioritize strategies that maintain ecosystem services and minimize negative impacts on water resources. Geospatially-centric land management methods enable informed cross-boundary activities that consider projects within the context of the landscape. Ultimately, “informed” restoration projects will help improve water quality and quantity in critical coastal habitats and help identify and improve valuable ecosystem services that will in turn help benefit the economy of the Apalachicola Region and the Gulf of Mexico. Additionally, this effort can provide hands-on and highly focused educational opportunities with broad ranging applications for students at Florida A&M University, the University of Florida, and other academic institutions across the State of Florida as well as agency personnel who seek a greater understanding of spatial ecology in the context conservation and restoration.

Figure 5.1.1. Priority Landscape scale restoration opportunities identified in Tate’s Strategy 1 for the Apalachicola Region. HUC boundaries often cross federal, state, and private lands, but actual restoration targets within each HUC varies by activity type and ownership.

Table 5.1.1. Partial list of priority HUC12s (Hydrologic Unit Codes) and corresponding Apalachicola National Forest management compartment boundaries (where applicable). “HUC Ownership” column = all (F)ederal, (S)tate, (M)unicipal and/or (P)rivate landowners within the HUC from most to least owned acreage. “General Location” column = general location of actual restoration target although this may not be the majority of acreage or land ownership within the HUC. “ANF Mgmt. Compartment” column = all compartments intersecting the corresponding HUC12 watersheds. ANF = Apalachicola National Forest, ARD = Apalachicola Ranger District, WRD = Wakulla Ranger District, BoST = Bluffs of St. Teresa, BPSP = Bald Point State Park, TC = Telogia Creek, THSF = Tate’s Hell State Forest.

HUC 12	HUC Name	HUC Ownership	General Location	Potential Target or Sub-location	ANF Mgmt. Compartment
031200010601	Lake Bradford	F, M, S, P	ANF	Dragstrip Site WRD	201, 202, 203, 217, 219
031300110603	Florida River	F, S, P	ANF	ARD	25, 26, 27 69, 72
031300110604	Kennedy Creek	F, S, P	ANF	ARD	26, 28, 29, 30, 31, 46, 67, 69, 70, 71, 74, 75, 76, 94, 95, 96, 97, 98
031300110801	Little Owl Creek	F, S, P, M	ANF	Little Owl Creek Compartment 68 ARD	46, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 76, 77, 78, 79, 93, 98, 99, 100, 101, 102, 103
031200031203	Brandy Creek- Crooked River	F, S, P, M	THSF	BoST	N/A
031200031204	Ochlockonee Bay	F, S, P, M	BPSP	BoST	353, 357
031300140401	Alligator Harbor- Frontal Gulf of Mexico	F, S, P, M	BPSP	BoST	N/A
031200030701	Devil's Branch- Telogia Creek	S, P, M	TC	Florida Forever Acquisition	N/A
031200030702	Panther Creek- Telogia Creek	S, P	TC	Florida Forever Acquisition	N/A
031200030704	Stokes Branch	F, S, P	TC	ANF	1, 2, 3
031200030705	Telogia Creek	F, S, P	TC	ANF	1, 2, 3, 8, 9, 10, 11, 18, 19
031300130404	Cat Creek	S	THSF	Cat Creek	N/A

References

Florida Sea Grant. (2020). *Apalachicola Bay Oyster Situation Report* (TP-200). National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from http://www.oyster-restoration.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/05/tp200_apalachicola_oyster_situation_report.pdf

5.2 Potential Water Yield Gain from Land Management Activities

Published results of the spatial application of southern pine water yield outlined in Section 4.4 (Vernon et al., 2023) illustrate potential hydrologic restoration opportunities throughout the Apalachicola Region identified by a novel workflow that incorporates field-verified, peer-reviewed (Acharya et al., 2022) water models for southern pine forests. This section elaborates on how these spatial and water models can be leveraged to gain insight into explicit restoration goals considered within the context of project or landscape-level forest management activities. Specifically, Figure 5.1.1 exemplifies how numerous watersheds can be identified as prime candidates for dense pine thinning operations to ideally redirect water to surface locations that would otherwise be lost to the atmosphere.

Figure 5.2.1 details a singular multi-factorial instance of a finely detailed operational view showcasing priority stand-level ecosystem restoration options within a management compartment on the Apalachicola Ranger District of the ANF. This example revolves around thinning densely populated offsite slash pine in the Little Owl Creek (HUC12) watershed near Sumatra, Florida. The comprehensive illustration integrates infrastructure, water, and vegetation resource management, and includes projections of water yield changes resulting from proposed stand-level treatments. Moreover, this example supplies comprehensive contextual insights, encompassing wetlands, wildlife, native vegetation, high-resolution water flow paths, and established hydrologic infrastructure in various states of repair. These related perspectives prove invaluable for decision-making, extending beyond timber management to include wildlife and native plant habitats, engineered structures and water resource management concerns.

Indeed, the Little Owl Creek HUC12 watershed consistently displays prominently in every PWYG scenario and holds a significant position across all PWYG scenarios for individual management compartments on the ANF. Water yield enhancements resulting from timber thinning strategies within compartment 68 exhibit a range from approximately 290,000 m³ to nearly 710,000 m³ of water not lost to the atmosphere over a year. Clearly, this variance hinges upon the degree of thinning executed in the 29% of the area exceeding the dense pine tree threshold, but nonetheless it's a prime candidate for a beneficial multifactorial restoration operation including replacing aging hydrologic infrastructure at the southern end of the compartment that will likely bear the brunt of increased waterflows returned to hydrologic system. By integrating geospatial information from other agency initiatives, we also showcased elements such as roads, road infrastructure, augmented hydrologic flow lines, QL1 USGS 3DEP lidar derivatives, and documented locations of federally listed threatened and endangered species. All this information can be consumed simultaneously as an effective instrument for land managers to devise an all-encompassing restoration blueprint. This comprehensive strategy optimizes resources to simultaneously address interconnected and co-located challenges within a compartment by considering downstream effects. Of note, next generation drone laser scanning (DLS) data are currently being collected over the same area which will reveal even higher resolution results to water yield estimates and vegetation structural metrics.

A significant aspect to highlight here is that the pine water yield model applied in this study was precisely tailored to southern pine ecosystems in Florida, yet its relevance likely extends to other pine-dominated ecosystems across the southeastern coastal plain. A related study by Acharya et al. (2022) indicated that water yield variations among dominant pine species were not statistically significant at the stand level. This implies that both the model and tools developed in this study could be effectively employed for water yield predictions in other regions where southern pine trees predominate. Expanding the adoption of this workflow to other southern forests would primarily involve creating a pine basal area raster, similar to the one developed here. However, not everyone has the ability to generate this type of raster data for a variety of reasons. From our prior results, we were able to

demonstrate that such raster datasets can be generated with practical precision, using the U.S. Forest Service's Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) data that are available nationwide (Section 8.3). Additional data sources like local lidar data, aerial imagery, or satellite imagery at various spatial resolutions can further facilitate this approach and its broader applications.

Figure 5.2.1 Project scale (high-resolution) restoration opportunities identified for Management Compartment #68 on the Apalachicola NF. Total compartment hectares, dense pine BA hectares (≥ 18 m^2/ha), and PWYG in m^3/yr are shown for three timber-reduction scenarios—down to 7, 11, and 18 m^2/ha (legend). Also included are 2017 infrastructure condition survey data, enhanced hydrologic flow lines, and general locations of federally listed threatened and endangered species (from Vernon et al., 2023). Note, hydrologic flow lines were developed using point clouds and derivative elevation models.

All told, there are more than 103,000 acres of dense pine stands over 80 BA within selected conservation lands in the THS1/ARRI landscape (Table 5.2.1). All of these areas have been modeled in this effort and the results have been shared with partners as a guide for silvicultural activities planned for ARRI Strategies 2&3. More detailed potential water quantity benefits and other focal areas are explored below.

Table 5.2.1 Summary of dense pine (>80 BA) on selected public and conservation lands in ARRI.

Managed Area	Acres of Dense Pine (>80 BA)
Apalachee Wildlife Management Area	1,427
Apalachicola National Forest	63,155
Apalachicola River Wildlife and Environmental Area	1,643
Bluffs of St. Teresa (Tate's Hell SF, Florida Forest Service)	3,166
Bluffs of St. Teresa (Bald Point SP, Florida DEP)	1,323
Flint Rock Tract	370
Tate's Hell State Forest	32,198
Torreya State Park	837

References

- Acharya, S., Kaplan, D. A., McLaughlin, D. L., & Cohen, M. J. (2022). In-Situ Quantification and Prediction of Water Yield from Southern US Pine Forests. *Water Resources Research*, 58, s2021WR031020.
- Vernon, J., St. Peter, J., Crandall, C., Awowale, O. E., Medley, P., Drake, J., & Ibeanusi, V. (2023). Spatial Application of Southern U.S. Pine Water Yield for Prioritizing Forest Management Activities. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 12(2), 34. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi12020034>

5.3 Apalachicola National Forest Road 128 and Other Hydrologic Infrastructure

During the initial 2017/18 field season and subsequent winter 2021 THS1 hydrologic infrastructure and AOP assessment on the Apalachicola National Forest (ANF), several features were identified by USFS and CATT Team personnel as potential candidates for restoration. These features exhibited significant hydrologic flow barriers, erosion occurrences, obstructions to aquatic organism passage (AOP), and often an aesthetically displeasing appearance. One standout restoration opportunity identified during the THS1 hydrologic restoration planning phase was National Forest System Road number 128 (NFR 128) in the northeastern corner of the Apalachicola Ranger District.

NFR 128 is a 5.57-mile-long, single-lane road categorized as maintenance level 3 (improved native material, suitable for passenger cars) approximately 13.5 miles southeast of Bristol, FL. Two sites of concern were readily acknowledged as potential restoration targets at the intersections of NFR 128 and two first-order perennial streams, Big Branch, and an unnamed tributary (Figure 5.3.1), both fully located within the Telogia Creek HUC12 watershed (HUC ID: 031200030705), were also included. The combined drainage area for these two stream segments is approximately 620 acres, with nearly 294 acres classified as vital riparian habitat.

Each of these sites had two corrugated metal circular pipes in varying condition. At the northern site, the pipes were approximately 60 ft long, posing a barrier to aquatic organism passage. Additionally, both sites had culverts set at elevations higher than the streambed, with one of the culverts perched at the outlet (Figure 5.3.2). This configuration not only blocked flow and organism passage but also contributed to significant erosion events. These factors undoubtedly led to some habitat fragmentation and a loss of aquatic connectivity during low flow conditions resulted in chronic or episodic

sedimentation that flowed into nearby Telogia Creek, a major tributary of the Ochlockonee River. The Ochlockonee watershed is also of noteworthy concern and is further detailed in Section 5.6.

Based on this information and input from ANF engineering staff, the northern portion of NFR 128 was identified as a clear priority and would serve as a template for future infrastructure improvement projects with similar objectives to improve ecological and hydrologic conditions in strategic areas across the forest. Once identified, USFS personnel took immediate action and formulated a statement of work that was divided into two phases: field construction and stream channel remediation. This encompassed pre-construction planning and coordination, construction implementation, stream channel remediation, and a comprehensive assessment of inlet/outlet transition zones. The overarching objective of the project was to enhance the stream-road crossings and promote the formation of stable streambeds within the culverts, allowing unimpeded water flow, movement of bedload, and wildlife passage. Secondary goals included reducing sediment delivery into the streams, maximizing infrastructure longevity, and optimizing public safety.

Through collaborative interactions, we were able to leverage funds from the THS1 Project and additional funding received by the CATT Team from USFS Region 8 to complete surveys on all remaining cross-drains on the Apalachicola Ranger District, and to conduct Aquatic Organism Passage (AOP) cross-drain surveys during winter 2021. USFS staff expanded partner relationships to include the Southeastern Aquatic Resources Partnership (SARP), and this collaboration along with the RESTORE-funded surveys enabled us to secure in-kind support and an additional \$100,000 to implement this priority hydrologic improvement project.

ANF Engineering staff obtained approval from the Army Corps of Engineers for a silviculture exemption within the ACOE permitting process. Fortunately, the roadway had already undergone NEPA analysis as part of a recent timber sale project, and construction was confined to the existing road prism. The engineering design was completed by USFS staff, while ANF Engineering established the elevations prior to the commencement of the project. Because of these meaningful partnership and support from our partners, we were able not only to execute this project, but also to identify similar targets on NFR 128. Overall, the results of the NFR 128 surface flow and aquatic organism passage improvement project exceeded our expectations, both in terms of the achieved results (Figure 5.3.2) and the generous support, both internally and externally, through match funding and direct contributions. This project also served as an ideal pilot project for hydrologic improvements that are planned in ARRI Strategies 2&3.

Figure 5.3.1 USFS/RESTORE National Forest Road (NFR) 128 hydrologic and ecosystem restoration site project site on the northeastern corner of the Apalachicola Ranger District near Telogia Creek.

Figure 5.3.2. Pre- and post-hydrologic infrastructure restoration conditions located at the intersections of NFR 128 and two first-order perennial streams, Big Branch, and an unnamed tributary (Images on left by USFS Center for Aquatic Technology Transfer, 2017/2018; image on lower right by J. Vernon, FAMU, 2020; and image on upper right by J. Drake, USFS, 2022).

Since the identification and completion of the hydrologic improvements shown in Figure 5.3.2, multiple restoration targets for hydrologic infrastructure have been identified by ANF I and CSER staff. These targets are located not only in the vicinity of the original sites but also at critical locations throughout the national forest. This comprehensive assessment was made possible by the hydrologic infrastructure database created by CSER at the beginning of the THS1 Project, utilizing data collected during the 2017/2018 surveys and subsequent CATT Team efforts in 2021. The information provided valuable insights into the condition of roads and infrastructure, enabling timely and informed assessments of potential priority restoration sites.

Based on compiled spatial survey data and the expertise of ANF Engineering staff, it was found that culverts along 9 forest roads, including NFR 109, 112-S, 112-Y, 113, 118, 141, 141-A, 173 and 174, exhibit varying degrees of deterioration and represent high-priority restoration targets. Field surveys also identified numerous erosion events occurring in conjunction with these restoration sites, providing contextual information on the chronic and episodic sedimentation flowing into nearby rivers, streams, wetlands, and other water bodies. While many of these sites are currently queued for restoration, the majority awaits funding. Once funding is secured, the plan is to remove and replace approximately 84 culverts with new culverts or low water crossings (LWCs), depending on size and location (for low volume roads). Approximately 58% of the identified deteriorating culverts are scheduled to be replaced with LWCs, which not only provides a more visually pleasing option but also allows for aquatic organism passage. It is worth noting that many of these culverts were significantly impacted by Hurricane Michael in 2018, further highlighting the urgency to repair or replace the damaged infrastructure.

The locations of potential culvert restoration targets are displayed in Figure 5.3.3. Initial funding estimates for completing this task were approximately \$700,000. However, these estimates were made before the recent (post-2020) core inflationary pressures experienced in the U.S. Nevertheless, CSER and its partners are committed to exploring creative avenues to leverage funding and expertise in

addressing the systemic regional issues associated with decaying hydrologic infrastructure and the significant impact on regional water quality and quantity.

Figure 5.3.3. Location of waterbody and drain culverts on national forest system roads that have been identified as potential restoration targets on the Apalachicola Ranger District of the Apalachicola National Forest. Map by D. Ditchler, USFS, Apalachicola National Forest.

5.4 Apalachicola NF Dragstrip Gully Erosion Site

The Surface Water Improvement and Management (SWIM) plans for the Apalachicola River (NFWFMD, 2017a) and the Ochlockonee River and Bay (NFWFMD, 2017b) have both identified soil erosion as nonpoint sources of pollution, which are concerns for water quality as well as contributors of sedimentation into receiving waters and wetlands. In the Apalachicola Region, as with many other areas along the Gulf Coast, highly erodible soils (e.g., Chipley, Bonifay, Lakeland) are susceptible to gully erosion events where large volumes of soil can rapidly erode into nearby wetlands and streams.

For this portion of the THS1 Project, CSER Team members investigated the utility of lidar for characterizing gully erosion events, as well as for monitoring soil erosion through time on a pilot site in southeastern Leon County, FL on the northeastern boundary of the Apalachicola NF (Figure 5.4.1). This private parcel is located directly north of the gully erosion site and contains a 0.5-mile long paved and abandoned drag strip, which slopes downward (0.5%, 1.5 degrees) in a southerly direction and terminates within a few feet of the ANF boundary. This impervious surface can rapidly divert large quantities of runoff towards the highly erodible soils just over the ANF boundary. This has no doubt been a significant contributing factor to gully erosion in this location in recent years (Figure 5.4.2).

Figure 5.4.1. Pilot site for analysis of soil erosion using airborne lidar monitoring techniques on the northeastern boundary of the Apalachicola NF (ANF). The green line shows the boundary of the ANF with private lands, including a parcel that contains a long (half mile) paved drag strip that slopes downward towards the forest boundary.

Figure 5.4.2. Photos from eastern side of pilot gully erosion site (Images by H. Shenk, USFS, 2011).

CSER staff used airborne laser scanning (ALS) data collected for Leon County in 2002, 2007, 2009 and 2018 as well as 2020 lidar data collected through the USGS 3DEP program. To enable comparisons through time, new 10 ft resolution DEMs were created from lidar points classified as ground points using the LAS Dataset to Raster tool in ArcGIS Pro (Esri Inc., 2023) with a binning interpolation type, inverse distance weighted (IDW) cell assignment and a natural neighbor void fill method. Elevation change products were created for each time period (e.g., 2002 to 2007) however only the changes from 2002 to 2020 are presented (Figure 5.4.3).

To estimate the volume of soil that was eroded, the vertical change was simply multiplied by the cell size (100 ft²). From 2002 to 2020 we estimate that over 378,000 cubic feet has eroded from this 2.3 acre site, for a total of almost 17,000 tons. As can be clearly seen in the bottom panel of Figure 5.4.3, the distribution of this soil erosion is not uniform. Areas to the west had 3 to 5 ft of soil loss whereas areas in the SE had as much as 16 feet of soil loss. This corresponds very well with conditions observed in the field (e.g., Figure 5.4.2).

This approach shows great potential for rapid characterization of existing gully erosion sites and could help with planning efforts with private land owners, NRCS and other stakeholders as well as engineering and design efforts. It also provides a reliable and repeatable way to monitor changes through time (e.g., after restoration activities have occurred). This methodology has been used with ALS and drone laser scanning (DLS) data and the techniques have already been transferred to other RESTORE Natural Resource Damage Assessment (NRDA) restoration projects in Florida.

CSER staff also worked closely with the National Forests in Florida hydrologist, as well as ANF Engineering and Silvicultural staff to develop a restoration plan for this erosion area (see text below and Table 5.4.1.). This water quality improvement project would consist of activities including construction of earthen slope improvements, and bank repairs with installation of preventative erosion measures and establishment of native vegetation.

Repair and stabilization of the eroded area, along with blocking illegal UTV/ATV traffic with trees removed during clearing, would restore the forest to a healthier condition, drastically reducing invasive plant potential, and helping reestablish forest hydrology in addition to mitigating erosion and sedimentation into the nearby wetlands. Covering the clearing area with woody material has also proven effective at re-inoculating fragile soils with macro- and micro-biotic life to support rapid native vegetation regrowth, and redirecting forest hydrology towards the aquifer rather than the high evapotranspiration loss of a compacted soil. In Florida, these restoration treatments have been highly effective due to the area being instantly impassable and restored to native vegetation after the first rainy season.

This erosion repair project will require the estimated timeline and resources to complete:

Fall 2023

- PRISM UAS flight for pre-work lidar and imagery.
- NEPA approval and archaeological clearance for the project.

Spring 2024

- Complete clearing of site.
- Re-contour the site.
- Install coir mats with millet seed.
- Sow native seed over coir mats using farm tractor/grasslander.
- Scatter uprooted trees from clearing operation to prevent future vehicle access.
- PRISM (Section 8.8) monitoring data collection during operations when possible.

Winter 2024-25

- Hand Plant longleaf seedlings
- Overseed with ryegrass if needed.

Spring 2025

- Field monitor for grass establishment, overseed with millet if needed.
- Additional PRISM monitoring.

Spring 2026

- Hand tool release longleaf seedlings if needed.
- Additional PRISM monitoring.

Assumed Construction Guide for Planning and Estimate as follows:

- Clear trees within the project area by pushing over in-order-to retain root-ball. Trees within the clearing limits will be staged within project area. These clearing slash trees will be spread along the contours after recontouring is completed. Reestablish contour by transitioning from solid ground to the erosion areas when recontouring. Clearing limits should allow for a transition with no more than a 4:1 slope. Clearing limits are estimated at 20 acres.
- Establishing groundcover with coir mat and seed with annual and native seed mix, along with longleaf pine containerized seedlings hand planted at 440 containerized seedlings per acre (10'x10' spacing on average).
- Lay clearing slash trees following the contours and allowing for the clearing to be blocked to illegal ATV/UTV traffic. Trees should be pushed over during clearing to allow for entire stumps and root balls to be utilized when blocking the clearing area.

Table 5.4.1. Estimated costs for hydrologic restoration work at drag strip erosion site.

Description	Cost
Clearing and relaying trees – 20 acre clearing limit est. for the 4:1 slope @ \$1,200/Ac.	\$ 24,000
Excavation - in place excavation/repair of eroded area with contours @ 1,800/Ac.	\$ 36,000
Coir rolls – control sediment and establish groundcover. (800 rolls; estimated cost includes coil rolls, freight, labor, and contingencies) @360/roll.	\$ 288,000
Soil and erosion sediment control - Establish groundcover on coir mat using seed with annual and native seed mix. (35 lb/acc. seed – 700 lbs. total; cost includes seed, labor, and contingencies.) @ \$34/lb.	\$ 23,800
Furnish and plant longleaf containerized seedlings – soil and sediment control, and native trees establishment (plant 20 ac. at 440 seedlings/ac. = 8,800 seedlings costs include trees, labor, and contingencies) @ 0.50/seedling.	\$ 4,400
Mobilization @ 5%	\$ 18,810
Total Cost of Project	\$ 395,010

Figure 5.4.3. Soil erosion estimated from lidar monitoring from 2002 to 2020.

In summary, the primary objective of this initiative was to accurately assess the drag strip gully erosion site and neighboring landforms in their historical and current states. Furthermore, it highlights the practicality of employing such technology in ongoing and future erosion restoration initiatives, as already initiated in a similar Natural Resource Conservation Service RESTORE Project in the western Panhandle of Florida (Santa Rosa County). The utilization of advanced data and associated analyses offers timely and actionable information, facilitating strategic decision-making concerning ongoing or planned hydrologic and ecosystem restoration activities. The overarching goal is to enhance hydrologic conditions by reducing nutrient and sediment runoff at the targeted locations. Together with other potential hydrologic infrastructure restoration work along FR-128 (Section 5.3), these restoration initiatives will have a direct impact on the water quality within the greater Ochlockonee HUC 6 watershed and the Gulf of Mexico (Figure 5.4.4), complimenting other ongoing projects within this and other hydrologic units.

Figure 5.4.4. Locations of potential water quality improvement projects within the Ochlockonee watershed (HUC6: 031200). The FR-128 site is located within the Lower Ochlockonee HUC8 (03120003) near Telogia Creek. The Dragstrip erosion site is in the Apalachee Bay-St. Marks HUC8 (03120001) near Bradford Brook and Lake Talquin.

References

- Esri Inc. (2023). ArcGIS Pro (Version 3.1) [Computer software]. Environmental Systems Research Institute.
- Northwest Florida Water Management District. (NFWFMD, 2008). *2008 Water Supply Assessment Update. Water Resources Assessment 08-2. Havana, Florida*. Retrieved June 20, 2023, from https://nfwfwater.com/content/download/7478/56759/WSA_Final2008.pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD, 2009a). *Tate's Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan - Executive Summary*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://www.nfwfwater.com/content/download/5001/33687/Exec_070910a.pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD, 2009b). *Tate's Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan – Vol. 1*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://nfwfwater.com/content/download/4722/32292/Tates_Hydro_Vol_1_081310a.pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD, 2009c). *Tate's Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan – Vol. 2*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://www.nfwfwater.com/content/download/4687/32117/Tates_Hydro_Vol_2_081310a.pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD, 2012). *Draft - Ochlockonee River and Bay Watershed Surface Water Improvement and Management Plan*. Retrieved June 20, 2023, from <https://www.nfwfwater.com/content/download/7421/56170/DraftOchlockoneeSWIMplan.pdf>
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD, 2017a). *Apalachicola River and Bay Surface Water Improvement and Management (SWIM) Plan*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://www.nfwfwater.com/content/download/18031/121997/Apalachicola%20River%20and%20Bay%20SWIM%20Plan%20November%202017_errata.pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD, 2017b). *Ochlockonee River and Bay Surface Water Improvement and Management (SWIM) Plan*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://nfwfwater.com/content/download/18958/127421/Ochlockonee%20River%20and%20Bay%20SWIM%20Plan%20June2021_errata.pdf

5.5 Bluffs of St. Teresa

In 2020, the state of Florida acquired a 17,112-acre tract of land known as the Bluffs of St. Teresa a.k.a. the St. Teresa Tract. The property is situated approximately 30 miles south/southeast of Tallahassee, Florida, and borders the Ochlockonee River and Bay on the north, and Alligator Harbor and the Gulf of Mexico on the south. The eastern property edge is approximately two miles due west of the Gulf of Mexico where Ochlockonee Bay meets the Gulf. The northern portion of this tract along Ochlockonee Bay and the portion east of U.S. Highway 98 (total of approximately 7,296 ac.) was added to the adjacent Bald Point State Park, managed by the Florida Park Service within the Florida Department of Environmental Protection (FDEP). The southern and northwestern portion (9,816 ac.) of the tract was added to the adjacent Tate's Hell State Forest, managed by the Florida Forest Service within the Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services (FDACS) (Figure 5.5.1).

According to the recent natural community mapping work by the Florida Natural Areas Inventory, the predominant historic natural community on the Bluffs of St. Teresa (BoST) was sandhill, followed by flatwoods (mesic, scrubby, and wet flatwoods) and 18 other natural communities (Figure 5.5.1 and Table 5.5.1). On the FFS-managed portion of BoST, approximately 89% of the historic sandhill was converted to pine plantation, primarily off-site sand pine, and on the FDEP portion over 99% was converted. Other historic natural communities that have been heavily altered to pine plantations include all flatwoods (48-96% across both properties and flatwoods types), scrub (59-68%), and wet prairies (96%).

Figure 5.5.1. Historic natural communities of the Bluffs of St. Teresa, an approximately 17,112 acre tract acquired by the State of Florida in 2020. This tract spans 3 HUC 12 watersheds: Ochlockonee Bay (north), Alligator Harbor-Frontal Gulf of Mexico (south) and Brandy Creek-Crooked River (west). HUC12 boundaries are shown with dashed blue lines, management boundaries are shown with solid black lines.

Table 5.5.1. Historic natural communities of the Bluffs of St. Teresa. Note, some smaller communities were combined in Figure 5.5.1.

Historic Natural Community	Acres	%
Basin marsh	376	2.20%
Baygall	165	0.96%
Bottomland forest	290	1.70%
Depression marsh	255	1.49%
Dome swamp	14	0.08%
Flatwoods lake	147	0.86%
Floodplain marsh	593	3.47%
Floodplain swamp	1,136	6.64%
Marsh lake	8	0.05%
Mesic flatwoods	2,007	11.73%
Mesic hammock	9	0.05%
Salt marsh	407	2.38%
Sandhill	8,111	47.40%
Sandhill upland lake	91	0.53%
Scrub	658	3.84%
Scrubby flatwoods	1,056	6.17%
Shrub bog	329	1.92%
Tidal creek	115	0.67%
Upland hardwood forest	5	0.03%
Wet flatwoods	1,221	7.13%
Xeric hammock	35	0.20%
Wet prairie	85	0.50%

In 2022, FDEP created a draft Unit Management Plan for Bald Point State Park which included future assessment, restoration, and management priorities for St. Teresa Tract (FDEP, 2022). One of the top priorities for this tract is directly relevant to RESTORE and ARRI 2&3 including the restoration of thousands of acres of former pine plantation. FFS does not require an updated management plan, but staff on Tate’s Hell SF are exploring options for improving road access to timber activities, including the removal of offsite sand pine from sandhill communities. On both properties the restoration of native groundcover (e.g., wiregrass) will be important so that prescribed fire can be reintroduced to maintain these ecosystems.

As described in Section 4.3 the ecological condition model (ECM) for open pine ecosystems across all lands within the Apalachicola Region provides valuable insight to help guide restoration efforts on BoST. The ECM results for BoST (Figure 5.5.2.) estimate that over 87% of the ecosystems are in fair or poor condition, which agrees closely with the field-based natural community assessments from FNAI staff. The restoration goals of FDEP and FFS will involve removal of the sand pine understory, and reestablishment of native wiregrass and longleaf pine along with reintroduction of prescribed fire. This restoration work has proven to be successful on other conservation lands in the Apalachicola Region such as TNC’s Apalachicola Bluffs and Ravines Preserve and should also prove successful at BoST.

In addition to drastically improving ecosystem conditions, this restoration will significantly improve the water quantity from this site by reducing evapotranspiration from dense sand pine. CSER staff applied the spatial water yield model from Section 4.4 to estimate the potential water yield gain

from two different silvicultural scenarios applied to BoST (Figure 5.5.3). If the approximately 4,400 acres of the densest sand pine stands are restored, this could return over 400M gallons of water per year to this ecosystem, the underlying aquifers and the adjacent Ochlockonee Bay, Alligator Harbor and the Gulf of Mexico.

Figure 5.5.2. Current ecological conditions (see Section 4.2) estimated for the Bluffs of St. Teresa.

USFS and CSER staff plan to meet with staff from FDEP, Bald Point SP, Tate’s Hell SF, and TNC in the Fall of 2023 to explore opportunities to leverage limited restoration funding on this high priority tract. Products and workflows developed during this THS1 planning project will also be used to add value to the restoration activities that will occur. For example, initial estimates of potential water yield gain from clearcutting sand pine and planting lower density (30-50 BA) longleaf pine are presented in Figure 5.5.3. These water yield estimates can be refined as needed based management plans. The reintroduction of prescribed fire will also be important to maintain long-term water quantity improvements by limiting ET from hardwood shrubs and trees, especially in sandhill communities.

Figure 5.5.3. Detail view of Bluffs of St. Teresa tract potential water yield gain from thinning dense pine stands under two different silvicultural scenarios.

Another priority in the Bald Point State Park draft Unit Management Plan (FDEP, 2022) includes restoring and protecting the water quality of the surrounding bays and marshes, which support local mariculture activities and habitat for numerous species. A major aspect of this element will assess the park’s hydrologic restoration needs including mapping ditches and erosion issues. CSER staff plans to collaborate with FDEP and Florida Park Service staff in Fall 2023 to share relevant THS1 data products and workflows and explore ways to work together as part of the ARRI Strategies 2&3 Project. For example, lidar-derived products may be of use for identification of ditches, plow lines, and other hydrologic disturbances (Figure 5.5.4).

Figure 5.5.4. Standard deviation of lidar ground elevation within the Bluffs of St. Teresa tract of Bald Point State Park. Lighter shades represent areas with greater variability within a 3m x 3m moving window and can be used to identify ditches along roads and fire plow lines around wetlands (e.g., lighter shades which are linear).

References

- Cohen, M., McLaughlin, D., Kaplan, D., & Acharya, S. (2017). *Managing Forest for Increase Regional Water Availability: Report on Task7: Year 3 Annual Report* (FDACS Contract No. 20834). Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services. State of Florida. Retrieved from https://www.fdacs.gov/content/download/76293/file/20834_Del_7.pdf
- Florida Department of Environmental Protection (FDEP). Ochlockonee River State Park, Bald Point State Park- Advisory Group Draft Unit Management Plan. (Draft, Oct 2022) Retrieved from: <https://floridadep.gov/parks/parks-office-park-planning/documents/ochlockonee-river-and-bald-point-state-parks-2022-draft-0>
- Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Florida Forest Service (FFS). Ten-year Management Plan for the Tate's Hell State Forest- Franklin and Liberty Counties. October 2019. Retrieved from: <https://www.fdacs.gov/content/download/4904/file/Tate%27s-Hell-SF-2019-LMP.pdf>

Nordman, C., White, R., Wilson, R., Ware, C., Rideout, C., Pyne, M., & Hunter, C. (2016, May 12) *Rapid Assessment Metrics to Enhance Wildlife Habitat and Biodiversity within Southern Open Pine Ecosystems*. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and NatureServe, for the Gulf Coastal Plains and Ozarks Landscape Conservation Cooperative.

https://www.natureserve.org/sites/default/files/projects/files/openpinemetrics-finalreport_12may16.pdf

St. Peter, J., Anderson, C., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2020). Spatially Quantifying Forest Loss at Landscape-scale Following a Major Storm Event. *Remote Sensing*, 12(7), 1138.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs12071138>

St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., & Ibeanusi, V. (2021). Forest Structural Estimates Derived Using a Practical, Open-Source Lidar-Processing Workflow. *Remote Sensing* 13(23), 4763.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13234763>

5.6 Telogia Creek Watershed

The Telogia Creek Watershed, situated in the Florida Panhandle, spans across Gadsden and Liberty Counties northeast of the Apalachicola River and west of Tallahassee. As a component of the larger Apalachicola-Chattahoochee-Flint (ACF) River Basin, the creek is enclosed within the Lower Ochlocknee HUC8 watershed (HUC ID: 03120003) (Figure 5.6.1). Its relatively compact area encompasses a network of streams, tributaries, and wetlands, ultimately feeding into Telogia Creek and serving as a significant tributary of the Ochlockonee River. Numerous wetlands within the watershed contribute to the overall biodiversity and ecological health of the watershed and surrounding uplands. Telogia Creek is a notably critical habitat for multiple aquatic species of concern, including the federally-threatened Purple Bankclimber (*Elliptoideus sloatianus*) and endangered Ochlockonee Moccasinshell (*Medionidus simpsonianus*).

Figure 5.6.1. Telogia Creek watershed within the Apalachicola Region showing various conservation lands, hydrographic units, and potential restoration opportunities.

Various challenges threaten the health of the Telogia Creek Watershed, together with water quality deterioration due to agricultural runoff, sedimentation from development, and habitat disruption. Water quality impairments are prevalent in many areas of the Telogia Creek Watershed and the adjoining Ochlockonee River Basin due to elevated bacterial concentrations from agricultural runoff and the presence of approximately 23,000 known or likely active septic systems within the watershed (NFWMD, 2017). Agricultural and urban runoff have introduced pollutants and excess nutrients, such as nitrogen and phosphorus, into the creek. These nutrients cause algal blooms, oxygen depletion, and disruptions in the aquatic ecosystem. Additionally, flow regime and natural systems in the Telogia Creek basin have historically been heavily modified by farm pond construction, in-stream impoundments, and agricultural water withdrawals (NFWMD, 2008, 2012). Ongoing land use changes and development in the watershed exacerbate issues like soil erosion and sediment runoff, amplifying the deterioration of water quality, disturbance of aquatic habitats, and obstruction of waterways. At this juncture, a comprehensive strategy is imperative to restore and safeguard the Telogia Creek ecosystem, ensuring clean water for both inhabitants and imperiled wildlife.

Of significant importance in the Telogia Creek watershed is a recent acquisition of a 12,428-acre tract of land by the Florida Forever Program⁺. This tract is on the south side of State Road 20 between Bristol and Hosford, approximately 12 miles upstream from Telogia Creek's confluence with the Ochlockonee River. Conservation lands are located within five miles of the proposal area (Figure 5.6.1)

including the Apalachicola National Forest, Torreya State Park, Apalachee River WMA, and Apalachicola Bluffs and Ravines Preserve. As well, nearby Florida Forever projects include the Apalachicola River Project and the Hosford Chapman’s Rhododendron Protection Zone.

Moving forward, CSER and partners intend to work closely with RESTORE, state and federal agencies, and other partners/stakeholders to assist with projects in the Telogia Creek Watershed such as:

- Characterize upland habitat conditions and vegetation metrics particularly in riparian areas of Telogia Creek using advanced remote sensing and spatial analysis as detailed in Figure 5.6.2.
- Conduct targeted and relevant water quality/quantity assessments in strategic, non-attainment areas of the watershed, particularly in areas that may improve conditions for threatened and endangered species.
- Model watershed hydrology on a fine scale.
- Recommend and participate in strategies to improve general water quality and quantity conditions in Telogia Creek and its tributaries.
- Explore ways to make this watershed more climate resilient.

Figure 5.6.2. Current high-resolution ecological condition estimates (see Section 4.2) for recently acquired state conservation lands in the Telogia Creek Watershed, created by CSER in the Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 Project.

References

- Northwest Florida Water Management District. (NFWWMD, 2008). 2008 Water Supply Assessment Update. Water Resources Assessment 08-2. Havana, Florida. Retrieved June 20, 2023, from https://nfwwater.com/content/download/7478/56759/WSA_Final2008.pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWWMD, 2012). Draft - *Ochlockonee River and Bay Watershed Surface Water Improvement and Management Plan*. Retrieved June 20, 2023, from <https://www.nfwwater.com/content/download/7421/56170/DraftOchlockoneeSWIMplan.pdf>
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWWMD, 2017). *Ochlockonee River and Bay Surface Water Improvement and Management (SWIM) Plan*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://nfwwater.com/content/download/18958/127421/Ochlockonee%20River%20and%20Bay%20SWIM%20Plan%20June2021_errata.pdf

5.7 Geographically Isolated Wetlands

The response of Southeastern forests to climate change has underscored the significance of forested wetlands, which play a pivotal role in the region's hydrological cycle. Geographically isolated wetlands (GIWs) also known as ephemeral wetlands, are an integral component of southeastern pine forested ecosystems, and provide a spectrum of advantages to both the environment and resident species. GIWs function as natural hydrologic buffers, effectively managing water balance during extreme climatic events such as floods and droughts. They exhibit a dynamic inundation extent, adjusting in response to the severity of flooding or drought, thereby embodying a form of innate adaptation. Amplifying their efficacy through forest management tactics renders them indispensable in addressing the challenges posed by shifting climate conditions. This phenomenon is of particular importance to the Apalachicola Region primarily because it is a major source of clean freshwater for the Gulf of Mexico, an international biodiversity hotspot, and a significant landscape for longleaf pine restoration.

A notable example of this spectacle can be readily seen on the Apalachicola National Forest, where Figure 5.7.1 illustrates the correlation between precipitation and forested wetlands, depicting diverse and occasionally drastic inundation patterns. These hydrologically classified wetlands, often small in scale, experience brief inundation during periods of low evapotranspiration, typically in winter or early spring. Significantly, these wetlands contribute to resilience against climate-induced disturbances by adapting their inundation dynamics. This hydrological regulation capability is pivotal in moderating micro-climates and extreme precipitation events by curtailing runoff. However, accurately delineating the inundation status of forested wetlands remains a hurdle, especially when contrasted with more permanent water bodies. Here is a summary of several key benefits offered by ephemeral wetlands in these forests:

- **Water Regulation and Quality**
 - Ephemeral wetlands help regulate water flow by acting as natural sponges, temporarily storing excess water during heavy rainfall, and slowly releasing it, which reduces the risk of downstream flooding.
 - GIWs play a role in filtering and purifying water as it passes through, improving water quality by trapping sediments and absorbing nutrients.
- **Fire Management**
 - Ephemeral wetlands can act as natural firebreaks in pine forests, reducing the spread of wildfires.
 - During dry periods, these wetlands contain moisture that can hinder the advance of fires, protecting adjacent forested areas.

- **Biodiversity and Habitat Support**
 - Ephemeral wetlands create unique habitats that support a diverse range of rare plant and animal species.
 - These wetlands serve as breeding grounds for amphibians, reptiles, insects, and various bird species.
 - The fluctuating water levels and nutrient-rich soils promote the growth of diverse and unique plant species, contributing to overall ecosystem diversity. Some rare plants are only located in or near these areas.
 - They have been identified as critical habitat for the federally threatened Frosted Flatwoods Salamander (*Ambystoma cingulatum*) that occurs in only a few remaining areas in this region.
- **Nutrient Cycling**
 - These wetlands contribute to nutrient cycling by capturing and retaining nutrients that might otherwise leach into groundwater or nearby waterbodies.
 - Nutrient cycling supports the growth of vegetation and enhances overall ecosystem productivity.
- **Carbon Sequestration**
 - Ephemeral wetlands store carbon in their soils, contributing to carbon sequestration and helping to mitigate the effects of climate change.
 - GIWs also promote the growth of vegetation, which further aids in carbon capture.
- **Preservation of Endangered Species**
 - Ephemeral wetlands often provide habitat for rare or endangered species that rely on these unique environments for survival.
 - Conserving these wetlands can contribute to the protection of these species and help maintain overall biodiversity.
- **Resilience to Climate Change**
 - Ephemeral wetlands contribute to ecosystem resilience by providing refuge for species during extreme weather events. They can essentially create microclimates and serve as refugia where species can survive through extended periods of unfavorable climate conditions.
- **Educational and Recreational Opportunities**
 - Ephemeral wetlands provide excellent opportunities for environmental education and research, allowing scientists and students to study unique ecosystems and their dynamics.
 - These wetlands can also offer recreational benefits to visitors, such as birdwatching, photography, and nature observation.
- **Economic Value**
 - Ephemeral wetlands can contribute to local economies through ecotourism and recreational activities, attracting visitors who spend money on accommodations, transportation, and related services.
 - The wetlands' ability to regulate water flow can also provide indirect economic benefits by reducing flood damage and associated costs.

Overall, GIWs are essential components of southeastern pine forests, offering a wide array of ecological, societal, and economic benefits that underscore their importance for both the environment and the human communities that depend on them. Moving forward, it is CSER's intent to collaborate closely with state and federal partners to investigate Geographically Isolated Wetlands (GIWs) in the Apalachicola Region, focusing mainly on the Apalachicola National Forest. By leveraging advanced

drone-borne lidar, hyperspectral, and thermal imagery across 350,000 acres of the Apalachicola Ranger District on the ANF (see Section 8.8), this project aims to employ cutting-edge remote sensing technologies and meticulous spatial analyses to bridge knowledge gaps concerning the role of forested wetlands in hydrological management amidst changing water availability and climate fluctuations.

Figure 5.7.1 Geographically isolated forest wetlands showing variable inundation in the Apalachicola National Forest. Images show an isolated wetland under drought conditions (above) and another inundated wetland below.

5.8 Prescribed Fire

In the absence of regular prescribed fire, the understory of southern open pine ecosystems often rapidly transitions from thick pyrogenic herbaceous cover to one principally dominated by different species of woody shrubs. Management areas with accurate and spatially-explicit fire history data can typically use these data as a proxy to estimate current ground cover conditions. Unfortunately, these data are often not available and vary in quality over space and time. For greater consistency in this project, CSER staff have incorporated fire history data from the Florida Fire Occurrence Dataset (FWC, 2020) and have provided feedback to partners from Tall Timbers Research Station and the SE FireMap⁺ as they continue to develop and refine these data using Landsat and soon harmonized Landsat and

Sentinel-2 imagery. Figure 5.8.1 illustrates the considerable variability in burn history for the northeastern corner of the Apalachicola NF. This is a very challenging area for prescribed fire management given the close proximity of the City of Tallahassee, the Tallahassee Airport, and several major thoroughfares.

Figure 5.8.1. Total number of fires from 1994-2019 from the FWC Florida Fire Occurrence database[‡].

As discussed in Section 4.3, these fire history data were combined with relative shrub density metrics derived from airborne lidar to estimate the condition of the understory for all open pine ecosystems in the Apalachicola Region. Not surprisingly, the spatial patterns observed in fire history (Figure 5.8.1) closely correspond to those seen in the ECM understory condition scores shown in Figure 5.8.2. Areas with very few to no fires over the observation period (1994-2019) also typically have heavy encroachment from woody shrubs and score poorly in multiple criteria used in the understory component of the ECM. While fire history is an important indicator of understory ecological condition, it is important to note remote sensing techniques to map fires can easily miss low severity fires in predominately herbaceous ecosystems such as wet prairies. Additionally, these products are currently produced at a resolution of 30 m and may miss fires in narrow, ecotonal areas between uplands and wetlands (e.g., seepage slopes on the western Apalachicola NF). By incorporating two additional fine-resolution (5-m) lidar-derived structural metrics into the ECM understory component and using different

weighting thresholds for wet prairies, we have mitigated some of these impacts to create a more robust understory condition score to guide management activities.

Figure 5.8.2. Understory ecological condition model scores (see Section 4.2) for the northeastern corner of the Apalachicola NF near the Tallahassee Airport.

Lidar shrub density metrics can also be used operationally to target prescribed fire activities to maximize ecological benefits. For example, in areas where shrubs have encroached but have not yet totally dominated, a fire management professional may time a prescribed fire so that it reduces shrub cover while favoring pyrogenic herbaceous species. Lidar data, particularly from UAS platforms with high-resolution sensors (Figure 5.8.3), provide detailed, tactical information for field crews to use to plan and implement ecologically oriented burning, and to monitor prescribed fire effectiveness by collecting post-fire UAS data.

Figure 5.8.3. Drone laser scanning (DLS) data (~140 returns/m) from a pine stand with dense midstory vegetations and tall shrubs. DLS data was collected through the PRISM project (Section 8.8) and provides fine detail for developing prescribed fire and silvicultural plans and for measuring treatment effectiveness.

5.9 Midstory Treatments/Timber Stand Improvements (TSI)

Several forest structural products created for this project (Section 4.2) can also be used to identify areas for midstory treatments and timber stand improvements (TSI). For example, total basal area, pine basal area, basal area by DBH class, and trees per acre and quadratic mean stem diameter can help target areas for TSI work. Lidar midstory relative density metrics and the midstory condition scores from the Ecological Condition Model (Section 4.3) can also help target areas for silvicultural treatments to improve the health and growth of timber and to reduce evapotranspiration (Section 4.4). Figure 5.9.1 illustrates areas where midstory hardwood cover could be reduced to improve connectivity of high quality habitat for Red-cockaded Woodpecker (*Dryobates borealis*). Drone laser scanning (DLS) data as shown in Figure 5.8.3 and other parts of this manuscript can also be deployed to capture detailed measurements for planning tactical silvicultural treatments as well as monitoring the effectiveness of treatments after implementation.

Figure 5.9.1. Midstory ecological condition model scores (Section 4.3) for the northeastern corner of the Apalachicola NF near the Tallahassee Airport. This area includes Leon Sinks Geological Area and provides habitat for the federally listed Red-cockaded Woodpecker (RCW), however areas of dense midstory hardwoods bisect portions of this habitat.

5.10 Wildlife Habitat Improvements

As touched on in the midstory hardwood example previously, products created by CSER staff in this project have multiple applications for planning wildlife habitat improvement activities. Forest structure is a critical indicator of wildlife habitat conditions, and preferred habitat conditions for species such as the Red-cockaded Woodpecker (RCW, *Dryobates borealis*) are well known (U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service, 2003) and are commonly used by land managers to help guide forest restoration at project to landscape scales. In Figure 5.10.1, we illustrate how derived products such as pine basal area can be combined to achieve multiple restoration objectives, including previously described water yield benefits and habitat improvements for federally listed species such as RCW and Frosted Flatwoods Salamander (*Ambystoma cingulatum*). Lidar data also offer remarkably detailed information for evaluating the condition of and monitoring restoration efforts in small (<0.05 acres) geographically isolated wetlands, which can potentially serve as breeding locations for Frosted Flatwoods Salamanders (Figure 5.10.2).

Figure 5.10.1. Detail view of ecological restoration opportunities in management compartments 4 and 13 on the Apalachicola NF. This map relates to the fine-resolution hydrologic restoration opportunities shown in Figure 5.2.1. Dense pine (>80 square ft/ac) are shown in relation to habitat for two federally listed species- Frosted Flatwoods Salamander and Red-cockaded Woodpecker (RCW). Highest priority restoration areas could not only increase water yield (but could also improve habitat conditions for priority species.

Figure 5.10.2. Airborne laser scanner (ALS) data (~6 returns/m) from two small ephemeral ponds that provide potential breeding habitat for the Frosted Flatwoods Salamander. Left hand plots are 3D point clouds from an untreated, fire-excluded pond (top left) and from a pond that was restored by field crews that manually removed small diameter hardwoods trees and shrubs (bottom left). Right hand plots represent histograms of the percentage of all lidar returns by height for the untreated (top right) and restored (bottom right) ephemeral ponds. Although there is not a substantial difference in mean height, the canopy cover, midstory and shrub layers are significantly higher in the untreated pond.

5.11 Coastal Blue Carbon Stocks and Mangrove Condition Assessments

Mangroves hold significant ecological and socioeconomic value, but many regions around the globe have experienced significant losses in their distribution. These declines are predominantly attributed to human caused activities and sea level rise (Van der Stocken et al., 2018). That said, in spite of the significant losses of this habitat type, a fairly recent phenomenon has begun to occur, which facilitates northward expansion of mangroves along the coasts of Florida. This migration of mangrove habitat into temperate regions is both ecologically and environmentally noteworthy primarily due to mangroves' traditional association with tropical and subtropical climates. Historically thriving in southern Florida, mangroves have been extending their range up the Atlantic (Kyle et al. 2013) and Gulf Coasts (Bardou et al., 2023) and into the Big Bend Region of Florida near Apalachicola (Figure 5.11.1). In a seminal study from the Smithsonian Environmental Research Center and the University of Maryland, Kyle et al. 2013 examined 28 years of satellite imagery to track the poleward expansion of mangroves on Florida's Atlantic Coast. Between 1984 and 2011, the east coast of Florida gained more than 3,000 acres (1,240 hectares) of mangroves. The primary reason for the migration appears to be driven by fewer extreme cold weather events that allow their survival further north. During the initial five years of the

study, the region of northern Daytona Beach observed a reduction of 1.4 days per year with temperatures falling below -4 degrees Celsius (24.8°F). In contrast, during the same time frame, the frequency of killing frosts in southern Florida was unchanged. In essence, mangroves, which historically struggled with prolonged freezes, are now flourishing in regions where there was previously a concern because the freeze duration is less even though the frequency remains unchanged. Expanding upon this, it is worth noting that while the migration of mangrove and other tree species in response to a warming climate is expected to involve shifts to higher latitudes or elevations, the substantiation of such latitudinal range adjustments for various species groups is largely inferred through indirect observations (Zhu et al., 2011). However, this situation does raise the question of whether we are approaching a climatic tipping point or perhaps other factors are involved. That said, the actual answer is likely multi-factorial and anything but direct.

In addition to the shifting climate, an additional theory suggests that the increased frequency of hurricanes might aid mangroves to disperse their seeds. It is known that episodic events like hurricanes can force species to surpass migration limitations, resulting in temporary phases of swift range shifts (Renwick & Rocca, 2015). In a 2020 study by Kennedy et al., researchers examined how hurricanes create the conditions needed to drive range expansion at a northern distributional limit of the neotropical Black Mangrove (*Avicennia germinans*). This phenomenon is known to shape patterns of genetic variation in expanding populations of this species. For similar weather-related reasons, areas like the Apalachicola Region are witnessing the flourishing of mangroves, which were previously uncommon.

Another notable fact about mangroves is that they are a significant source of what is termed “blue carbon.” Blue carbon refers to the carbon stored in coastal and marine ecosystems, specifically in vegetation, sediment, and soils of ecosystems like mangroves, seagrasses, salt marshes, and tidal marshes. These ecosystems are often located in coastal areas and play a significant role in carbon sequestration and climate change mitigation. Blue carbon draws parallels to “green carbon”, which represents the carbon stored in terrestrial forests and vegetation. Blue carbon ecosystems, however, are found in aquatic environments, making them an essential component of the global carbon cycle. They have the capacity to sequester and store carbon dioxide (CO²) from the atmosphere, helping mitigate the effects of climate change. Key features of blue carbon ecosystems include:

- **Coastal Protection** - Mangrove ecosystems act as natural buffers against coastal erosion and storm surges, contributing to coastal resilience.
- **Vegetation** - Mangroves, seagrasses, and other marine plants are particularly effective at capturing and storing carbon through photosynthesis. They accumulate biomass both above and below the water surface.
- **Sediment and Soil** - The sediment and soil in these ecosystems can accumulate organic carbon over time. Anaerobic (low-oxygen) conditions in waterlogged soils prevent organic matter from fully decomposing, allowing carbon to be stored for extended periods.
- **Stable Carbon Storage** - Blue carbon ecosystems can store carbon for centuries or even millennia, making them valuable in long-term carbon sequestration efforts.
- **Habitat for Biodiversity** - These ecosystems provide critical habitat for various species, including commercially important fish and shellfish. Protecting blue carbon habitats supports biodiversity conservation.
- **Climate Change Mitigation** - The conservation and restoration of blue carbon ecosystems contribute to global efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and limit global temperature rise.

CSER's recent methodological breakthroughs, particularly in employing ultra-resolution DLS for structural assessments of forested ecosystems, have paved the way for new, innovative opportunities. These advancements have sparked collaborative endeavors focusing on the expansion of mangrove

habitats in Florida's Big Bend Region, alongside investigations into vegetation structure and the concept of blue carbon. Specifically, CSER has embarked on a comprehensive analysis of the expanding mangrove habitat along the Gulf of Mexico's coastal areas, stretching from Apalachicola to Cedar Key in Florida. This collaborative effort aims to provide an in-depth characterization of mangrove ecosystems, enhancing our ability to quantify and comprehend their significance, particularly in terms of coastal protection and their role as blue carbon reservoirs. The implications of this are profound, as it offers the potential to tap into the impressive capabilities of mangroves in mitigating the impacts of climate change and serving as protective coastal barriers to promote coastal resiliency.

By safeguarding and revitalizing coastal habitats, these ecosystems assume a critical role in sequestering carbon, preserving biodiversity, and acting as a natural barrier against the detrimental effects of climate change on coastal communities. The expansion of mangrove ecosystems into the Big Bend and Apalachicola Regions accentuates the importance of continuous monitoring to accurately gauge shifts in carbon stocks and sequestration rates over time. This ongoing endeavor not only underscores the dynamic nature of mangrove expansion but also reinforces the essential role of scientific collaboration in comprehending and addressing the pressing challenges posed by climate change.

Figure 5.11.1. Presence / absence of mangrove habitat within tidal wetland complexes and inland wetland mitigation spaces for the Big Bend and Apalachicola Regions of Florida (mangrove presence/absence and wetland location data from Bardou et al, 2023).

References

- Bardou, R., Osland, M. J., Scyphers, S., ... [et al.]. (2023). Rapidly Changing Range Limits in a Warming World: Critical Data Limitations and Knowledge Gaps for Advancing Understanding of Mangrove Range Dynamics in the Southeastern USA. *Estuaries and Coasts*, 46, 1123–1140. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12237-023-01209-7>
- Kyle, C. C., Kellner, J. R., Forde, A. J., Gruner, D. S., Parker, J. D., Rodriguez, W., & Feller, I. C. (2013). Poleward expansion of mangroves is a threshold response to decreased frequency of extreme cold events. In G. M. Woodwell (Ed.), *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(2), 723-727. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1315800111>
- Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC). (2020). *Florida Fire Occurrence Data*. [Data set]. State of Florida. <https://myfwc.com/research/gis/wildlife/florida-fire/>
- Renwick, K. M., & Rocca, M. E. (2015). Temporal context affects the observed rate of climate-driven range shifts in tree species. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 24, 44–51. <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12240>
- US Fish and Wildlife Service, 2003. Red-cockaded Woodpecker Recovery Plan, Second Revision. Retrieved from: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/O30320_2.pdf
- Van der Stocken, T., Carrol, D., Menemenlis, D., & Koedam, N. (2018). Global-scale dispersal and connectivity in mangroves. In A. Hastings (Ed.), *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 116(3), 1161-1165. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1812470116>
- Zhu, K., Woodall, C. W., & Clark, J. S. (2011). Failure to migrate: lack of tree range expansion in response to climate change. *Global Change Biology*, 18(3), 1042-1052. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2011.02571.x>

6 Decision Support Systems (DSS)

Decision Support Systems (DSS) for conservation and restoration across large landscapes are essential tools that integrate data, models, and analytical techniques to aid in making informed and effective decisions in environmental management. These systems address the complex challenges associated with managing and restoring ecosystems, biodiversity, and natural resources on a larger scale. Here is a summary of key aspects related to DSS used for conservation and restoration across large landscapes:

- **Data Integration and Analysis** - DSS for conservation and restoration rely on a diverse range of data sources, including satellite imagery, remote sensing data, GIS (Geographic Information Systems) data, ecological surveys, and climate data. These systems integrate these data to create comprehensive spatial and temporal models that represent the landscape's ecological, hydrological, and climatic characteristics.
- **Spatial Modeling and Simulation** - DSS employ spatial models to simulate changes and interactions within a landscape. These models help in predicting the impacts of various conservation and restoration strategies, such as habitat restoration, invasive species management, and land-use planning. They allow decision-makers to visualize and assess the potential outcomes of different actions.
- **Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)** - Conservation and restoration decisions often involve multiple conflicting objectives and criteria. MCDA techniques help prioritize actions by considering factors such as biodiversity, ecosystem services, economic costs, and social preferences. DSS incorporate MCDA to facilitate a systematic evaluation of trade-offs and to select optimal solutions.

- **Scenario Planning** - Large landscapes are dynamic, and future conditions can be uncertain. DSS facilitate scenario planning, allowing stakeholders to explore different future scenarios and assess their implications on conservation and restoration efforts. This helps in identifying robust strategies that are resilient to various uncertainties.
- **Stakeholder Engagement** - Effective conservation and restoration require the involvement of various stakeholders, including government agencies, local communities, NGOs, and scientists. DSS include participatory features that engage stakeholders in the decision-making process, ensuring that diverse perspectives are considered to help lead projects to more socially acceptable outcomes.
- **Risk Assessment** - DSS incorporate risk assessment methodologies to identify potential threats and vulnerabilities to conservation efforts. By analyzing factors such as habitat fragmentation, climate change impacts, and human disturbances, these systems help decision-makers develop strategies to mitigate risks and enhance the long-term success of restoration initiatives.
- **Adaptive Management** - Conservation and restoration efforts often require adaptive management, where strategies are continuously refined based on monitoring and feedback. DSS facilitate adaptive management by providing real-time or near-real-time data on the effectiveness of ongoing restoration actions, allowing managers to adjust their approach as needed.
- **Visualization and Communication** - Effective communication of complex data and models is crucial for gaining support and understanding among stakeholders. DSS provide visualization tools that simplify the presentation of data, helping decision-makers and the public comprehend the potential impacts of different decisions.
- **Scale Considerations** - Large landscapes encompass various scales, from local to regional. DSS must address these scales appropriately to ensure that the conservation and restoration strategies are effective across different spatial dimensions.

In conclusion, Decision Support Systems for conservation and restoration across large landscapes play a pivotal role in guiding evidence-based decision-making. By integrating data, modeling, and stakeholder engagement, these systems empower managers and policymakers to make informed choices that enhance ecosystem health, biodiversity, and the sustainable use of natural resources on a broader scale.

6.1 Regional Restoration Decision Support System (RRDSS) Prototype

As a key deliverable for the Ecological and Hydrological Restoration Planning Component of the RESTORE-funded Tate's Hell Strategy 1 (THS1) Project, a regional restoration decision support system (RRDSS) was developed to showcase the compilation of relevant data within an interactive Web-enabled mapping framework (ESRI's ArcGIS Online) to help users drive science-based decision making and restoration planning in the Apalachicola Region of Florida. Geospatial data developed and compiled in this project can now be used within an online mapping application to create suitability assessment scenarios that help determine where restoration activities would be most beneficial during the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI) Strategies 2 & 3. The ARRI project area is comprised of roughly 4.7 million acres in the Florida panhandle, including multiple public lands managed by federal and state agencies, like the Apalachicola National Forest (ANF), St. Marks National Wildlife Refuge[‡], Tate's Hell State Forest, Apalachicola River Wildlife and Environmental Area[‡], and Bald Point State Park[‡]. Offering regional and perhaps national land managers an accessible and adaptable tool that could strategically help target and prioritize restoration activities across large project areas, especially those for ARRI Strategies 2 & 3, is a primary goal of this initiative, and a welcome asset for long-term regional or national planning activities, particularly those related to longleaf pine habitat restoration. This Web-based prototype developed by CSER staff in partnership with the Chesapeake Conservancy's

Conservation Innovation Center (CIC)[‡] successfully delivers a fully functional prototype, which is now hosted on the U.S. Forest Service ArcGIS enterprise system currently available to FS and CSER staff for testing and stakeholder demonstrations. Future iterations of this transferable technology are wholly dependent on continued funding and stakeholder's desire to implement the RRDSS as a strategic planning solution for land managers.

In recent years, land management across the Apalachicola Region has consistently been dominated by longleaf pine regeneration with an emphasis on restoring historic hydrologic regimes that were disrupted when commercial pine production dominated the landscape (NFWFMD, 2017a, b). Previously, as a mechanism to evaluate current and desired future condition of the natural communities of the ANF, the U.S. Forest Service National Forests in Florida developed an Ecological Condition Model (ECM)[‡] based on reference conditions of various ecosystems throughout the region and other parts of Florida[‡]. The natural communities included in this analysis were wet savannas, sandhills, flatwoods, and upland pine forests, where forest management activities were planned and conducted. To accomplish this effort and calibrate the condition models, the ECM used ground-truthed field plots at over 400 locations on the Apalachicola National Forest, which included comprehensive information on the structure and composition of canopy, midstory, shrub and ground cover layers. Other spatially explicit data included in the predictive ECM were derived products from airborne lidar, burn history, stand age and dominant species type. The work conducted during the THS1 Planning Component expands on previous ecological condition modeling efforts by addressing one of the ECM's biggest limitations – a limited geographic extent dictated by legacy data used to derive various forest structural metrics. In other words, the geographic extent of the original ECM could not be expanded beyond national forest boundaries because enterprise Forest Service data, the best available data at the time, had to be used for several variables to derive ecological condition indexes, thus limiting the transferability of this methodology to areas beyond the national forest boundary. However, with advances in spatial data collection and processing techniques discussed in other sections of this document, datasets included in this RRDSS were developed using peer-reviewed, open-source methodologies, which can easily be replicated to other areas across Florida and the Gulf Coast Region but not necessarily be restricted to property or other administrative boundary types. The high spatial resolution and extent of these datasets have also provided the ability to create an extremely scalable and adaptable decision support system, thus allowing land managers to make informed planning decisions at multiple scales regardless of ownership. This is particularly beneficial to restoration efforts that involve public land managers and private landowners by aiding collaborative partnerships to effectively apply management techniques across broad areas of multiple ownership types.

RRDSS Prototype Evolution, Configuration, Data, Storage and Estimated Costs

The THS1 RRDSS prototype deliverable configuration employs a weighted raster overlay (WRO)[‡] published as an image service to an Esri ArcGIS Enterprise Image Server instance. Weighted overlay models like the one we selected for the prototype RRDSS provide a powerful way to manipulate, analyze, and visualize site suitability characteristics based on applicable user-selected criteria which in our case were specifically related to ecological and hydrological restoration within the Apalachicola Region. Typically, a weighted overlay has three analytical steps as follows: 1) individual raster datasets are assigned a weight of importance designated as a percentage, 2) raster values are mapped to a common suitability scale which allows the user to compare information in each raster layer, and 3) all raster layers are overlaid, and each cell's suitability value is multiplied by the assigned layer weight and totaled. The result is a data-driven suitability value symbolized in the output raster layer for practitioner-guided planning priorities.

For the prototype restoration suitability modeler, we published a WRO from a mosaiced dataset that included relevant data layers, which are listed in Table 6.1.1 and show the data layer name, steward, or publisher, estimated size of each layer when clipped to the ARRI study area, and the spatial resolution of the original raster layer included in the RRDSS WRO (2023) imagery layer currently hosted on the U.S. Forest Service ESRI ArcGIS Enterprise Image Server. The Geospatial Data Requirements Table 6.1.2 includes data layer names, corresponding WRO ranges, and feature subtypes. Unfortunately, the WRO layer can only contain 15 raster datasets to allow for effective publishing. If additional layers are needed for a more complex analysis, users may need to export the results from the Web application and import the data into ArcGIS Pro, which is a somewhat seamless process. While CSER developed most of the datasets utilized in the RRDSS, some of the layers originate from other agencies and will rely upon a 3rd-party update schedule for inclusion in this tool if updates continue after the first RRDSS publication version. A maintenance and update schedule for incorporating new data and versioning of the Web image service would also be required, likely following agency reporting and fiscal schedules. It is recommended to provide annual updates, aligning with the inclusion of the previous year's data from the FWC fire occurrence database (now SE FireMap[†]). Additionally, updates should correspond with the NRCS soil survey, which is typically refreshed in late fall. New data versions could also be incorporated in future application iterations for improved accuracy and higher spatial resolutions of final prioritization schemes — e.g., forest structural metrics currently use USGS 3DEP QL2 lidar point clouds but could be updated based on derivatives from higher density point clouds from other sources. Supplementary instructions on how to create a WRO can be found at ESRI's ArcGIS application design and planning Website for the Weighted Raster Overlay Service Toolbox[†].

Table 6.1.1. Online RRDSS data layer attributes included in the current weighted raster overlay.

Dataset	Acquisition Year	Steward	Estimated Size	Spatial Resolution
Canopy Basal Area	2018	CSER	938 MB (16bit)	5m
Canopy Relative Density (RD)	2018	CSER	480 MB (8bit)	10m
Upper Midstory RD	2018	CSER	480 MB (8bit)	10m
Lower Midstory RD	2018	CSER	469 MB (8bit)	10m
Shrub RD	2018	CSER	469 MB (8bit)	10m
Canopy Cover (%)	2018	CSER	480 MB (8bit)	10m
Fire Frequency	1994-2019	FWC	408 MB (8bit)	30m
Year Since Last Burn	1994-2019	FWC	480 MB (8bit)	30m
Cooperative Land Cover	2021	FWC	480 MB (8bit)	10m
Soils - Hydrologic Group	2022	NRCS	240 MB (4bit)	30m
Soils - Drainage Class	2022	NRCS	521 MB (8bit)	30m

Once the WRO is available online, it can be utilized within the ESRI ArcGIS Online GeoPlanner[†] application. Alternatively, it can be integrated into a customizable web application using the suitability modeler application widget[†]. Both options were evaluated for functionality and serviceability. However, the widget was chosen as the preferred interface for the RRDSS. This choice was primarily influenced by the fact that GeoPlanner requires active membership in a specific GeoPlanner project, which restricts access to users within an ArcGIS Online organization. Additionally, GeoPlanner's standard tools and capabilities focus on the use of vector data for environmental planning, rather than the raster-based inputs required for the modified ECM. Therefore, effective utilization of GeoPlanner as a land management tool would require extensive user data management to ensure proper functionality within the platform, along with the provision of an in-depth technical report to guide users in this process.

Table 6.1.2. THS1 RRDSS weighted raster overlay geospatial data requirements.

Layer	WRO Ranges	Cooperative Land Cover	Hardwood Forested Uplands
Canopy Basal Area	0-19	Cooperative Land Cover	Scrub
	20-39		Sandhill
	40-49		Flatwoods
	50-59		Shrub and Brushland
	60-69		Developed
	70-79		Ruderal
	80-89		Wet Prairie
	>=90		Mixed Scrub-Shrub Wetland
Canopy RD >45 ft	0-4		Marshes
	5-9		Freshwater Forested Wetlands
	10-19		Non-vegetated Wetland
	20-39		Shrub Bog
	40-59		Coniferous Plantations
	>=60		Upland Mixed Woodland
Midstory RD 20-45 ft	0-9		Upland Pine
	10-14		Coastal Uplands
	15-19		Barren and Outcrop Communities
	20-24		Water
	25-34		No value
	>=35		very poorly drained
Midstory RD 10-20 ft	0-3		poorly drained
	4-9		somewhat poorly drained
	10-19		well drained
	>=20		moderately well drained
Shrub RD 2-10 ft	0-2	somewhat excessively drained	
	3-4	excessively drained	
	5-9	None	
	>=10	A	
Fire Frequency 1994-2019	>=4	B	
	2-3	C	
	1	D	
	0	A/D	
Years Since Last Burn 1994-2019	<2	B/D	
	2-3	C/D	
	4-6		
	>=7		
Canopy Cover	0-49		
	50-59		
	60-79		
	>=80		
		NRCS Soil Drainage Class	
		NRCS Soil Hydro Group	

Regarding application functionality, there are several additional features that act as companions to the suitability modeler widget. Users can add their own boundary layers in the model. Datasets that can be added to the map include pre-published feature layers in AGOL or any zipped shapefile, CSV, KML, GPX, or GeoJSON uploaded from the user's desktop. Recommended layers that can be used in the Web application include HUC12 subwatersheds, property ownership boundaries, and any management unit or compartmental polygons. Drawing speed and performance may be impacted by the inclusion of additional data and their complexity. Users should refrain from uploading intricate polygons that cover a large area as the app is likely to become unresponsive. Each suitability modeler will default to the pre-configured datasets and values, however, both the suitability values and included data layers can be modified by the end user. This allows for full customization by the user depending on restoration and management objectives. By default, two pre-configured models are available to the user based on forest structural groups, including canopy and understory conditions. Details on pre-configured models are available in the Restoration Scenarios & Priorities subsection and described below.

In addition to functionality and development considerations, achieving a balance between data accessibility, storage size, and cost efficiency is a crucial aspect to address when creating a practical RRDSS prototype. Three options, which included ArcGIS Online environments at CSER, USDA FS, and CIC, were considered for hosting and storage of the RRDSS and its components. Base storage costs are dependent on the platform used for hosting the WRO layer and underlying raster data. The original decision to host data and the WRO on partner servers, rather than within the CSER FAMU instance was based on two factors: 1) CIC had existing infrastructure in place to support the data hosting needs for this project, and 2) they were already working with a professional GIS service company for geospatial hardware and software maintenance which will be an ongoing cost of any future RRDSS iteration. While monthly costs of Microsoft's Azure environment can vary widely based innumerable variables, a generalized estimate of \$180.79 per month for a well-equipped virtual machine that contained the image server instance was projected for CSER using the built-in usage calculator.

The below graphic (Figure 6.1.1) is a depiction of virtual machine costs in MS Azure for hosting the WRO layer. These were the initial costs for a VM running 24/7. An alternate cost savings (auto-shutdown) option was also tested in which the VM was only active during core working hours, Monday-Friday from 8am to 6pm. This auto-shutdown option resulted in a 47% cost reduction per month to \$107.91 for data hosting on the VM. While this was much more cost-effective for long-term management at a small enterprise such as CSER, it limits the availability of the underlying hosted data for updates and restricts the utilization of the prioritization tool to a narrow time window which does not account for peak usage in other time zones.

Figure 6.1.1 Monthly breakdown of Microsoft Azure costs before (Top) and after (Below) implementing an auto-shutdown option on the virtual machine hosting the weighted raster overlay (WRO) and base raster data.

After considering multiple RRDSS deployment scenarios and costs with partners and 3rd party contractors, we ultimately decided to deploy the prototype on the U.S. Forest Service ArcGIS Online instance until our stakeholders determine whether they would like to continue the development of the application as an enduring service. As a result, while the RRDSS is still being evaluated and demonstrated to stakeholders, we did not need to be concerned about paying for 3rd party virtual machines or hosting raster data which can quickly get very costly and was not allowed for based on the original project budget plan. Since the current prototype has been developed on the Forest Service ArcGIS Online organization and enterprise servers, its use requires a domain specific login for access and additional limitations exist that affect the Web application’s functionality, but this can readily be delivered if the decision is to continue operational support and deploy it publicly. Additional widgets can also be added should stakeholders request extra features, however, updates and maintenance to the Web application are solely dependent upon continued funding and designated support staff. For an enhanced, public-facing restoration-focused Web application, deeper conversations with external partners that can assist in the management and maintenance of such a product would be required to determine accurate cost estimates, cost/benefit, and long-term viability.

Restoration Scenarios & Priorities

Included below are snapshots from the RRDS Prototype Web application for multiple customizable scenarios suitable for ecosystem and hydrologic restoration in the Apalachicola Region of Florida and beyond (Figures 6.1.2 – 6.1.5).

Figure 6.1.2. RRDSS Prototype Web application displaying the results of the pre-configured canopy condition model (pane on the right) for the Apalachicola Region of Florida.

Figure 6.1.3. RRDSS Prototype Web application displaying the results of the pre-configured shrub condition model (pane on the right) for Forest Service compartment 64 on the Apalachicola National Forest.

Figure 6.1.4. RRDSS Prototype Web application displaying the results of the pre-configured shrub condition model, with summary of condition classes by Forest Service compartment boundary in the window to the right.

Figure 6.1.5. RRDSS Prototype Web application displaying the results of the pre-configured canopy condition model for the Apalachicola Region. Pane on the right shows the application feature that allows the addition of user data to the map interface to summarize condition classes from the pre-configured model.

References

- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD). *Tate's Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan – Vol. 1*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://nfwwater.com/content/download/4722/32292/Tates_Hydro_Vol_1_081310a.pdf
- Northwest Florida Water Management District (NFWFMD). *Tate's Hell State Forest Hydrologic Restoration Plan – Vol. 2*. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from https://www.nfwwater.com/content/download/4687/32117/Tates_Hydro_Vol_2_081310a.pdf

7 Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI) - Strategies 2 & 3

7.1 ARRI Overview

The Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative Strategies 2 & 3 (“ARRI 2&3”) are collaborative, landscape-level projects focused on restoring longleaf pine, coastal ecosystems, and hydrology within the Apalachicola Region of Florida. The USDA Forest Service, The Nature Conservancy (TNC), Apalachicola Regional Stewardship Alliance (ARSA), Florida Forest Service (FFS), Florida A&M University (FAMU), University of Florida (UF), and the Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER) at FAMU will partner to implement a range of region-wide ecological restoration activities on more than 137,000 acres of federal, state, and private lands. Activities include improvement to water quality and quantity, outreach to public landowners, monitoring, and targeted education to minority students. Under Strategy 2, project partners will implement ecological restoration activities including: region-wide restoration for approximately 137,000 acres of longleaf habitat, targeted silvicultural treatments for about 7,200 acres of dense pine forests, hydrologic restoration for around 1,500 acres, increased

regional prescribed fire, invasive species treatments, and imperiled wetland restoration. Under Strategy 3, the Florida Forest Service will lead a partnership to advise private forest landowners in active management and restoration and educate landowners on stewardship and sustainable forest management. The combined restoration efforts will help restore and conserve critical habitat, and water quantity and quality, benefiting the local economy. ARRI 2 & 3 was approved on Funding Priority List 3B by the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration (RESTORE) Council in 2021 and is expected to begin in early FY 2024.

7.2 Monitoring

CSER will lead ARRI 2&3 monitoring activities in coordination with partners. Monitoring will occur at scales ranging from individual sites to the landscape-level and results will be disseminated using online repositories[‡], annual reports, briefing papers, peer-reviewed publications, and regular meetings with partners and stakeholders. Meetings with partners and stakeholders will include quarterly meetings of the ARRI Steering Committee and/or the Apalachicola Regional Stewardship Alliance (ARSA) and will help inform and adapt ongoing management activities.

Hydrologic restoration (e.g., low water crossing installation) will be monitored before, during, and after treatments. Monitoring will include site visits using standard protocols developed by the CSER, USFS Center for Aquatic Technology Transfer, and Southeast Aquatic Resource Partnership to 1) assess conditions of cross drains, culverts, ditches, and plugs, 2) improve hydrologic flow, 3) reduce sedimentation, and 4) improve aquatic organism passages (Center for Aquatic Technology Transfer, 2019). A subset of hydrologic restoration sites will also be more intensively monitored using drone-borne image sensors to map changing conditions (e.g., water levels, vegetation).

Field-based monitoring of prescribed fire and timber thinning activities will be led by the Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI) in conjunction with CSER. Field data (e.g., % herbaceous cover and % shrub cover,) will be collected at a subset of treatment locations across a range of conditions (e.g., different natural communities, soil types, etc.) both before and after treatments occur. These results will be analyzed and shared in annual reports for the USFS and the RESTORE Council.

Pre-treatment drone-based lidar and imagery are currently being collected over most of the Apalachicola Ranger District through the Partnership for Remote Inventory and Survey and Management (PRISM, see section 8.8), a partnership between the USFS and the University of Florida (UF). PRISM builds on the ongoing collaboration between the USFS and UF for rapid assessment of hurricane damage and the estimation of forest conditions, including tree-level crown metrics (Section 8.7). At many of the same sites where field monitoring data are collected, post-treatment drone-based lidar and imagery will also be collected. Lidar point cloud data will be used to derive forest structural metrics (see Table 4.2.1) both before and after activities thus demonstrating the effectiveness of treatments such as prescribed fire and timber thinning (e.g., changes in the relative density of shrubs).

An example of how airborne/drone-based lidar will be used to monitor changes in forest structure in ARRI 2&3 is illustrated below in Figure 7.2.1. In this example, Canopy Height Models (CHMs) representing the height of tree and shrub canopies relative to ground elevation are used to map fine-scale damage from Hurricane Michael, however the same approach could also be used to monitor the changes in forest structure from thinning an overstocked pine plantation. Similarly, changes in shrub density could also be measured after a prescribed fire activity using the lidar RDCC approach described in Section 4.2 (specifically, using the “RD_2to10ft” band from Table 4.2.1). The ability to rapidly deploy drone-based lidar to collect post-treatment data will be crucial, especially to monitor prescribed fire effectiveness. The 2020 post-hurricane airborne lidar data shown in Figure 7.2.1 was tasked immediately after Hurricane Michael (winter 2018/19), flown in spring 2020 and delivered as a final product in Oct

2022 (4 years after the hurricane). In contrast, post-treatment drone data can be collected, processed, and analyzed within days or weeks of an activity. An example of an ultra-resolution CHM derived from drone-based lidar is shown in Figure 7.2.2 (see Section 8.8 for more details).

Figure 7.2.1. Using lidar-derived Canopy Height Models (CHM) to monitor changes in forest structure. Top panel is a CHM from 2018 airborne lidar, middle panel is from 2020 (post-hurricane) CHM, bottom panel shows the CHM differences including downed (red) trees and leaning (blue) trees from Hurricane Michael.

Figure 7.2.2. Ultra-resolution (0.25 m) Canopy Height Model (CHM) from drone laser scanning (DLS) collected through Partnership for Remote Inventory, Survey and Management (PRISM, see section 8.8), a partnership between the USFS and the University of Florida (UF).

References

- Center for Aquatic Technology Transfer (CATT). (2019). Summary of aquatic organism passage surveys on the Apalachicola National Forest, Florida 2017-2019. USDA Forest Service Southern Research Station. Accessed: February 21, 2023. Available at: https://srs.fs.usda.gov/catt/pdf/aop/2017-2019_FL_CATT_AOP_report.pdf
- Prata, G., E. N Broadbent, D. Almeida, J. St. Peter, J. Drake, P. Medley, A. P. Dalla Corte, J. Vogel, A. Sharma, C.A Silva, A. Zambrano, R. Valbuena and B. Wilkinson. 2020. "Single-pass UAV-borne GatorEye LiDAR sampling as a rapid assessment method for surveying forest structure." *Remote Sensing*. 12(24), 4111; <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12244111>

8 Ancillary, Opportunistic and Supportive Research

8.1 Mapping Historic Natural Communities of the Apalachicola Region

The Apalachicola region is within an important biodiversity hotspot (Blaustein, 2008) which contains many endemic species and rare natural communities. Before ecological restoration efforts can occur, it is important to have reliable information about the natural communities that were present at some historical baseline. This information is invaluable to understand how current conditions differ from historic conditions (e.g., due to past management activities or fire exclusion) and to guide ecological restoration efforts. As an example, an area that is currently managed as an even aged slash pine plantation would require different restoration activities if it was historically a wet flatwoods versus historically a nearly treeless wet prairie community.

From 2012-2016, the National Forests in Florida Ecosystem Management staff worked closely with the Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI) to develop spatial datasets delineating historic natural communities for the Apalachicola NF (as well as for Ocala and Osceola NFs). Natural communities are characterized and defined by a combination of vegetation structure and composition, topography, landform, substrate, soil moisture condition, climate, and fire (FNAI, 2010). To delineate historic natural communities, FNAI scientists utilized a wide range of datasets including georeferenced aerial photos (1937-2014), NRCS soil data, lidar digital elevation models, rare species element occurrence records, cooperative land cover data (FWC, 2021), and hundreds of vegetation plots. The Apalachicola NF dataset was subsequently integrated with historic natural community data from surrounding state lands within the Apalachicola Region to create a regional historic natural community dataset that covers 873,576 acres (Figure 8.1.1).

Figure 8.1.1. Historic natural community data for six public conservation lands within the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative project area. Data was produced by FNAI scientists in conjunction with U.S. Forest Service, Florida Forest Service, and Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission staff.

References

- Blaustein, R. J. (2008). Biodiversity hotspot: The Florida panhandle. *BioScience* 58(9), 784–790. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.1641/b580904>
- Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission (FWC). (2021). *Florida Cooperative Land Cover Map*, (Version 3.5)[Data set]. State of Florida. <https://myfwc.com/research/gis/regional-projects/cooperative-land-cover>
- Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI). (2010). *Guide to the Natural Communities of Florida – 2010 Edition*. Institute of Science and Public Affairs. Florida State University. <https://www.fnai.org/species-communities/natcom-guide>

8.2 Apalachicola NF Ecological Condition Model (2016)

Once the historic natural communities were spatially delineated for the Apalachicola NF, the next step was to assess the current (as of 2016) ecological conditions of the main longleaf pine associated natural communities- flatwoods, sandhills, wet savannas and upland pine. Other natural communities such as freshwater forested wetlands were not evaluated because they are not actively managed by the USFS at this time. Desired or reference conditions for each longleaf natural community are defined in the NFs in Florida Land and Resource Management Plan (NFF, 1999) and in FNAI's Guide to Natural Communities of Florida (FNAI, 2010). Important indicators of condition were based on reference natural communities (FNAI, 2009), the RCW Recovery Plan (USFWS, 2003) and the expert opinion of scientists and land managers familiar with the area. A total of 5 overall ecological condition classes were defined (Table 8.2.1 and Figure 8.2.1).

Table 8.2.1. General ecological condition classes defined for the Apalachicola National Forest (adapted from Trager et al. 2018).

Condition Class	Description
1- Excellent	Meets all criteria for desired/reference conditions and only requires continuation of current management (usually frequent prescribed fire)
2- Good	Meets most criteria for desired conditions, usually only deviating slightly in age of canopy trees. Likely only requires continuation of current management for maintenance and eventual maturation of trees.
3- Fair	Historical community usually apparent from current conditions, but deviates from desired vegetation structure for multiple strata. Likely requires some management activities to improve such as timber thinning or midstory treatments in addition to frequent prescribed fire.
4- Poor	Historical community may not be apparent due to major deviation from desired vegetation structure and composition, though some evidence of natural vegetation is usually visible. Requires intensive management for improvement.
5- Very Poor	Historical community usually not apparent from current vegetation due to dramatic alteration of site such as offsite trees, hydrological alteration (e.g., ditches/bedding), long-term fire suppression or catastrophic wildfire. These sites require several intensive management activities for improvement.

Field data were collected in more than 400 rapid ecological assessment plots, which were widely distributed across the Apalachicola NF and covered a range of current ecological conditions. At each plot, information related to the structure and composition of the canopy, midstory, and understory (shrub and groundcover) layer was recorded, and expert ecological condition scores were assigned for each strata as well as for the overall plot condition. Plot locations were not random but were determined by evaluating a range of factors across the forest and by questions generated during the preliminary natural community mapping efforts. As an example, plots were placed in some areas that were identified as open canopy sandhill natural communities in the 1937 aerial photography but are currently dominated by hardwoods. These plots were used to collect field data from sandhills presumed to be in poor or very poor condition. This process both field-validated the natural community dataset (Section 8.1) and provided information that could be used to derive and calibrate ecological condition scores across a wide range of conditions.

Figure 8.2.1. Pictorial representation of general ecological condition classes defined for the Apalachicola National Forest (Images by J. Drake and Amy Jenkins, 2012).

To create a spatially-explicit model of current ecological conditions, several spatial input datasets were utilized, including USFS corporate forest stand data to derive stand age and dominant tree species layers. Corporate datasets for prescribed fire history were explored but were found not appropriate for this application because fires were mapped at the burn unit level (average size of 2,856 acres). Instead, NFs in Florida staff and interns used the differenced normalized burn ratio approach (Robertson & Picotte, 2011) to map the extent and severity of fires (prescribed and wildfires) over a 15-year period (1997 to 2012) for the Apalachicola NF.

Several input layers were also derived from 2007 to 2011 airborne lidar data using the USFS FUSION software (McGaughey, 2022), including canopy height percentiles, canopy cover, and relative shrub density. Basal area was also estimated by developing a multiple linear regression relationship between field estimated basal area (from a 10-factor prism in variable width timber cruise plots) and lidar metrics. Input layers were aggregated at a spatial scale of approximately 0.52 acres (150 ft cell size) and were cross walked first into individual condition scores based on published and expert knowledge from USFS, FNAI, and partners. For example, condition scores for flatwoods and sandhills canopy basal area were based on the Red-cockaded Woodpecker (RCW) Recovery Plan (USFWS, 2003). In other cases, the field expert assigned strata condition scores from a subset of the approximately 400 field plots collected for this project were used to derive breakpoints between different condition scores, particularly for lidar-derived metrics (e.g., relative density), which do not have a direct equivalent in field measurements.

Individual condition scores cross-walked from each input layer were then combined using a weighted sum approach to derive summary condition scores for canopy, midstory, and understory strata. The weights assigned to each were adjusted based on how well they were related to the subset of the corresponding field scores (e.g., if the fit was not good between model canopy condition scores and field estimated canopy condition scores, some weights were adjusted accordingly). The mean overall ECM score was then just a simple average of the weighted condition scores for canopy, midstory, and shrub/groundcover conditions. The final overall ECM scores for the Apalachicola NF are shown in Figure 8.2.2 and are summarized for each historic natural community in Table 8.2.2.

Figure 8.2.2. Comprehensive 2016 Ecological Condition Model (ECM) tier scores for the Apalachicola NF from 1 = Excellent to 5= Very Poor condition.

Table 8.2.2. Total acres and percent of total of each ecological condition class within historic longleaf pine natural communities on the Apalachicola NF (adapted from Trager et al. 2018).

Tier	Flatwoods (%)	Sandhill (%)	Wet Prairie (%)	Upland Pine (%)	All (%)
1- Excellent	110 (<1)	18 (<1)	1,823 (5)	3 (<1)	1,954 (<1)
2- Good	57,709 (23)	14,262 (26)	4,871 (14)	341 (20)	77,183 (23)
3- Fair	69,623 (28)	19,699 (36)	7,461 (22)	357 (21)	97,140 (28)
4- Poor	52,734 (21)	12,386 (22)	8,123 (24)	328 (20)	73,571 (22)
5- Very Poor	69,499 (28)	8,860 (16)	12,222 (35)	651 (39)	91,232 (27)
(Total)	249,675	55,225	34,500	1,680	341,080

The 2016 ecological condition model (ECM) developed for the Apalachicola NF has been a very helpful tool to illustrate both opportunities and challenges. For example, the model results closely align with red-cockaded woodpecker (RCW) habitat preference at multiple spatial scales (Trager et al. 2018) and show where silvicultural treatments (e.g., midstory oak treatments in sandhills) can improve RCW habitat conditions. The historic natural community and ECM process also reveal that there are over 5 times more wet prairies than were previously mapped in USFS databases, however the majority (59%) of these areas are in poor or very poor condition because they have either been bedded and planted with slash pine or have been encroached by dense woody shrubs due to lack of prescribed fire (Trager et al. 2018). Because wet prairies provide habitat for many listed and rare plant species, the USFS have used these results to target several hundred acres of historic wet prairies for ecological restoration activities.

There are some important issues and caveats to consider for the 2016 Apalachicola NF ECM. One of the main limitations of this approach for estimating the current ecological conditions is that it relies heavily on forest stand data from a USFS corporate database (“FSVeg”). The stand data (attributes and stand spatial boundaries) in this corporate database are typically only updated when timber and silviculture activities are being analyzed and planned in a project area. Thus, although there are over 340,000 acres of potential longleaf pine habitat on the Apalachicola NF, database updates may be made to several hundred to a few thousand acres (<1%) in any given year. USFS corporate stand data also do not currently contain information related to different strata such as shrubs and groundcover where most of the biodiversity is found in these natural communities. Finally, the corporate stand data are only available for National Forest System lands, thus prohibiting expansion of the ECM to nearby public lands (for example the surrounding public lands in the inset of Figure 8.1.1.) or private lands.

To overcome these limitations, the National Forests in Florida leveraged this RESTORE project to create partnerships such as the Center for Spatial Ecology and Restoration (CSER, Section 2.3) to develop new, open source, efficient, repeatable, and transferable workflows to create key forest structural metrics (St. Peter et al. 2021, Section 4.2) as well as workflows to translate these into ecological condition scores across all ARRI lands (Section 4.3). These workflows can also be applied to different datasets (e.g., airborne or drone borne lidar), which will facilitate the monitoring efforts in ARRI. When combined with potential water yield benefits, these workflows and datasets provide invaluable information to prioritize forest management activities (Section 5).

References

- Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI). (2009). *Reference natural communities geodatabase*. Institute of Science and Public Affairs. Florida State University. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from <https://www.fnai.org/species-communities/reference-communities>
- Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI). (2010). *Guide to the Natural Communities of Florida – 2010 Edition*. Institute of Science and Public Affairs. Florida State University. <https://www.fnai.org/species-communities/natcom-guide>
- McGaughey, R. (2022, May 19). *FUSION/LDV: Software for LiDAR Data Analysis and Visualization (v4.40)*. U.S. Forest Service. U.S. Department of Agriculture. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from <http://forsys.sefs.uw.edu/fusion/fusionlatest.html>
- Picotte, J. J., & Robertson, K. M. (2011). Validation of remote sensing of burn severity in south-eastern US ecosystems. *International Journal of Wildland Fire* 20(3), 453–464. <https://doi.org/10.1071/WF10013>
- St. Peter, J. R., Drake, J., Medley, P., & Ibeanusi, V. (2021). Forest Structural Estimates Derived Using a Practical, Open-Source Lidar-Processing Workflow. *Remote Sensing* 13(23), 4763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13234763>
- Trager, M., Drake, J., Jenkins, A., & Petrick, C. (2018). Mapping and modeling ecological conditions of longleaf pine habitats in the Apalachicola National Forest. *Journal of Forestry*, 116(3), 304-311. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jofore/fvx017>
- U.S. Forest Service. (1999). *Land and Resource Management Plan for the National Forests in Florida*. U.S. Department of Agriculture <https://www.fs.usda.gov/detail/florida/landmanagement/planning/?cid=stelprdb5269793>
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. (2003). *Recovery plan for the red-cockaded woodpecker (Picoides borealis): Second revision*. US Department of the Interior. <https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML1119/ML111920406.pdf>

8.3 The Longleaf Mapping Project

Before Tate's Hell Strategy 1 commenced, research collaborations took place among staff from the USFS National Forests in Florida (NFF), Rocky Mountain Research Station (RMRS), and Florida Natural Areas Inventory (FNAI) on a significant initiative known as the Longleaf Mapping Project (LMP). This multi-year endeavor was initially funded by the National Fish and Wildlife Foundation through a grant to the Longleaf Alliance (Grant ID #50661), the U.S. Forest Service, State and Private Forestry, RMRS, and NFF. Additional support for the development of the RMRS Raster Utility was provided by the Agriculture and Food Research Initiative Competitive Grant 2013-68005-21298 from the USDA National Institute of Food and Agriculture through the Bioenergy Alliance Network of the Rockies (BANR).

The overarching goal of the LMP was to find ways to accurately locate and map longleaf pine stands across nearly 35 million acres of southern pine forest habitat in Alabama, Florida, and Georgia. The study emphasized the use of readily-available, area-wide, high-resolution imagery (including Landsat, NAIP, and Sentinel) and extensive field plot data to enhance the accuracy of the analysis. The methods used in the first part of this study relate summarized FIA field plot data to spectral and textural metrics derived from imagery in four regions of the Southeastern U.S. Specifically, this research presented a remote sensing-based methodology to estimate species composition, basal area and stand tree density for pine and hardwood tree species, and landcover composition at the spatial resolution of a Forest Inventory Analysis (FIA) program plot (78 m by 70 m). Details and outcomes of this initiative are described in multiple peer-reviewed publications, general technical reports, primary datasets and derivatives, and tutorials (Hogland & Anderson, 2015, 2017; Hogland et al., 2017a, 2017b, 2018a, 2018b, 2018c; St. Peter et al., 2018). To facilitate this research, the team employed customized spatial tools and

workflows that were specifically developed to leverage function modeling and parallel processing. These tools and techniques facilitated the tabular, spatial, and statistical analyses necessary to quantify forest structural metrics across vast landscapes. Ultimately, this approach allowed for the characterization and mapping of longleaf pine habitats in a meaningful way, providing valuable information for informed decision-making related to forest management, restoration, and conservation activities.

In 2015, prior to the LMP, Hogland and Anderson introduced an essential research element that has been incorporated into their spatial analysis tools, both in this study and in subsequent projects like THS1 (Hogland & Anderson, 2015, 2017). This concept, known as function modeling, significantly reduces input/output operations when writing to logical disks during spatial data processing. As a result, complex calculations are performed, and sizable derivatives are quickly generated without the need for expensive high-performance computing resources. This advancement has empowered RMRS and CSER staff to work locally and in cloud-computing environments with landscape-scale high spatial resolution datasets, efficiently producing large raster derivatives. Thanks in part to this breakthrough, collaborators have successfully inventoried extensive tracts of southern pine forests, particularly longleaf pine stands, in five³ Significant Geographic Areas (SGAs) across the Southeastern U.S. (Figure 8.3.1). Subsequently, a similar methodology was employed to assess the Apalachicola Region of Florida in the Tate's Hell Strategy 1 RESTORE Project that utilized lidar data instead of imagery. This approach has proven to be highly effective, enabling efficient analysis and characterization of the region's forested landscapes.

Figure 8.3.1. Longleaf Mapping Project (LMP) Significant Geographic Areas (SGAs) utilized as operating zones by America's Longleaf Restoration Initiative (ALRI) Local Implementation Teams (LITs).

³ A follow-up project to the LMP included a similar study to capture forest metrics across the Fort Stewart/Altamaha Longleaf Conservation Partnership SGA north of the Osceola NF – Okefenokee NWR SGA. The Fort Stewart/Altamaha Local Implementation Team (LIT) operational area covers much of the Georgia coast and comprises about 5 million acres⁴.

The RMRS Raster Utility developed by Dr. John Hogland[‡] and used in the LMP study originated from a 2010 collaboration between USFS RMRS scientists and Bureau of Land Management personnel. The goal was to quantify landscape-scale above-ground biomass and biomass flows resulting from restoration activities and fuel reduction treatments on the Uncompahgre Plateau in western Colorado. This scalable software library of ingenious spatial tools was initially designed around the Environmental Systems Research Institute (ESRI[‡]) ArcGIS software ecosystem. Since its inception, the raster toolkit has undergone major revisions. The latest iteration can now be found on GitHub as a Python package[‡] that leverages the open-source JupyterLab[‡] development environment for notebooks, code, and data. The current version introduces novel spatial, statistical, and machine learning concepts, all integrated into an easy-to-use Python-based API. These open-source tools offer invaluable benefits, notably in their ability to significantly reduce processing times and save disk storage space when analyzing large spatial datasets. This is particularly vital in situations where high-performance computing resources are unavailable.

To accurately assess southeastern forested landscapes and evaluate the quality of raster surfaces produced in the LMP, researchers utilized the Southern Open Pine (SOP) Field Protocol, which can be adjusted to independently evaluate mapped outputs. The integrated modeling tools in the RMRS Raster Utility[‡] (Hogland & Anderson, 2015, 2017) facilitated the creation of a raster geodatabase that aligned with existing tabular, vector, and raster databases from Auburn University, The Longleaf Alliance, and FNAI. A project working group, composed of key individuals, was also established to ensure database standardization and transferability, and provide feedback on various aspects of the project, anticipating the needs of America's Longleaf Restoration Initiative (ALRI) Local Implementation Teams (LITs) who function as on-the-ground restoration operation coordinators in unique zones of the Southeast known as Significant Geographic Areas (SGAs). Detailed project deliverables included:

- A geodatabase that seamlessly integrates with existing longleaf pine habitat resources.
- A model to acquire and work with FIA program data in SGAs.
- Documented methodologies used to estimate forest characteristics from nationally available data.
- Field protocols to qualitatively evaluate remotely sensed ALRI LLP maintenance condition classes.
- Spatially explicit fine-resolution raster surfaces estimating forest structural characteristics for multiple coniferous and deciduous species across five southeastern SGAs.
- Demonstrable examples showing how deliverables can be used to: 1) develop classification rules to crosswalk raster surfaces to longleaf pine condition classes, 2) quantify the extent and condition of LLP ecosystems, 3) track and prioritize a range of restoration activities, 4) optimize restoration efforts for multiple benefits of LLP ecosystems, including wildlife habitat, and 5) integrate disparate databases, workflows, and datasets.
- A final report, multiple webinars and in-person presentations to deliver project results, along with documentation explaining the products and their associated accuracies, precision, and utility.
- A feasibility assessment template and tool for evaluating an organization's capacity and capability to meet technical requirements of the methodology.
- A proposal to apply LMP methodologies and data to other SGAs across the range.

Following the approval of a Material Transfer Agreement with the U.S. Forest Service Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) Program and RMRS researchers, FIA field plot data with true plot locations were used for the LMP study and related to fine resolution (1 m²) National Agricultural Imagery Program (NAIP) imagery. Four band NAIP imagery (red, green, blue and near infrared) was used to create predictor variables for each 1 m² image pixel as if it was the center of a 78x70 meter FIA plot. These predictor variables consisted of digital numeric values summarized by mean, standard deviation, and

gray level co-occurrence matrix for each of the 4 NAIP bands. The variables were extracted at the FIA plot points and plot attributes were used as response variables to create models of forest structural metrics. Seven models were built for each state covering the extent of the 4 SGAs and resulting in a total of 21 unique models. Three of these models were developed using a Softmax neural network to estimate class probabilities, including dominant tree type (DomType), tree regeneration dominance (Regen), and longleaf pine dominance (LongDom). Four other models created for each state were random forest regression trees of basal area per acre, trees per acre for pine trees, and all tree species.

Together, these models efficiently produced raster datasets for the forest metrics at 1 m² spatial resolution across the entire study area (4 SGAs), and later for a modified study covering the Fort Stewart/Altamaha SGA in Georgia. Raster grid files were provided to LIT coordinators, conservationists, and stakeholders for all SGAs, and specifically included pine species basal area per acre (BAA), hardwood species BAA, pine trees per acre (TPA), hardwood TPA, dominant forest type classification, probability of an area being composed primarily of regeneration, probability of longleaf pine presence in an area, and pine and hardwood species presence/absence raster datasets. All of these raster surfaces were created using machine learning relationships between the USFS FIA plot data (2010-2015) and eventually normalized using Landsat imagery (2013-2015) with the explicit purpose to help accurately quantify existing conditions and prioritize restoration efforts across the southeastern LLP forested ecosystems.

Along with the forest structural metric raster datasets, a novel probabilistic landcover classification was also produced. This work is detailed in St. Peter et al., 2018 and summarized in Section 8.4. of this document. To provide clarity, it is important to note that while the LMP results showed considerable promise, they also revealed more errors in the forest metric models than anticipated. This is illustrated in Tables 8.3.1 and 8.3.2 below. Areas where longleaf pine was the dominant tree species were successfully classified; however, it was not possible to accurately quantify areas where LLP was present but was not the dominant canopy species (other than a probability). This prompted us to change our course of action for THS1 and subsequent research. From these results we concluded that two main sources of variability had to be addressed to further reduce output errors. Specifically, the sources of variability were related to the FIA sampling protocol (see section 3.1) and the variable acquisition times of NAIP images that complicated the imagery mosaicking process (Hogland et al., 2018c).

Table 8.3.1. Soft-max neural net fit statistics for DomType, LongDom and Regen models. Modified from Hogland et al., 2018a.

Model	State	Average Error (Bagged)	Most Likely Class Map Accuracy (Bagged)
DomType	Alabama	23% (35%)	76% (73%)
	Georgia	20% (34%)	76% (70%)
	Florida	23% (35%)	74% (73%)
Regen	Alabama	10% (11%)	94% (94%)
	Georgia	16% (17%)	89% (89%)
	Florida	11% (11%)	94% (94%)
LongDom	Alabama	13% (13%)	92% (92%)
	Georgia	6% (7%)	96% (95%)
	Florida	12% (12%)	92% (92%)

Table 8.3.2. Random Forest model, fit statistics for BAA and TPA, and standard deviation of FIA plots. Modified from Hogland et al., 2018a.

State	Model	Train RMSE	OOB RMSE	Std. Dev.
Alabama	Pine BAA	9.66	28.03	35.14
	Pine TPA	25.34	72.35	89.87
	All BAA	12.46	36.51	52.69
	All TPA	25.21	71.79	99.05
Georgia	Pine BAA	7.95	23.17	30.29
	Pine TPA	18.86	54.8	67.23
	All BAA	13.62	40.2	52.86
	All TPA	24.98	72.36	93.59
Florida	Pine BAA	8.00	23.38	31.37
	Pine TPA	20.53	59.55	82.27
	All BAA	15.82	46.12	58.91
	All TPA	27.17	77.87	103.60

These seven raster datasets, containing detailed forest structural metrics, along with the probabilistic landcover classification summarized in Section 8.4, provided consistent and standard spatial data reference points for local longleaf pine implementation teams and resource managers to help make restoration decisions based on priorities revealed from the LMP raster outputs. To help implement this work and provide examples of the various applications of these data, tutorials were created and are available online[‡]. The LMP tutorials focused on how to identify open pine areas that are structurally similar to high quality longleaf pine stands using the previously describes RMRS Raster Utility batch processing functions. A tutorial to help identify and prioritize longleaf pine restoration targets for improving red-cockaded woodpecker (*Dryobates borealis*) habitat was also produced and demonstrated to LIT restoration specialists. Two additional tutorials were focused on demonstrating how to use spatial tools to modify and/or create forest metric raster products such as image-based landcover classifications and basal area (BAA) estimates.

Following the LMP study that covered the initial 4 SGAs, a Fort Stewart/Altamaha Longleaf Conservation Partnership follow-up study, detailed in Hogland et al., 2019, tackled a key source of variability from the initial LMP methods by using coarser Landsat 8 imagery data to bring finer resolution NAIP imagery to a common radiometric scale using aggregate no-change (ANR) regression (Figures 8.3.2 and 8.3.3) by leveraging prior research of Hogland, 2005. Additional workflow improvements incorporated a hurdle model, a statistical technique that deals with random variables with zero or positive values, to enhance BAA and TPA models. Also, three phenological periods (growing, dormant, and leaf-off seasons) were added to accommodate the enhanced temporal resolution of the Landsat 8 imagery. The hurdle model employed dominance type models to exclude cells without the target tree species, enabling the tree species models to be trained and predict only areas where their target species were present. The exclusion of zero inflation, which had previously compromised the accuracy of linear models, resulted in improved predictive outcomes. The processing methods and normalizing phenological periods also played a significant role in refining the models which were subsequently utilized by CSER staff to assess forest damage following Hurricane Michael, as described in Section 4.1,

and later in multiple THS1 offshoots that employed airborne lidar data as a game-changing enhancement.

Figure 8.3.2. Location, date, path/row, and mosaicking order of Landsat 8 imagery used in the Fort Stewart/Altamaha Longleaf Conservation Partnership follow-up study. Path/row 17/38 was used as the reference scene to relatively normalize scenes within a given phenology. The order in which images for a given phenology were mosaicked are displayed in parentheses after path/row designation in the lefthand image above (from Hogland et al., 2019).

Figure 8.3.3. Before aggregate no-change regression (ANR) normalization (**left**) and after ANR normalization (**right**) of Landsat 8 scenes for Leaf off, Growing and Dormant phenologies. Bands 6, 5 and 4 are displayed here for the extent of the Fort Stewart study area (orange outline) as red, green, and blue, color composites with a 2.5 standard deviation color stretch for each four scene mosaic (from Hogland et al., 2019).

The modeled results from the Fort Stewart/Altamaha Longleaf Conservation Partnership follow-up study closely aligned with the seven forest structural metric raster outputs produced in the LMP study. However, the accuracy of the results significantly improved due to the incorporation of the hurdle model and image normalization techniques (Table 8.3.3). To accommodate these enhancements, additional software functions were integrated into the RMRS Raster Utility and made available to Fort Stewart/Altamaha Local Implementation Teams (LITs). Furthermore, tutorials were developed to demonstrate how the raster outputs could be applied to characterize gopher tortoise (*Gopherus polyphemus*) habitat conditions across the SGA. This information is accessible online[‡].

Besides providing valuable information on longleaf pine forest health and condition to restoration organizations in the Southeastern U.S., we equipped them with custom tools and conducted training to effectively prioritize and direct restoration efforts. This multi-year initiative yielded numerous large and innovative datasets, depicting forest structural characteristics across tens of millions of acres without the use of high-performance computing resources. Additionally, it resulted in multiple peer-

reviewed publications, the development of a valid field protocol for evaluating LLP condition class, four training webinars, and four packaged tutorials with accompanying data and examples that set the stage for THS1. While this study effectively addressed the primary sources of model error identified in the LMP study, the FIA field plot data, particularly related to the FIA plot design, remained as a primary source of error. This issue was subsequently mitigated through the design of RESTORE field plots which are more ideally suited to be related to imagery and lidar data, as detailed in Section 3.1 of this document.

Table 8.3.3. Model name, type, sample size and fit statistics for each model in the Ft. Stewart study. From Hogland et al., 2019. “N_” refers to needle-leaved trees, “B_” refers to broad-leaved trees. “_Leaf” refers to presence. BAH= Basal Area per Hectare, TPH= trees per hectare.

Model Name	Type	Sample Size	AIC ¹ /R ²	Deviance ¹ /RSE	P-Value ²
DomType	Softmax	762	878.644	794.644	<0.001
N_Leaf	Softmax	682	460.150	446.150	<0.001
B_Leaf	Softmax	682	418.850	408.850	<0.001
L_Leaf	Softmax	682	408.600	396.600	<0.001
Regen	Softmax	682	273.940	257.940	<0.001
N_BAH	Linear	530	0.521	0.949	<0.001
N_TPH	Linear	530	0.467	0.981	<0.001
B_BAH	Linear	569	0.574	1.081	<0.001
B_TPH	Linear	569	0.266	1.075	<0.001

¹ AIC and Deviance fit statistics apply to Softmax models, while coefficient of determination (R²) and residual standard error (RSE) of transformed values apply to linear models. ² P-values were calculated for chi-squared and F distributions for Softmax and linear modeling techniques, respectively.

In conclusion, it is essential to recognize the immense significance of the Longleaf Mapping Project and the groundbreaking research conducted by Drs. John Hogland and Nate Anderson of the USFS Rocky Mountain Research Station. Their work has played a pivotal role in advancing the predictive capabilities of landscape-scale remote sensing not only in Tate's Hell Strategy 1 but also in the subsequent RESTORE-funded Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI). Since the completion of the Longleaf Mapping Project, its research techniques have been repeatedly utilized and now form the foundation for more recent and precise iterations of the methodology used to produce landscape-scale remote forest structural characterizations. These newer techniques involve airborne and drone-borne lidar, combined with spatial-data-friendly plot designs derived from the original studies.

Furthermore, we are immensely grateful to the visionary sponsoring organizations, including the Longleaf Alliance and the National Fish and Wildlife Foundation (NFWF), whose generous support facilitated the harnessing of these cutting-edge geospatial analytical capabilities. Their timely funding of the Longleaf Mapping Project has proven invaluable to this evolutionary process. These advancements have grown increasingly critical as technology continues to advance at a rapid pace, and conservation efforts extend beyond large publicly-owned tracts to encompass private lands, which make up a substantial portion of the southeastern longleaf pine forest landscape.

References

Hogland, J. (2005). Creating Spatial Probability Distributions for Longleaf Pine Ecosystems across East Mississippi, Alabama, The Panhandle of Florida and West Georgia. [Master's thesis, Auburn University]. AUETD. <http://etd.auburn.edu/handle/10415/603>

- Hogland, J. S., & Anderson, N. M. (2015). Estimating FIA plot characteristics using NAIP imagery, function modeling, and the RMRS Raster Utility coding library. In S. M. Stanton & G. A. Christensen (Eds.), *Pushing boundaries: new directions in inventory techniques and applications: Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) symposium 2015* (pp. 340-344). Gen. Tech. Rep. PNW-GTR-931. Portland, OR: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Pacific Northwest Research Station. <https://www.fs.usda.gov/research/treesearch/50440>
- Hogland, J., & Anderson, N. (2017). Function Modeling Improves the Efficiency of Spatial Modeling Using Big Data from Remote Sensing. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 1(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc1010003>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., Gilbert, J., Abernathy, R., Knight, G., Knight, A. (2017a). Cost-Effective Mapping of Longleaf Extent and Condition using NAIP Imagery and FIA Data: A Pilot Project in the Heart of the Longleaf Range. Longleaf Pine Mapping and Monitoring Final Report to delivered to the National Fish & Wildlife Foundation and Longleaf Alliance, 33pp.
- Hogland, J. S., St. Peter, J. R., & Anderson, N. M. (2017b). Raster surfaces created from the cost-effective mapping of longleaf extent and condition using NAIP imagery and FIA data project. <https://doi.org/10.2737/RDS-2017-0014>
- Hogland, J.S., Anderson, N., Affleck, D., St. Peter, J. (2018a). Using FIA Plot and Remotely Sensed Data to Map Longleaf Extent and Condition: Emphasizing High Resolution Outputs for Cross-ownership Planning, Monitoring, and Restoration. Ft. Stewart Longleaf Mapping Project Final Report delivered to the National Fish & Wildlife Foundation and Longleaf Alliance, 32pp.
- Hogland, J. S., St. Peter, J. R., & Anderson, N. M. (2018b). Raster surfaces created from the mapping of longleaf extent and condition using Landsat and FIA data project. Fort Collins, CO: Forest Service Research Data Archive. <https://doi.org/10.2737/RDS-2018-0039>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., St. Peter, J., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2018c). Mapping Forest Characteristics at Fine Resolution across Large Landscapes of the Southeastern United States Using NAIP Imagery and FIA Field Plot Data. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 7(4), 140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi7040140>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., Affleck, D. L. R., & St. Peter, J. (2019). Using Forest Inventory Data with Landsat 8 Imagery to Map Longleaf Pine Forest Characteristics in Georgia, USA. *Remote Sensing*, 11(15), 1803. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs11151803>
- St. Peter, J. R., Hogland, J. S., Anderson, N. M., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2018). Fine resolution probabilistic land cover classification of landscapes in the southeastern United States. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 7(3), 107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi7030107>

8.4 Probabilistic Fine Resolution Landcover

A land cover classification is a standard remote sensing procedure that assigns specific land cover types (classes) to geographic areas based on the features covering the Earth's surface at those locations. This highly useful and adaptable data type, often presented as a raster image, provides valuable contextual information for remote sensing analyses used in Earth inventory, monitoring, and assessment research of various systems, either independently or in conjunction with other spatial analyses. A land cover classification typically categorizes features into different classes based on the spectral similarity of image pixels, where like pixels are grouped into classes such as forests, grasslands, wetlands, cultivated lands, urban areas, etc. This process is akin to how people naturally perceive and visually differentiate various elements in a landscape image.

As an extension of the Longleaf Mapping Project mentioned earlier, U.S. Forest Service scientists from the Rocky Mountain Research Station and National Forests in Florida collaborated to produce a broad-scale land cover classification spanning four Significant Geographic Areas (SGAs) associated with

America's Longleaf Restoration Initiative (ALRI) within Alabama, Florida, and Georgia (Figure 8.4.1). The aim was to help characterize approximately 29 million acres of southeastern longleaf pine forest habitat. While this procedure has a deep-rooted history in remote sensing, it has evolved significantly since the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) developed one of the first land use/land cover classifications systems specifically for use with remotely sensed imagery (Anderson et al., 1976). In this section, we describe an advanced process to create a landscape-scale, fine spatial resolution (1 m²) 13-band probabilistic (type likely to occur) land cover classification, which is further detailed in St. Peter et al., 2018. The employed methodology is quick and efficient and does not require specialized computing resources.

Figure 8.4.1. Four Significant Geographic Areas (SGA) included in the probabilistic land cover mapping effort shown with a grid of overlapping NAIP Digital Orthophoto Quarter Quadrangle (DOQQ) tiles. (St. Peter et al., 2018)

In this particular project, the imagery was obtained in 2015 through the National Agricultural Imagery Program (NAIP[†]), which falls under the administration of the Geospatial Enterprise Operations (GEO) Branch[†] of USDA's Farm Production and Conservation Business Center (FPAC-BC). The primary aim of the NAIP program is to acquire digital orthophotography and make it readily available to both governmental agencies and the general public. The 4-band color and near-infrared "leaf-on" imagery, with a spatial resolution of 1 m², serves as a fundamental layer in numerous GIS programs, and is also utilized as an analytical platform in this study. This raster product is available for all U.S. states and insular areas, offering the option to view it in color or near infrared. Since 2006, its absolute accuracy specification has been tied to true ground locations using control points, with a requirement that all tested well-defined points fall within 6 meters of true ground at a 95% confidence level. In 2016, the accuracy requirement was updated to 4 meters.

In this research, individual Softmax neural network models were applied to the NAIP imagery from each of the three states (AL, FL, GA) to generate the probabilistic raster datasets. The models were fed with inputs from 3,280 randomly sampled points, classified into 13 classes (Table 8.4.1) with the top six principal components from a principal component analysis of the NAIP digital number values.

Additionally, the models utilized the standard deviation (3x3) and horizontal contrast gray level co-occurrence matrix (3x3) of the digital number values from all four NAIP spectral bands. The Softmax neural network classification models achieved approximately 9% probability errors for each state, with most of the errors arising from visually similar classes of pine tree (crown red class) and deciduous tree (crown pink class).

Remarkably, the entire 28.8 million acre study area, encompassing 720 billion data cells, was processed in just 168 hours on a standard desktop computer. This accomplishment was facilitated in part by the RMRS Raster Utility Toolbar, an ArcGIS Desktop add-in developed at the Rocky Mountain Research Station (Hogland & Anderson, 2017). As mentioned, the RMRS Raster Utility incorporates function modeling, parallel processing, and a vast library of spatial functions to efficiently process large datasets. The generalized workflow is illustrated in Figure 8.4.2 below.

Table 8.4.1. Land cover classes and descriptions. (St. Peter et al., 2018)

Class	Description
Shadow	Shadows associated with an object
Pavement	Roads, driveways, and other paved objects
Building	Buildings
Crown Pink	Light green trees usually broadleaf
Crown Red	Pine trees
Shrub	Green shrub species
Green Grass	Growing grass
Water	Lakes, ponds, streams, and ocean
Burn	Recently burned charred areas
Bare Ground	Exposed soil or rock
Crown Gray	Gray tree canopy usually senesced broadleaf
Dry Grass	Dormant grass
Crops	Platted or irrigated areas that did not have exposed soil

Figure 8.4.2. Generalized workflow of probabilistic landcover classification method. (St. Peter et al., 2018)

The probabilistic Land Cover Classification (LCC) outputs generated from the described workflow are in the form of a multiband raster, where each band represents a different land cover class. Each cell of the raster output contains values for all land cover classes, indicating the probability of that cell

belonging to a specific land cover category. Traditionally, land cover classifications are discrete, which assign a single deterministic class (most likely class or MLC) to each raster cell or classified area. However, probabilistic classifications provide users with the probabilities for each classification and individual cell, preserving more information and enabling users to set their own thresholds if they prefer to create a discrete classification.

Probabilistic classifications offer advantages in terms of accurately representing the distribution of land cover classes across an area. Uncommon classes are not undercounted, and more common classes are not overcounted when summarizing data. Additionally, users can manipulate and display the class bands independently, allowing for more detailed visualizations. For example, Figure 8.4.3 shows a subsection of the pine tree class band with a color gradient representing the probabilities of each cell being categorized as a pine tree. Clear patterns of low probability cells, depicted in orange, emerge along roadways, around lakes and ponds, and in riparian zones. Furthermore, pine tree plantations are distinguishable by green to deep blue sections. Moreover, these outputs are easily converted into discrete classifications using a Most Likely Class (MLC) function. Once colored appropriately, this type of output closely resembles an aerial image, as shown in Figure 8.4.4. The fine spatial scale and comprehensive classification allow for more detail in the classified output. Such detail is not achievable with coarse-scale resolutions or ecological regime classifications, or when fewer categories are used. Overall, the use of probabilistic LCC outputs greatly enhances the accuracy and granularity of the land cover classification process.

Figure 8.4.3. A subsection of the pine tree (Crown Red) class raster taken from the Florida landcover classification raster dataset. The shading shows pixels values from low probability of being pine tree (orange) to high probability of being pine tree (green).

Figure 8.4.4. Example of a high-resolution (1 m²) land cover classification generated by applying a most likely class (MLC) rule to a 13 band probabilistic land cover classification. (St. Peter et al., 2018)

The outcomes of this work proved valuable in several subsequent analyses and projects conducted by CSER and its partners for the Tate's Hell Strategy 1 Project. They were employed as a spatial filter for roads in damage analyses related to Hurricane Michael and Hurricane Laura (Sections 4.1 and 8.5), as well as a reference for forested areas in those hurricane projects and other lidar modeling initiatives (Section 4.2). Additionally, the LCC product was used in habitat models for endangered species to quantify understory and shrub layers. The versatility of this product extends to applications in climate modeling (Feddemma et al., 2005), biodiversity monitoring (Skidmore et al., 2015), landscape change detection (Falcucci, Maiorano & Boitani, 2007), land use planning (Mahiny & Clark, 2012), timber harvesting (McRoberts & Tomppo, 2007), forest restoration (van Leeuwen, 2008), and fire risk mitigation (Koetz et al., 2008). Its broad potential demonstrates its significance in addressing various environmental and ecological challenges.

In conclusion, this initiative developed as an extension of the Longleaf Mapping Project, aimed to create an efficient and replicable workflow for a fine-resolution Land Cover Classification (LCC) product, overcoming the limitations of existing LCCs with coarse resolution, broadly-defined classes, and inflexible discreet classifications. This methodology and spatial toolsets produced a flexible LCC that can be applied across large areas using standard computer hardware, common open-source software, and publicly available imagery. The resulting products have been and can continue to be effectively utilized to address various management questions, prioritize restoration activities, and inform decision-making across the landscape (St. Peter et al., 2018).

References

- Anderson, J. R., Hardy, E. E., Roach, J. T., & Witmer, R. E. (1976). A Land Use and Land Cover Classification System for Use with Remote Sensor Data. Geological Survey Professional Paper No. 964. U.S. Government Printing Office, Washington DC, 28.
- Falcucci, A., Maiorano, L., & Boitani, L. (2007). Changes in land-use/land-cover patterns in Italy and their implications for biodiversity conservation. *Landscape Ecology*, 22, 617-631. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-006-9056-4>
- Feddema, J. J., Oleson, K. W., Bonan, G. B., Mearns, L. O., Buja, L. E., Meehl, G. A., & Washington, W. M. (2005). The Importance of Land-Cover Change in Simulating Future Climates. *Science*, 310, 1674-1678. <https://doi.org/10.5814/j.issn.1674-764x.2021.03.001>
- Hogland, J. S., & Anderson, N. M. (2015). Estimating FIA plot characteristics using NAIP imagery, function modeling, and the RMRS Raster Utility coding library. In S. M. Stanton & G. A. Christensen (Eds.), Pushing boundaries: new directions in inventory techniques and applications: Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) symposium 2015 (pp. 340-344). Gen. Tech. Rep. PNW-GTR-931. Portland, OR: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Pacific Northwest Research Station. <https://www.fs.usda.gov/research/treearch/50440>
- Hogland, J., & Anderson, N. (2017). Function Modeling Improves the Efficiency of Spatial Modeling Using Big Data from Remote Sensing. *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, 1(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bdcc1010003>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., Gilbert, J., Abernathy, R., Knight, G., Knight, A. (2017a). Cost-Effective Mapping of Longleaf Extent and Condition using NAIP Imagery and FIA Data: A Pilot Project in the Heart of the Longleaf Range. Longleaf Pine Mapping and Monitoring Final Report to delivered to the National Fish & Wildlife Foundation and Longleaf Alliance, 33pp.
- Hogland, J. S., St. Peter, J. R., & Anderson, N. M. (2017b). Raster surfaces created from the cost-effective mapping of longleaf extent and condition using NAIP imagery and FIA data project. <https://doi.org/10.2737/RDS-2017-0014>
- Hogland, J.S., Anderson, N., Affleck, D., St. Peter, J. (2018a). Using FIA Plot and Remotely Sensed Data to Map Longleaf Extent and Condition: Emphasizing High Resolution Outputs for Cross-ownership Planning, Monitoring, and Restoration. Ft. Stewart Longleaf Mapping Project Final Report delivered to the National Fish & Wildlife Foundation and Longleaf Alliance, 32pp.
- Hogland, J. S., St. Peter, J. R., & Anderson, N. M. (2018b). Raster surfaces created from the mapping of longleaf extent and condition using Landsat and FIA data project. Fort Collins, CO: Forest Service Research Data Archive. <https://doi.org/10.2737/RDS-2018-0039>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., St. Peter, J., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2018c). Mapping Forest Characteristics at Fine Resolution across Large Landscapes of the Southeastern United States Using NAIP Imagery and FIA Field Plot Data. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 7(4), 140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi7040140>
- Koetz, B., Morsdorf, F., van der Linden, S., Curt, T., Allgöwer, B. (2008). Multi-source land cover classification for forest fire management based on imaging spectrometry and LiDAR data. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 256, 263-271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2008.04.025>
- Mahiny, A. S., & Clarke, K. C. (2012). Guiding SLEUTH land-use/land-cover change modeling using multicriteria evaluation: towards dynamic sustainable land-use planning. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 39, 925-944. <https://doi.org/10.1068/b37092>
- McRoberts, R. E., & Tomppo, E. O. (2007). Remote sensing support for national forest inventories, *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 110, 412-419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2006.09.034>

- Skidmore, A. K., Pettoirelli, N., Coops, N. C., Geller, G. N., Hansen, M., Lucas, R., Mùcher, C. A., O'Connor, B., Paganini, M., Pereira, H. M., Schaepman, M. E., Turner, W., Wang, T., & Wegmann, M. (2015). Agree on biodiversity metrics to track from space. *Nature*, 523, 403-405. <https://doi.org/10.1038/523403a>
- St. Peter, J., Hogland, J., Anderson, N., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2018). Fine Resolution Probabilistic Land Cover Classification of Landscapes in the Southeastern United States. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 7(3), 107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi7030107>
- van Leeuwen, W. J. D. (2008). Monitoring the Effects of Forest Restoration Treatments on Post-Fire Vegetation Recovery with MODIS Multitemporal Data *Sensors*, 8, 2017-2042. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s8032017>

8.5 Transferable Rapid Hurricane (Windstorm) Timber Stand Damage Workflow

Forest damage assessment results from Hurricane Michael (Section 4.1) highlighted the need for rapid post-storm assessments using remote sensing imagery (St. Peter et al., 2020). To develop a method for swift and accurate assessments, the workflows needed to rely on the earliest available post-hurricane imagery, typically within a single phenological period, even if it might be cloudier than desired. To overcome these challenges, we drew from our expertise in probabilistic classifications and image normalization. We utilized these techniques to create precise masks for individual post-hurricane images and merged them to generate composite cloudless images using the available Sentinel-2 imagery after the hurricane (Sections 4.1, 8.6). The newly created rapid assessment workflow (shown in Figure 8.5.1) was put to the test during the 2020 Gulf Coast hurricane season when Hurricane Laura, a category 4 hurricane, made landfall near Cameron, Louisiana on August 27th, passing over the Kisatchie National Forest. Immediately following the hurricane, we swiftly applied the rapid assessment workflow, but due to the hurricane's impact zone, we had to rely on FIA plot data because RESTORE field plots (Section 3.1) were not within Hurricane Laura's impact zone. Although this led to some error within the basal area estimates, FIA plots had the advantage of being readily available thus making our workflow transferable to virtually any post-windstorm forested landscape.

In general, the steps to complete the assessment included: 1) acquire pre-hurricane imagery within the same phenological period as the post-hurricane Laura landscape (around late August to early September), 2) use imagery, along with 208 FIA plots around the Kisatchie National Forest, to create a general linear model of basal area per acre (BAA), 3) wait for Sentinel-2 satellites⁴ to pass over the study area post-landfall, and 4) download the post-hurricane images and examine them for cloudiness. The first Sentinel image was received on Sept. 7th, which was almost entirely cloudless, but only partially covering the study area. Subsequent passes with fewer cloud cover occurred on Sept. 10th and Sept. 15th (Figure 8.5.2). From these images, the latest of which was two and a half weeks post-landfall. CSER staff trained and applied a probabilistic classification using four categories that would be used as image masks. These categories included forest, non-forest, cloud, and (cloud) shadow (Figure 8.5.3).

⁴ The Copernicus Sentinel-2 satellite mission consists of two polar-orbiting satellites positioned in the same sun-synchronous orbit, with a phase difference of 180° between them. This configuration allows for a wide imaging swath width of 290 km (180.2 mi) and a high revisit time of approximately 10 days at the equator for one satellite, and 5 days for both satellites under cloud-free conditions. This results in a 2-3 day revisit time at mid-latitudes, and a 3-5 day revisit time over the Kisatchie National Forest during the time of this study. For other locations, pre-planning can be done to determine local revisit times which is essential for effective utilization of this method.

Figure 8.5.1. Flowchart of imagery preprocessing and modeling. Pre and Post refer to before and after hurricane landfall. The classification model employed a Softmax neural network with 4 categories, forest, non-forest, cloud, and (cloud) shadow (St. Peter et al., 2018.)

Figure 8.5.2. Sentinel-2 imagery for a single post-Hurricane Laura scene with dates. The four southernmost ranger districts of the Kisatchie National Forest are outlined. The path of Hurricane Laura is shown in red.

Figure 8.5.3. Classified imagery of a partial scene over the Kisatchie National Forest. Classified Sentinel-2 images are from September 10th (left) and 15th (right), 2020.

After obtaining partially cloud-free Sentinel-2 images following Hurricane Laura, a composite image of the post-hurricane forest was created by combining the available cloudy images. The basal area model developed earlier was then applied to this composite image. By subtracting this from the pre-hurricane basal area estimates, a basal area loss raster was generated. The loss raster was then categorized into four damage levels: light (0-5 BA ft²/acre), medium (5-20 BA ft²/acre), heavy (20-60 BA ft²/acre), and severe (5-20 BA ft²/acre) damage, as depicted in Figure 8.5.4. This process provided a forest damage estimate at a 10 m² spatial resolution for the entire landscape within 20 days of Hurricane Laura's landfall. Subsequently, on September 30th, Sentinel-2 satellites acquired cloudless images for the entire post-hurricane study area. We applied basal area and classification models to these cloudless images to make a comparison with prior rapid damage assessment results, also shown in Figure 8.5.4.

Figure 8.5.4. Damage assessments comparisons using combination “rapid assessment” imagery (left) composed of Sentinel-2 imagery from September 7th, 10th, and 15th, and a cloudless image from September 30th (right). Data gaps from masked clouds and shadows are evident in the rapid assessment results.

Figure 8.5.5 displays the damage assessment for the entire study area, which included 4 of the 5 ranger districts on the Kisatchie National Forest, i.e., the Calcasieu, Catahoula, Kisatchie, and Winn Districts. For Hurricane Michael, CSER used data from revisited RESTORE field plots for a comprehensive accuracy assessment of model results (Section 4.1). However, FIA plots were not revisited until much later. Instead, CSER staff obtained NOAA high-resolution imagery from some hurricane-impacted areas which facilitated an accuracy assessment. Comparing areas with different levels of fallen trees in the NOAA images with forest damage results provided a qualitative check on the accuracy of the forest damage assessment maps. The results demonstrated good agreement, as depicted in Figure 8.5.6.

A final report was submitted to the USFS Region 8 Resource Information Management staff which included all project outcomes and recommendations for establishing a rapid forest damage assessment system based on the knowledge gained from our work on the Hurricane Laura Project (Medley et al., 2020). This effort was later expanded to Project “Storm Cloud” funded by the USFS Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) Program[†] detailed in Section 8.6.

Figure 8.5.5. Forest damage estimates for the Kisatchie National Forest post-Hurricane Laura (2020).

Figure 8.5.6. NOAA images of forested areas following Hurricane Laura (left) overlaid with CSER basal area composite damage assessment layer (right). Visual analysis based on recent post-hurricane high-resolution drone imagery reinforced the accuracy estimate of the modeled outputs.

References

- Medley, P., Drake, J., St. Peter, J., Ibeanusi, V., Hogland, J., Broadbent, E., & Vernon, J. (2020). Pilot Project: Remote Sensing, Artificial Intelligence, and Cloud Computing for Natural Disaster Assessment, Monitoring and Restoration. Report to USFS Region 8 Resource Information Management Office. Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER), Florida A&M University.
- St. Peter, J., Hogland, J., Anderson, N., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2018). Fine Resolution Probabilistic Land Cover Classification of Landscapes in the Southeastern United States. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 7(3), 107. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi7030107>
- St. Peter, J., Anderson, C., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2020). Spatially Quantifying Forest Loss at Landscape-scale Following a Major Storm Event. *Remote Sensing*, 12(7), 1138. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/rs12071138>

8.6 Storm Cloud

As mentioned, the RESTORE funded THS1 Project has led to multiple ancillary and opportunistic endeavors for the U.S. Forest Service (USFS) and our partners. Through a Center for Spatial Ecology &

Restoration (CSER) partnership with the University of Florida’s Spatial Ecology & Conservation (SPEC) Lab[†], many projects have arisen including an expanded collaboration with the USFS Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) Program[†] called “Storm Cloud”. This project leverages several methods developed and described by USFS, CSER, and SPEC Lab researchers, which will ultimately help create a remote, post-disaster evaluation of forest damage using Sentinel-1 SAR[†], Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery, and combinations of both remote sensing datasets along with FIA field data (Broadbent et al., 2021; Hogland & Affleck 2019; Hogland, Anderson, Affleck, & St. Peter, 2019; Hogland, Anderson, St. Peter, Drake, & Medley, 2018; St. Peter, Drake, Medley, & Ibeanusi, 2021; St. Peter, Anderson, Drake, & Medley, 2020). Notably, Sentinel-1 SAR is not dependent on cloud-free observations which are very difficult to acquire in the early days post-storm. This approach along with newly developed techniques and workflows will help create, calibrate, and validate a rapid, cost-effective process to enable the quantification of forest ecological and economic damages within days of a destructive natural disaster event. By leveraging previous RESTORE-funded research that examined the damaging effects of Hurricane Michael (Figure 8.6.1 and Figure 8.6.2), the 2-year Storm Cloud Project addresses the need for rapid and accurate estimates of forest timber stand damage and ecosystem impacts following catastrophic events, particularly as it distresses community health and safety.

Figure 8.6.1. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration’s Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellites (GOES) image of Hurricane Michael Category 5 landfall event near Mexico Beach, Florida (Image from NOAA, 2019[†]).

Figure 8.6.2. Massive post-Hurricane Michael timber stand damage on the cooperatively-managed Juniper Creek Wildlife Management Area a.k.a. Chipola Tract of the Apalachicola National Forest near Clarksville, FL (Image extracted from ESRI World Imagery, ArcGIS Online Image Service, 2020).

To further this technology, UF SPEC Lab and CSER will analyze FIA plot data metrics within the Hurricane Michael damage zone in the Apalachicola Region of Florida prior to and following Hurricane Michael. Key indicators for wind damage, tree health, and resiliency will be identified and used to inform a model that includes wind lines, elevation models, and relevant landscape-scale datasets across the entire hurricane-impacted region. The model will then be assessed using post-hurricane Michael FIA field plots to produce a baseline damage assessment map. From this, an integrated workflow utilizing the initial wind line-based assessment, a subsequent SAR imagery-based assessment, and pre- and post-multiband imagery will be outlined following methods detailed in Medley et al., 2020. Ultimately, this project will strive towards rapid, finer spatial resolution damage assessments by refining and tuning the initial evaluation. The following three distinct but integrated project components will result in key findings to provide critical elements for each subsequent component:

1. Hurricane related structural and compositional changes in different forest type groups.
2. Hurricane damage assessment through FIA plot integration with wind lines to estimate storm impact of Hurricane Michael.
3. Interpolated storm damage using passive and active (SAR) satellite data fusion of FIA plots.

Moreover, this effort will provide proof-of-concept for the use of a Google Earth Engine (GEE) cloud-based approach, aka “Storm Cloud”, to rapidly identify, quantify, and map storm related damages on ecosystems through the integration of the static (one per FIA data collect) damage assessment maps from component 2. The results are a near-real-time (one week) forest damage using SAR remote sensing in GEE. The study area was defined based on the Hurricane Michael FIA Plots locations, covering states of Florida, Alabama, and Georgia (Figure 8.6.3).

Figure 8.6.3. Storm cloud Project study area.

While this project is ongoing, some preliminary results have been found in relation to the use of GEE to address project components two and three. After selecting variables from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 datasets, three change detection approaches were tested for hurricane damage classification following Hurricane Michael. Those methods consisted of differencing, subtracting two co-registered images on differing dates, and rationing, which showed to be a great option to the statistical properties of SAR images, and the normalized difference change detection (NDCD) procedure. Geographic Object-Based Image Analysis GEOBIA methods were used to perform the classification. In GEE, the GEOBIA method is a Simple Non-Iterative Clustering (SNIC) algorithm, for grouping pixels and identifying objects. Then a Random Forest algorithm was selected to perform the classification with a 10-fold cross validation.

The damage assessment maps varied based on the availability of new images. Hurricane Michael made landfall on October 10th, 2018, and the first post-hurricane observations of the study area taken by the Sentinel constellation of satellites was three days after landfall. Sentinel observations were added to the model as days from landfall were increased and images became available, and a new observation was made roughly every three days. With the addition of new imagery, the map's damage assessment accuracy improved, as measured by model accuracies and confusion matrices. Damage map accuracies ranged from 0.305 ± 0.032 (mean $\pm$ standard deviation) and 0.360 ± 0.036 for maps generated only from Sentinel-1 (SAR), from 0.404 ± 0.036 to 0.454 ± 0.037 from maps fed a combination of S-1 and S-2 data, and from 0.394 ± 0.038 to 0.437 ± 0.033 in maps using only S-2 variables (Figure 8.6.4). As the models moved farther from the date of landfall and more observations are included, average accuracies slightly improved starting at the 3rd post-hurricane date to the 30th day after landfall.

This project is still ongoing, but initial results are encouraging. These results show that creating a damage assessment model within GEE that uses Sentinel data can produce usable damage assessment maps rapidly following a major storm event. This GEE setup also allows damage assessment maps to be continuously updated and improved as more data become available.

Figure 8.6.4. Damage maps for the 10th day after the hurricane for scenarios using only S-1 imagery, combination of S-1 and S-2 and only S-2 images. Catastrophic damages are represented in red color, Severe damage in orange, Moderate in yellow, Light damage in green and No damage prediction in gray.

References

- Broadbent, E. N., Sharma, A., Drake, J., Medley, P., Almeyda Zambrano, A. M., St. Peter, J., & Schroeder, A. (2021). *Rapid assessment of forest damage and economic impacts using radar and optical remote sensing combined with Forest Inventory and Analysis (FIA) plot data: The Hurricane Michael case study – development of the “Storm Cloud” rapid remote damage assessment system*. Proposal to U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Forest Inventory & Analysis Program.
- Hogland, J., & Affleck, D. L., (2019). Mitigating the Impact of Field and Image Registration Errors through Spatial Aggregation. *Remote Sensing*, 11(3), 222. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11030222>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., Affleck, D., St. Peter, J., (2019). Using forest inventory data with Landsat 8 imagery to map longleaf pine forest characteristics in Georgia, USA. *Remote Sensing*, 11(15), 1803. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11151803>
- Hogland, J., Anderson, N., St. Peter, J., Drake, J., & Medley, P. (2018). Mapping Forest Characteristics at Fine Resolution across Large Landscapes of the Southeastern United States Using NAIP Imagery and FIA Field Plot Data. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 7(4), 140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi7040140>
- Medley, P., Drake, J., St. Peter, J., Ibeanusi, V., Hogland, J., Broadbent, E., & Vernon, J. (2020). Pilot Project: Remote Sensing, Artificial Intelligence, and Cloud Computing for Natural Disaster Assessment, Monitoring and Restoration. Report to USFS Region 8 Regional Information Management Office. Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER), Florida A&M University.
- National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). (2019, April 19). Hurricane Michael upgraded to a Category 5 at time of U.S. landfall: Post-storm analysis estimates sustained winds of 160 mph. *National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration Media Release*. <https://www.noaa.gov/media-release/hurricane-michael-upgraded-to-category-5-at-time-of-us-landfall>
- St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., & Ibeanusi, V. (2021). Forest Structural Estimates Derived Using a Practical, Open-Source Lidar-Processing Workflow. *Remote Sensing*, 13(23), 4763. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13234763>
- St. Peter, J., Anderson, C., Drake, J. & Medley, P., (2020). Spatially quantifying forest loss at landscape-scale following a major storm event. *Remote Sensing*, 12(7), 1138. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12071138>

8.7 UF Gatoreye Preliminary Drone-based Lidar Projects

Rapid Forest Damage Assessment using Drone-based Lidar

Immediately after Hurricane Michael, CSER began working closely with colleagues from the UF School of Forest Resources and Conservation (renamed to the UF School of Forest, Fisheries, and Geomatic Sciences) to explore cost-effective methods for mapping fine-scale forest damage and downed fuels from Hurricane Michael. This collaboration involved field assessments from UF silviculturists (Drs. Ajay Sharma and Jason Vogel) as well as drone-based surveys led by Dr. Eben Broadbent, Director of the UF Spatial Ecology and Conservation (SPEC) lab and PI of the UF GatorEye Unmanned Flying Laboratory which includes LiDAR, hyperspectral and thermal sensors. On November 15, 2018, an initial, “proof-of-concept” GatorEye flight demonstrated impressive capability for detecting fine scale hurricane damage (Figure 8.7.1). An existing partnership between the CSER and the USFS Rocky Mountain Research Station was thus expanded to further explore the utility of GatorEye for detecting forest damage from Hurricane Michael.

Figure 8.7.1. Downed trees from Hurricane Michael as detected by GatorEye lidar during proof-of-concept flight on the Apalachicola National Forest, Florida.

CSER staff used post hurricane high resolution aerial imagery from NOAA and Google, and rapid helicopter-based damage reports from Apalachicola NF staff to select 8 drone survey sites which covered a wide range of hurricane damage, natural community types, and hydrologic conditions. These sites also had existing (pre-hurricane) field plot data that could be leveraged for other research activities (Figure 8.7.2).

Damaged and downed trees were clearly visible in the UAS lidar point clouds (Figure 8.7.1), demonstrating the utility of this technology for rapid assessment of forest damage. This single-pass, rapid assessment UAV approach also produced accurate results when compared with airborne lidar

even up to wide lidar scan angles (Prata et al., 2020). Lidar point clouds and derived products such as canopy height models (CHMs) from UAV also correspond well with airborne lidar (Figure 8.7.3).

Figure 8.7.2 Location of eight initial GatorEye UAV-LiDAR study sites at the Apalachicola National Forest, Florida (From Prata et al., 2020).

Tree-level Digital Mensuration from Drone-based Lidar

Tree crown metrics provide essential information for forest management and are influenced by the environment and competition between plants. Field based inventory has historically been the only way to obtain crown information, however these surveys are time consuming and expensive. Active remote sensing approaches, like LiDAR, may be able to overcome these difficulties by providing tree level data quickly and relatively cheaply. Recently, drone-based LiDAR has demonstrated great potential of generating extremely dense (100s of returns per meter) point clouds which could be used to provide tree and crown level metrics.

To further investigate this possibility, CSER and the UF SPEC lab focused on the Ordway Swisher Forest Dynamics Plot[‡] near Melrose, Florida. This approximately 57-acre plot (~1575 ft x 1575 ft) is located in a sandhill ecosystem with predominantly longleaf pine and turkey oak canopy and is part of the ForestGEO global network of field plots led by the Smithsonian Institute. Throughout the entire plot, all trees over 0.4-inch diameter are mapped and recorded, with a total of 10,215 stems censused.

Figure 8.7.3. (A) GatorEye UAV-LiDAR post-hurricane Michael (low impact area) and (B) aircraft LiDAR pre hurricane CHM with trees detected. (A1, A2, B1, B2) Tree detection locations and crown delineation. (A3, A4, B3, B4) point clouds corresponding to each location.

Integration of the field inventory census and drone-based lidar data for tree segmentation and crown metric estimation was accomplished through a new automated workflow (Figure 8.7.4). Dozens of metrics are calculated for each tree crown, including crown length, crown width, and crown ratio (Figure 8.7.5). Developed using a series of R functions and tested extensively on Ordway Swisher Forest Dynamics Plot data, this workflow successfully produced stem maps with over 80% accuracy based solely on drone-based lidar data including identification of smaller understory trees. The results also revealed that longleaf pine and turkey oaks have different crown and stem diameter characteristics depending on competition from neighbors. Crown metrics such as volume, width, and radius, decrease as tree density increases, for the three scenarios of species dominance (Table 8.7.1). While a known principle in silviculture, the novel and compelling aspect here is the use of drone-based crown measurements for swift estimation of these tree structure variations. It may even be possible to remeasure tree crown metrics through time to determine how well they respond to silvicultural treatments (e.g., 3rd row thinning).

Figure 8.7.4. Tree level crown metrics estimation workflow in manuscript under preparation for peer review by Dr. Gabriel Prata, Dr. Dan Johnson (P.I. of Ordway Swisher Forest Dynamics Plot) and others from CSER and the UF SPEC Lab.

Figure 8.7.5. Illustration of tree crown metrics derived from final step of workflow in Figure 8.7.4.

Table 8.7.1. Differences in tree diameter and crown structure based on local neighborhood density.

	LOW-DENSITY			MEDIUM-DENSITY			HIGH-DENSITY		
	PIPA	QULA	MIX	PIPA	QULA	MIX	PIPA	QULA	MIX
dbh (m)	23.48	16.83	20.46	17.69	15.04	15.70	15.23	13.40	13.32
Crown Volume (m3)	49.54	29.23	38.10	23.36	19.30	20.09	13.05	15.38	12.05
Crown width (m)	5.97	4.75	5.33	4.42	4.19	4.16	3.71	4.02	3.65
Crown length (m)	8.90	7.54	8.37	8.61	7.39	7.73	8.35	7.57	7.49
Crown projected area (m2)	24.95	16.26	19.69	13.12	11.57	11.66	8.63	10.30	8.31
Crown radius (m)	2.51	2.00	2.24	1.84	1.74	1.72	1.53	1.65	1.49

References

Prata, G., Broadbent, E. N., Almeida, D., St. Peter, J., Drake, J., Medley, P., Dalla Corte, A. P., Vogel, J., Sharma, A., Silva, C. A., Zambrano, A., Valbuena, R., & Wilkinson, B. (2020). Single-pass UAV-borne GatorEye LiDAR sampling as a rapid assessment method for surveying forest structure. Remote Sensing, 12(24), 4111. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12244111>.

8.8 Partnership for Remote Inventory Status and Management (PRISM)

Remote sensing technologies are invaluable digital mensuration, analysis, and predictive tools with many applicable uses for the USDA Forest Service and other land management organizations. That said, progress towards full development of this technology has often been limited by high costs, long data processing times, glacial product delivery times, or even the lack of suitable technology capable of

quickly collecting enough seamless data to enable high resolution (<1-meter) temporal spatial analyses over large landscapes, such as entire national forests or regions. Encouragingly, the past 5 plus years have seen exponential growth and development in multiple related industries that helps solve difficult technological challenges such as 1) novel, micro- and nano-structured materials that helped launch lightweight, powerful and capable unmanned aerial systems and sensors as data collection devices and platforms, 2) advanced, small form factor, high-resolution, and low-power usage optical sensors with new frequency bands including terahertz (THz) radiation, 3) readily accessible, flexible, and affordable high-performance computing systems and cloud computing platforms for workgroups, 4) low cost, large data storage arrays and flash memory, 5) significant advances in image processing and analysis software, and 6) giant strides in the field of artificial intelligence that can now be leveraged for repetitive processes previously relegated to humans. All these elements combined now position large-area drone-borne and rapidly deployable terrestrial data capture capabilities and relevant advanced remote sensing analyses within reach as a reliable, long-term, operational resource to help redefine decades-old forest mensuration techniques. The data and derivatives that come from these quick and resilient data collection platforms and processing systems are often vast, rich, dense, translational⁵, and transformable⁶.

Since its inception, the partnership that created the Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER), has afforded unique opportunities to build upon the productive relationships established between the U.S. Forest Service and academic partners at Florida A&M University (FAMU), the University of Florida (UF), and Florida State University (FSU). Academic collaborators bring considerable top-tier expertise to the project table along with centuries of applicable experience, as well as high-caliber students, relevant resources, and infrastructure. Through the CSER partnership, healthy collaborative synergies have formed that now provide us with the ability to collect and process extremely rich, dense spatial data and fusion derivatives in highly compressed timelines as compared to traditional data acquisition procedures. By leveraging RESTORE Act funds early in the THS1 Project process, we have positioned additive resources that permit us to develop next generation forest mensuration technology efficiently and effectively. Consequently, we have discovered that many of the newly developed acquisition and processing techniques and systems integration components rarely exist elsewhere. Early in the CSER partnership, this effort was greatly facilitated by two Microsoft Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Earth grants, which enabled CSER and our partners to mature repeatable workflows that apply AI to novel spatial data in standalone or cloud-based ecosystems with collocated workflow code repositories and data. This effort saves time by collocating computational resources to quickly streamline and automate workflows which can then be applied recurrently to multiple datasets without having to reinvent the process each time when a need arises. Moreover, our partners at UF have contributed extensive experience configuring and deploying Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS) globally, often in extreme conditions while repeatedly delivering on complex data collection and processing commitments. The combination of these partners, techniques, and resources presents unique opportunities to further advance and apply elaborate data fusion workflows that integrate contextual information from the surrounding target landscapes. It also provides opportunities for all participating members to join our efforts, particularly to attract students who are interested in becoming future high-technology natural resource managers and data scientists.

In September 2021, the USDA Forest Service and the University of Florida established the Partnership for Remote Inventory, Status and Management (PRISM) by leveraging funds from the

⁵ Translational Data - information translated into knowledge and action to benefit the world.

⁶ Transformable Data - information transformed into alternative or higher forms such as multi-dimensional analogues (hypercubes) that can be created when merging collocated, simultaneously captured imagery and lidar datasets from an array of positionally-calibrated optical sensors.

Supplemental Appropriations for Disaster Relief Act, 2019. PRISM was established through a challenge cost share agreement to collect, process, and analyze drone-based LiDAR and imagery data to aid in post-disaster recovery as well as restoration and monitoring. This initial agreement focuses specifically on the western half of the Apalachicola National Forest that was impacted by Hurricane Michael.

PRISM data collection is led by the UF Spatial Ecology and Conservation (SPEC) lab utilizing the GatorEye XL platform (Figure 8.8.1). This effort is directed and managed by Dr. Almeyda Zambrano, who also leads mission logistics, data pre-processing, and quality control. Dr. Eben Broadbent supports PRISM through integration of new hardware and workflow development.

Figure 8.8.1. The GatorEye XL flight platform, a hybrid battery-gas powered system with flight times exceeding 2 hours with a 13-pound payload (Image by P. Medley, USFS, 2023).

At the end of this initial 3-year partnership (2021-2024), PRISM will have collected drone-based LiDAR and imagery over approximately 350,000 acres of the Apalachicola National Forest using a block and grid system (Figure 8.8.2). In addition to visual (RGB) imagery, thermal and hyperspectral imagery will also be collected over approximately 25% (~88,000 acres). Lidar data products include flight line point clouds as well as colorized point clouds and ultra resolution raster derivatives such as digital surface models (DSMs), digital elevation models (DEMs), and canopy height models (CHMs) shown in Figure 8.8.3. In total, PRISM is expected to collect approximately 600 terabytes (TB) of data.

Figure 8.8.2. PRISM data collection block and grid system developed for the western half of the Apalachicola National Forest. Total area to be covered is approximately 350,000 acres (547 sq. mi.).

Figure 8.8.3. Examples of bare earth digital elevation model (DEM) and canopy height model (CHM) for PRISM. These products will be created from pre- and post-damage lidar data to determine damage impact and capture change over time.

Drs. Zambrano and Broadbent are also creating additional (bonus) products that add tremendous value to the partnership. For example, 2018 and 2020 airborne laser scanning (ALS) data are being made available for each grid cell. GatorEye and ALS datasets (from different USGS vendors) are also meticulously aligned using the same horizontal and vertical datums to facilitate reliable change detection and monitoring efforts. Preliminary comparisons of 2018 ALS and 2022 PRISM point clouds combined with field visits reveal that PRISM data can be used to detect even minor damage (e.g., mortality of a single tree) as well as moderate to heavy damage (e.g., groups of trees or whole stands) from natural disasters such as hurricanes and wildfires (Figure 8.8.4). Drone-based colorized lidar point clouds and ultra-resolution imagery also hold tremendous potential for rapid assessment of forest damage (Figure 8.8.5) and can be extremely useful for assessing post-hurricane damage to infrastructure such as forest roads, bridges, recreation areas, etc. (Figure 8.8.6)

PRISM would almost certainly not have been created were it not for our Tate’s Hell Strategy 1 (THS1) planning project. THS1, allowed CSER and SPEC lab to collaborate on pioneering drone-based workflows to rapidly assess hurricane damage (Figure 7.2.1, Section 8.7, Prata et al., 2020, and Prata et al., In prep), and these workflows have been leveraged and greatly expanded through PRISM. In turn, ARRI 2&3 will also benefit tremendously from the unprecedented, ultra-density baseline data collected for PRISM over areas that will be treated over the 5-year project. Revisits from both field and GatorEye XL after treatments (i.e., timber thinning, prescribed fire, and hydrologic improvements) have occurred will provide unparalleled monitoring data to document treatment effectiveness.

Figure 8.8.4. Left- 2018 airborne lidar point clouds, Middle- 2022 PRISM point clouds and Right- field photos for areas with light and heavy forest damage from Hurricane Michael and a subsequent wildfire (Field Images by J. Drake, USFS, 2023).

Figure 8.8.5. Colorized (RGB) PRISM lidar point clouds showing damage from Hurricane Michael and a subsequent wildfire.

Figure 8.8.6. Ultra-resolution colored lidar point cloud (top) and visual (RGB) image of flooded bridge over Black Creek, located NE of Sumatra, FL on Apalachicola NF Forest Road 181-C.

References

- Prata, G.A., E. Broadbent, J. St. Peter, J. Drake, P. Medley, A.M.M Zambrano. 2023. Assessing Hurricane Michael impacts on Apalachicola National Forest using multi-sensor, multi-platform remote sensing fusion. In preparation.
- Prata, G., E. N Broadbent, D. Almeida, J. St. Peter, J. Drake, P. Medley, A. P. Dalla Corte, J. Vogel, A. Sharma, C.A Silva, A. Zambrano, R. Valbuena and B. Wilkinson. 2020. "Single-pass UAV-borne GatorEye LiDAR sampling as a rapid assessment method for surveying forest structure." *Remote Sensing*. 12(24), 4111; <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12244111>

9 Summary and Conclusions

The Tate's Hell Strategy 1 (THS1) Ecological and Hydrological Restoration Planning Component has unveiled multiple findings that underscore the potential for enhancing freshwater resources across the Apalachicola Region's wetlands, aquifers, water bodies, and the Gulf of Mexico. This collaborative project identified and prioritized critical hydrologic and ecological restoration opportunities throughout the Region. This is of vital importance primarily because the Apalachicola Region is a major source of clean freshwater for the Gulf, an international biodiversity hotspot, and a significant landscape for longleaf pine restoration. Several high priority restoration opportunities identified in this project will be targeted in the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI) Strategies 2 & 3, and many others will be addressed in future ARRI phases.

The overarching objective throughout this project has been to establish reliable and repeatable workflows for assessing hydrologic and ecological conditions and for prioritizing restoration opportunities by employing novel geospatial data, tools, and solutions. This encompasses field-based workflows designed to assess forest conditions (Section 3.1) and hydrologic infrastructure (Section 3.2). This objective extends to geospatial workflows created to quantify hurricane damage to forests (Section 4.1), map forest structure (4.2), predict current ecological conditions (4.3), estimate potential water yield (4.4), enhance hydrologic flow paths (4.5) and to improve riparian buffer estimates (4.6). Notably, this effort has contributed to the development of multiple peer-reviewed spatial data assets and data-centric workflows, poised to support decision-making for land managers. Furthermore, these outcomes establish a baseline for monitoring within ARRI and will also be used to evaluate the effectiveness of future ARRI and other restoration activities.

The achievements described in this report would not have been attainable without the innovative and collaborative partnerships forged and leveraged in this project. The USDA Forest Service and Florida A&M University's Center for Spatial Ecology and Restoration (CSER) played an essential role throughout this endeavor. CSER closely collaborated with experts from the USDA Forest Service Research (Rocky Mountain Research Station and Southern Research Station), Florida Natural Areas Inventory, Florida Forest Service, University of Florida Spatial Ecology and Conservation lab, Chesapeake Conservancy, Microsoft, and numerous other partners to develop and refine the workflows and geospatial products detailed in this report. These partners also aided in disseminating project datasets and workflows through annual reports, peer-reviewed papers, story maps, online repositories[‡], and other channels. Furthermore, through CSER and other partnerships, the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council's \$2.5 million investment in the THS1 Planning Component has been supplemented with over \$6.7 million in direct and in-kind partner contributions. This has allowed the project to expand in depth and breadth to incorporate new innovations such as drone laser scanning (DLS) which has proven to be an invaluable and cost-effective assessment and monitoring tool.

In total, the THS1 Ecological and Hydrological Restoration Planning Component encompassed the characterization of approximately 5 million acres of habitat in the Florida Panhandle at multiple scales. This involved identifying riparian wetlands, assessing stand-level ecological conditions, evaluating

forest structural metrics, estimating potential water yield gains, and more. Throughout this process, lidar data emerged as a cornerstone in conservation and restoration efforts, with DLS data collection showcasing considerable potential for creating datasets rich in resource information. The fusion of data has unequivocally emerged as a pivotal approach for enhancing forest health analysis, storm damage assessments, and hydrologic and wildlife habitat modeling, in addition to understanding forest structure and condition. The techniques pioneered in the THS1 Project have broad applicability, particularly in the Gulf Coast Region of the U.S., and many are transferable to other regions as well. Together, these endeavors have not only made significant contributions to ecological and hydrological restoration efforts but have also played a crucial role in educating and training the next generation of natural resource managers who are adept in high-technology spatial analysis skills.

To summarize, the prospects for Spatial Information Systems Technologies (SIST) in domains like ecology, restoration, conservation, and land management are exceedingly positive. SIST has been rapidly evolving, offering unparalleled capacities for spatial data analysis, storage, manipulation, and visualization. Its potential uses are on the verge of further expansion, establishing a crucial role in natural resource and forestry management, particularly considering recent advancements in artificial intelligence. Beyond its traditional functions in mapping and inventorying, SIST is anticipated to become an integral component of monitoring, planning, decision-making, and collaborative efforts. As technology continues to advance, SIST is expected to grow more sophisticated and adept, positioning itself as a vital tool for supporting sustainable land management. The ongoing refinement of these technologies will enhance their capabilities and make them even more versatile, ensuring their relevance in addressing the multifaceted challenges of resource management. In essence, SIST's trajectory points towards a future where it becomes a smarter, more comprehensive, and central instrument in the pursuit of maintaining and conserving our natural landscapes for generations to come.

10 Acknowledgements

We thank the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration (RESTORE) Council for their generous support of this project through an Interagency Agreement with the U.S. Forest Service (17-IA-11083150). The visionary leadership of the USDA Forest Service, National Forests in Florida, and the continued support from Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Team and USFS Southern Region have made these initiatives possible. We greatly appreciate the generous support from the administration, faculty, and staff of Florida A&M University who helped create and maintain the Center for Spatial Ecology and Restoration (CSER) which not only played a central role in this project but will also be a vital part of the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative (ARRI) - Strategies 2 and 3. We would also like to thank our many other collaborators and stakeholders who have contributed to and supported this work, including Florida Natural Areas Inventory, Florida Forest Service, Drs. John Hogland and Nate Anderson (USFS Rocky Mountain Research Station), USFS Southern Research Station's Center for Aquatic Technology Transfer (CATT), Dr. Johnny Grace of the USFS SRS Florida Forest Watershed Research Program, USDA Natural Resource Conservation Service, The Nature Conservancy, University of Florida, Chesapeake Conservancy, Northwest Florida Water Management District, Southern Aquatic Resource Partnership, Microsoft, the USGS, and all of our many partners and collaborators.

Recommended Citation

Medley, P., Drake, J., St. Peter, J., Vernon, J., Hogland, J., Battle, B., Broadbent, E., Zambrano, A., Ibeanusi, V., Chen, G., Prata, G., Crandall C., Wu, Y., Abood, S., Awowale, E., Prasai, R. (2023). Tate's Hell Strategy 1 Ecological and Hydrological Restoration Planning Component: Phase 1 of the Apalachicola Regional Restoration Initiative. Center for Spatial Ecology & Restoration (CSER) at Florida A&M University. Final Report to the Gulf Coast Ecosystem Restoration Council, 181 pp.